

Développement d'instrumentation pour la radioastronomie

Development of Instrumentation for Radioastronomy

Habilitation à Diriger la Recherche
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Résumé

Le développement de récepteurs pour la radioastronomie est une activité qui englobe plusieurs domaines techniques pour réaliser un système qui doit guider le rayonnement astrophysique depuis l'espace à travers une chaîne électronique vers des détecteurs et les analyseurs de signaux pour enfin être visualisé et analysé par l'astronome. Mes activités de recherche lors de ma carrière ont touché plusieurs aspects du développement d'instrumentation pour l'astronomie, pour un nombre de projets, et principalement pour des expériences en cosmologie observationnelle.

Abstract

The development of receivers for radio astronomy involves a number of technical domains in order to have a system which brings the electromagnetic signal from space through to the telescope, antenna, and various electronics before arriving at the system of signal processing and ultimately, analysis by the astronomer. I have worked in several of these domains for a number of instruments, and most often for instruments designed for observational cosmology.

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Je suis très reconnaissant aux rapporteurs et membres du jury d'avoir consacré un temps de travail non-négligeable pour mon HDR ! C'est un honneur pour moi d'avoir comme membres du jury Françoise Combes, et Jean-Loup Puget, et comme rapporteurs Frédérique Gadot, Étienne Parizot, et Juan Macías Pérez.

Mon HDR est soumis un peu tardivement dans ma carrière, mais c'est vraiment depuis que je suis membre du laboratoire APC que je me suis senti encouragé à le faire. Dans ce laboratoire je me trouve dans un environnement académique de très haut niveau, rempli de collègues sympathiques et à la pointe de la recherche et dans lequel je suis vivement invité à poursuivre la recherche. Je tiens donc tout d'abord à remercier la direction de l'APC, et en particulier le très regretté Stavros Katsanevas qui m'a accueilli dans le laboratoire en 2017, et Ken Ganga pour son accueil dans le groupe Cosmologie. Je suis également reconnaissant aux successeurs de Stavros, d'abord Sotiris Loucatos, et maintenant Antoine Kouchner, pour maintenir l'ambiance à l'APC qui est tellement propice à la productivité scientifique.

Quand Stavros a accepté ma mutation vers APC, il m'a dit que c'était à condition que je travaille sur QUBIC. J'en étais très heureux, et je le suis toujours ! QUBIC poursuit un objet qui est actuellement la cible d'un énorme effort global dans le monde scientifique, mais QUBIC entreprend le double défi de faire une mesure cosmologique difficile, et de le faire avec une technologie novatrice. Je suis très heureux d'être membre de l'équipe QUBIC, non-seulement pour l'intérêt scientifique et technologique du projet, mais pour y avoir trouvé une ambiance tellement positive. Je remercie Jean-Christophe Hamilton et Michel Piat qui m'ont accueilli dans la famille comme un frère. Ensuite, Louise Mousset a été la première étudiante de thèse pour laquelle j'étais co-directeur de thèse à l'APC, et elle a beaucoup contribué à mon encadrement comme encadrant de thèse ! Je remercie aussi Guillaume Stankowiak, et notre thésard actuel Mathias Regnier, et enfin, tous les membres de l'équipe QUBIC à l'APC : d'abord mon compagnon d'HDR Damien Prêle, Manuel Gonzalez qui a démarré le contrôle/commande de QUBIC, Laurent Grandsire, Jie Hu, Jean-Pierre Thermeau, Pierre Chaniel, Fabrice Voisin, et Claude Chapron. Merci à tout le monde pour les *Friday beers*, pas toujours forcément le vendredi !

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1 Introduction

La motivation pour le développement de technologie pour entreprendre une expérience quelconque est normalement la volonté de comprendre un aspect de la nature, ou de confirmer, ou infirmer, une théorie de la physique. Parfois cette logique est renversée, et c'est l'existence d'une technologie qui inspire une nouvelle expérience pour faire une découverte scientifique. C'est le cas, par exemple, de la technologie électronique de haute résolution temporelle et la découverte de pulsars dont l'existence n'avait jamais été postulée auparavant. J'ai travaillé dans les deux cas, avec le développement d'instruments pour une expérience particulière, et avec l'adaptation de la technologie existante pour des expériences astronomiques.

C'est la cosmologie, dans son sens le plus élargi, qui est la motivation principale de mes activités scientifiques et techniques. La cosmologie est l'étude de l'Univers dans son ensemble. On parle souvent de l'origine et les premiers instants de l'Univers, mais la cosmologie est aussi l'état actuel de l'Univers : la géométrie de l'espace-temps, la forme et distribution de matière dans l'Univers, l'identification des diverses formes de matière et d'énergie dans l'Univers, et le lien entre la structure actuelle et l'évolution de structures au cours de l'histoire de l'Univers.

Ce document est organisé en 5 parties. Cette introduction continue avec un aperçu des motivations scientifiques dont le fond diffus cosmologique et les oscillations acoustiques de baryons. Ensuite, je présente quelques notions de bases sur l'analyse des télescopes en astronomie et le principe de synthèse d'ouverture. Un relevé des projets en ordre chronologique est élaboré dans la Section 2. Le résumé de mes activités d'enseignement est présenté dans la Section 3. La direction des futurs projets de recherches est exposée dans la Section 4. Pour la sélection de publications qui se trouve dans la Section 5 (page 30), chaque publication est précédée par un résumé en français. Ceci est suivi d'un bibliographie (page 109) des publications auxquelles j'ai participées comme auteur ou co-auteur (indiqués en gras). Il y a aussi quelques publications dans lesquelles mon rôle a été reconnu dans les remerciements. Enfin, le résumé de ma carrière est présenté dans mon *curriculum vitae* qui se trouve dans la Section 7 (page 119).

1.1 Le fond diffus cosmologique

Depuis sa découverte, le fond diffus cosmologique continue à fournir de l'information sur l'Univers primordial avec des études de plus en plus approfondies de ce rayonnement. L'idée de l'Univers extrêmement dense et chaud dans le passé lointain a été inspirée par la théorie de relativité générale d'Einstein (1915). L'Univers en expansion a été prédit indépendamment par Friedmann (1922) et Lemaître (1927), et constaté par Hubble (1929) d'après les observations de Slipher (1917). Gamow (1946) a introduit l'idée de remonter dans le passé et a conclut que l'Univers en expansion aujourd'hui implique un passé plus petit, et donc très dense et très chaud. Cette température de l'Univers doit pouvoir être observée, ce qui fut le cas enfin quand Penzias and Wilson (1965) ont mesuré le fond diffus

cosmologique pour la première fois.

D'abord, la simple constatation de l'existence de ce rayonnement est généralement acceptée comme la preuve de l'idée de l'Univers en expansion avec une origine dans le passé. L'Univers n'est pas éternel et immuable. Ensuite, les études du fond diffus cosmologique ont permis le développement d'une théorie cosmologique de plus en plus sophistiquée.

Le fond diffus cosmologique est le rayonnement d'une époque particulière de l'histoire de l'Univers, comme un cliché photographique d'un moment dans le passé. C'est à ce moment que l'Univers a refroidi à une température où les particules libres, protons et électrons, deviennent suffisamment peu énergétiques pour se combiner et former la matière neutre, principalement les atomes d'hydrogène neutre. Après cette époque, que l'on appelle l'époque de recombinaison, les photons sont libres de traverser l'espace, sans être empêchés par le plasma primordial. La cartographie du ciel en ondes millimétriques autour de 2 mm de longueur d'onde est effectivement une image de l'Univers à l'époque de recombinaison.

Malgré le fait que l'image du rayonnement fossile est l'image d'un moment particulier dans le passé, cette image contient les indices de ce qui s'est passé avant. La nature uniforme du fond diffus cosmologique, à une précision d'un part pour cent mille, est l'indication d'une phase d'équilibre thermodynamique précédente dans l'évolution de l'Univers. Cette phase permet à la température du fond d'être partout la même, et ceci même si les endroits sont si éloignés les uns des autres qu'il n'y a pas moyen de communiquer entre eux. On conclut qu'il y a eu une phase d'expansion exponentielle avant l'époque de recombinaison que l'on appelle « Inflation » (Starobinskiĭ 1979; Guth 1981; Linde 1982).

Une autre information primordiale est donnée par la mesure des anisotropies dans l'image du fond diffus. Même à très faible niveau, ce phénomène est l'indication des oscillations acoustiques de baryons qui existaient dans le plasma primordial avant l'époque de recombinaison. Ces endroits de surdensité sont les germes à l'origine de toute la structure de l'Univers actuel, de la plus grosse jusqu'à la plus petite y compris les amas de galaxies, les galaxies, les systèmes stellaires, les planètes, et les êtres humains entre autres. C'est l'Inflation qui fournit un mécanisme pour générer ces endroits de surdensité (Mukhanov and Chibisov 1981; Mukhanov 2013).

Enfin, un dernier paramètre du rayonnement diffus cosmologique est sa polarisation. La nature parfaitement thermique de l'époque de recombinaison ne donnerait aucune préférence de l'angle de polarisation du rayonnement fossile. Par contre, il y a des mécanismes qui provoquent un alignement préférentiel du champ électromagnétique du rayonnement fossile. A l'époque de recombinaison, les oscillations acoustiques de baryons induisent une polarisation de type « mode-E » par l'effet de dispersion des électrons par les protons dans le plasma primordial. Peu avant cette époque, d'éventuelles ondes gravitationnelles provoqueraient un alignement de la polarisation du type « mode-B » (Seljak and Zaldarriaga 1997). Ces ondes gravitationnelles primordiales seraient le fruit de l'expansion exponentielle de l'Univers pendant l'époque d'Inflation.

1.2 Energie sombre et les oscillations acoustiques de baryons

Les oscillations acoustiques de baryons dans le plasma primordial de l'Univers, peu après le Big Bang, doivent imprimer une signature dans le spectre de puissance du fond diffus cosmologique (Eisenstein and Hu 1998). Les oscillations acoustiques ont créé des endroits plus et moins denses dans le plasma primordial et ces régions de surdensité sont les germes de la structure dans l'Univers. La signature des oscillations acoustiques de baryons est observée dans la distribution des anisotropies du fond diffus cosmologique. On doit aussi retrouver cette signature dans la distribution de matière dans l'Univers tout au long de son histoire, et cela sera toujours lié à une échelle physique définie par les oscillations acoustiques de baryons dans le plasma primordial (Blake and Glazebrook 2003). Ce résultat attendu a été confirmé par le projet « Sloan Digital Sky Survey » pour la structure à l'époque entre $z = 0.6$ et $z = 1.0$ (Gil-Marín et al. 2020). La mesure de cette signature à différentes époques dans l'histoire de l'Univers donne l'évolution de l'expansion de l'Univers. C'est la clef pour dévoiler le mystère de l'énergie sombre et c'est pourquoi c'est l'un des projets clef du projet « Square Kilometre Array » (voir par exemple Torchinsky 2009; Acero et al. 2017, Section 2.1.7).

1.3 Considérations optiques

Mon implication dans le développement d'instruments pour astronomie est souvent dans le domaine de la conception optique et le traitement de données. Le traitement de données est d'abord pour caractériser, valider et étalonner l'instrument. Je présente ici quelques notions de base en optiques qui jouent un rôle majeur dans la conception d'un instrument pour l'astronomie, et dans l'interprétation scientifique des données. Il s'agit de l'analyse des antennes, du concept de modes de propagation, et pour la radioastronomie, du concept d'un réseau phasé, et enfin, la synthèse d'ouverture.

1.3.1 Théorème de l'antenne

On cite souvent le théorème de l'antenne qui est simplement la relation :

$$A\Omega = \lambda^2 \quad (1)$$

dans laquelle A est la surface de l'ouverture du télescope, Ω est l'angle solide sur le ciel visible par le télescope, et λ est la longueur d'onde du rayonnement. Malgré sa simplicité, ce théorème est souvent mal appliqué. Notamment, on a tendance à confondre la puissance de rayonnement arrivant sur l'ouverture du télescope avec la puissance détectée par les sondes placées au foyer du télescope. Le rapport entre ces deux paramètres est une expression du rendement du télescope.

L'analyse des antennes s'appuie très souvent sur le principe d'équivalence en électromagnétisme. Au lieu de commencer l'analyse depuis la source pour calculer le signal reçu par une antenne, on fait le contraire, et on considère l'antenne comme un émetteur de

signal pour calculer le signal qui serait arrivé à l'endroit de la source. On appelle cela le profil de l'antenne et on peut le comprendre comme le signal qui serait parfaitement couplé à l'antenne. C'est à dire, c'est le signal que l'antenne est capable de recevoir. Le principe d'équivalence repose sur le principe qu'un champ électromagnétique à un endroit génère un champ ailleurs. On peut donc définir une surface entre la source et l'antenne, et le champ électromagnétique à cette surface généré soit par la source, soit par l'antenne en tant qu'émetteur, est le même dans les deux cas. Il suffit de faire la convolution des deux champs sur cette surface imaginaire pour calculer le signal véritablement capté par l'antenne. Le principe d'équivalence en électromagnétisme est aussi appelé le « principe d'équivalence des surfaces ». Une explication rigoureuse se trouve, par exemple, dans Balanis (2012), et aussi sur Wikipedia¹.

Pour la dérivation du théorème de l'antenne, on commence avec la définition de *brillance de surface*, ou *intensité*. L'intensité I_ν est la *puissance par unité de surface de la source, par l'angle solide de l'ouverture du télescope vue depuis la source, par bande-passante*. (Fig. 1 (gauche)). En invocant le principe d'équivalence, on peut également exprimer l'intensité comme la *puissance par unité de surface de l'ouverture du télescope, par l'angle solide de la source vue par le télescope, par bande passante*. (Fig. 1, droite).

Figure 1: La géométrie pour la définition de brillance, du point de vue du télescope vu par la source (gauche) et du point de vue de la source vue par le télescope (droite).

À partir de cette définition de l'intensité, I_ν , on peut calculer la puissance arrivant sur l'ouverture du télescope. C'est l'intégrale de la puissance rayonnée par la surface de la source visible par l'angle solide du télescope :

$$P = \Delta\nu \int_0^{\theta'_0} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[\int_0^{\theta_0} \int_0^{2\pi} I_\nu R^2 \sin\theta d\phi d\theta \right] \sin\theta' d\phi' d\theta'. \quad (2)$$

R est la distance entre l'ouverture du télescope et l'élément de surface rayonnant de la source (Fig. 1) (*c.à.d.* depuis l'élément de surface $R^2 \sin\theta d\phi d\theta$). On considère ici le cas

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Surface_equivalence_principle

d'une source parfaitement uniforme sur sa surface, comme le fond diffus cosmologique (négligeant les variations de 10^{-5}). On arrive à la relation :

$$P = \Delta\nu I_\nu A_S A_T / R_0^2 \quad (3)$$

R_0 est la distance entre le centre de l'ouverture du télescope, A_T , et le centre de la surface rayonnante de la source, A_S (voir Fig. 1). On considère, pour simplifier, que ces deux surfaces sont circulaires et que le faisceau du télescope est carré, parfois appelé un faisceau haut-de-forme (*top hat beam* en anglais). Le faisceau du télescope peut maintenant être exprimé en termes de la surface rayonnante de la source, A_S et la distance entre le télescope et la source. C'est l'angle solide de la source vue par le télescope (voir Fig. 1) : $\Omega_S = A_S / R_0^2$. On peut maintenant substituer Ω_S dans Eq. 3 :

$$P = \Delta\nu I_\nu A_T \Omega_S \quad (4)$$

Pour un rayonnement purement thermique, sans polarisation, autrement dit du bruit blanc, l'intensité dans une bande passante suit la loi de Planck. Aux basses fréquences, on peut utiliser l'approximation de Rayleigh-Jeans :

$$\Delta\nu I_\nu \simeq 2kT_B / \lambda^2$$

ou k est la constante de Boltzmann. Il est utile de définir un terme que l'on appelle la température de l'antenne, T_A . C'est simplement la puissance mesurée par le télescope mais exprimée en terme d'une température à la façon de l'approximation Rayleigh-Jeans du rayonnement thermique :

$$P \equiv 2kT_A.$$

Ensuite,

$$T_A = T_B A_T \Omega_S / \lambda^2. \quad (5)$$

Pour résumer, la température T_A est un paramètre mesuré lié à l'intensité détectée par le télescope. La température T_B est la température de brillance de la source. L'ouverture du télescope a une surface de taille A_T et l'angle solide vu par le télescope est Ω_S . Enfin, λ est la longueur d'onde du rayonnement.

Dans le cas idéal d'une source de rayonnement parfaitement thermique et uniformément distribué dans le ciel, et avec un télescope qui est parfaitement couplé avec le signal du ciel, *c.à.d.* $T_A = T_B = \text{constant}$, Eq. 5 devient :

$$1 = A_T \Omega_S / \lambda^2 \quad (6)$$

ce qui est le théorème de l'antenne : $A\Omega = \lambda^2$ (Eq. 1).

Il faut bien noter que la dérivation du théorème de l'antenne dépend des simplifications. Le faisceau du télescope est considéré « haut-de-forme » et parfaitement couplé au signal du ciel. Le théorème d'antenne est donc une expression du couplage *maximal* d'un télescope au rayonnement céleste. On peut maintenant définir la *surface effective*,

A_e , du télescope qui est inférieur à la surface physique. Dans cette forme, le théorème de l'antenne, Eq. 1 est valable pour n'importe quel télescope :

$$A_e \Omega_S = \lambda^2. \quad (7)$$

Ainsi, le théorème de l'antenne dans la forme de l'Eq. 7 est toujours valable, et le rapport entre la *surface effective* et la surface physique devient une expression du rendement du télescope, souvent appelé le rendement de l'ouverture (*aperture efficiency* en anglais) :

$$\eta_{ap} = A_e/A_T. \quad (8)$$

Le produit $A\Omega$ est appelé « l'étendue » du télescope. Il est souvent cité dans les analyses optiques, mais il faut faire attention à ce qu'il n'y ait pas d'ambiguïté à ce que l'on entend par A . Le théorème d'antenne, Eq. 1 n'est valable que pour la *surface effective* de l'ouverture.

La motivation pour l'introduction du paramètre A_e n'est peut-être pas évidente. La motivation vient de l'analyse électromagnétique des antennes à basses fréquences. Par exemple, pour un simple antenne en forme de dipôle, il n'y a pas une « ouverture » physique par laquelle traverse le rayonnement. Il est utile dans ce cas de parler d'une ouverture, ou d'une surface, « effective », et on la définit avec le théorème de l'antenne. Dans l'exemple d'un dipôle au sol qui a un faisceau sensible à un quart du ciel (π steradians), la surface effective est $A_e = \lambda^2/\pi$.

Pour un télescope optique, on voit très bien ce qu'est l'ouverture du télescope. Elle est simplement donnée par la taille du miroir primaire, et la puissance totale arrivant sur la surface de l'ouverture du télescope est donnée par l'expression de l'Eq. 4 dans laquelle on utilise la surface physique et non pas la surface effective. Si on préfère utiliser le concept de « l'étendue » avec la surface physique de l'ouverture, il faut modifier le théorème de l'antenne par le facteur η_{ap} :

$$A_T \Omega_S = \frac{1}{\eta_{ap}} \lambda^2 \quad (9)$$

Depuis une dizaine d'années, dans quelques publications d'instruments conçus pour les observations du fond diffus cosmologique (de Bernardis et al. 2009; Kogut et al. 2011; Kusaka et al. 2012, entre autres), on voit ce facteur $1/\eta_{ap}$ remplacé par un simple n et il est interprété comme le nombre de « modes de propagation ». C'est une interprétation erronée. On voit comment cette interprétation est trompeuse quand on remplace Eq. 9 dans l'expression de puissance (Eq. 4) :

$$P = \frac{1}{\eta_{ap}} \Delta\nu I_\nu \lambda^2. \quad (10)$$

Si le facteur $1/\eta_{ap}$ est remplacé par n et interprété comme le nombre de modes de propagation, on a tendance à conclure que la puissance arrivant à l'ouverture du télescope augmente avec le nombre de modes de propagation. C'est faux. Il faut plutôt comprendre

que la puissance est *partagée* parmi les modes de propagation. On ne peut pas utiliser Eq. 9 pour déterminer le nombre de modes qui propagent. Le nombre de modes est déterminé par la géométrie du guide d'ondes. Le fait que le facteur $n = 1/\eta_{ap}$ n'est pas forcément un entier est un indice clair que cela ne peut pas être le nombre de modes. Avant d'aborder davantage ce sujet, il faut présenter le concept de « modes de propagation » qui est le sujet de la prochaine section.

1.3.2 Modes de propagation dans un guide-d'ondes circulaire

Dans le domaine spectral autour d'une longueur d'onde d'environ 1 mm, un composant classique pour détecter le rayonnement arrivant au foyer du télescope est le cornet-antenne suivi d'un guide-d'ondes circulaire. Le guide-d'ondes est suivi d'une chambre d'intégration où on met une sonde, souvent un bolomètre, pour absorber le rayonnement.

Le guide-d'ondes est souvent un simple cylindre métallique (voir Fig. 2), et la distribution des champs électriques-magnétiques est calculée à partir des équations de Maxwell et

Figure 2: La géométrie d'un guide-d'ondes cylindrique.

les conditions aux limites : 1) que le champ électrique parallèle de la surface conductrice est nul, et 2) le champ magnétique normal de la surface conductrice est nul.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} &= 0 & \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{H} &= 0 \\
 \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} &= -\mu \frac{\partial \vec{H}}{\partial t} & \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} &= \varepsilon \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

On peut recombinaer les équations de Maxwell, Eq. 11, dans la forme de l'équation des ondes, et on peut simplifier le problème en choisissant les coordonnées pour aligner l'axe z avec la direction de propagation, qui est aussi l'axe du cylindre (voir Fig. 2). Ensuite, on peut séparer le problème en deux parties : le champ aligné avec l'axe de propagation, dite « normal », et le champ transverse de l'axe de propagation. Pour l'axe de propagation, les champs électriques et magnétiques doivent satisfaire l'équation :

$$\nabla^2 E_z - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} t = 0, \quad (12a)$$

$$\nabla^2 H_z - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} t = 0, \quad (12b)$$

et les champs transverses sont liés aux champs normaux par

$$\vec{E}_\perp = \frac{1}{\mu\varepsilon\omega^2 - k^2} \left[-i\mu\hat{z} \times \vec{\nabla}_\perp H_z + ik\vec{\nabla}_\perp E_z \right] \quad (13a)$$

$$\vec{H}_\perp = \frac{1}{\mu\varepsilon\omega^2 - k^2} \left[i\varepsilon\omega\hat{z} \times \vec{\nabla}_\perp E_z + i\mu k\vec{\nabla}_\perp H_z \right]. \quad (13b)$$

$\omega = 2\pi\nu$ est la fréquence exprimée en radians par seconde. ε est la permittivité électrique, et μ est la perméabilité magnétique. La vitesse de la lumière dans le vide est $c = 1/\sqrt{\varepsilon\mu} \equiv 299792458 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

Pour une géométrie avec symétrie cylindrique, comme le guide d'ondes dans cet exemple, la variation temporelle et la variation dans l'axe de propagation sont indépendantes de la distribution du champs transversal. Cela nous permet d'écrire la solution dans la forme :

$$\Psi(r, \theta, z) = \psi(r, \theta) e^{i(kz + \omega t)} \quad (14)$$

où le ψ est, soit le champs électrique $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$, ou le champs magnétique $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}$.

Les solutions de l'Eq. 13 sans champ magnétique dans la direction de propagation sont appelées *Transverse Magnetic* (TM) et les solutions sans champ électrique dans la direction de propagation sont les *Transverse Electric* (TE). Dans un cylindre avec une surface conductrice parfaite, les solutions sont des combinaisons linéaires des fonctions de Bessel, J_n :

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{\text{TE}} &= \left(\frac{-\omega a}{2\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} + J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{x} \\ &+ \left(\frac{-i\omega a}{2\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} - J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{y} \end{aligned} \quad (15a)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{nm}^{\text{TE}} &= \left(\frac{ika}{2\mu\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} - J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{x} \\
&+ \left(\frac{-ka}{2\mu\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} + J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{y} \\
&+ \frac{1}{\mu} J_n \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{in\theta} \hat{x}
\end{aligned} \tag{15b}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{\text{TM}} &= \left(\frac{ika}{2\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} - J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{x} \\
&+ \left(\frac{-ka}{2\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} + J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{y} \\
&+ J_n \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{in\theta} \hat{x}
\end{aligned} \tag{16a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{nm}^{\text{TM}} &= \left(\frac{-\omega a \varepsilon}{2\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} + J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{x} \\
&+ \left(\frac{i\omega a \varepsilon}{2\gamma_{nm}} \right) \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} - J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{y}
\end{aligned} \tag{16b}$$

a est le rayon du cylindre, Pour les modes TE_{nm} , γ_{nm} est le $m^{\text{ième}}$ zéro de la dérivée première de la fonction de Bessel d'ordre n , et pour les modes TM_{nm} , c'est le $m^{\text{ième}}$ zéro de la fonction de Bessel d'ordre n . Le premier mode est le TE_{11} avec $\gamma_{11}^{\text{TE}} = 1.84118$ et le deuxième est le TM_{01} avec $\gamma_{01}^{\text{TM}} = 2.40483$.

Le nombre d'onde, ou répérence, dans le guide d'ondes est

$$k = (\omega/c) \sqrt{1 - (\gamma_{nm}/\gamma)^2} \tag{17}$$

où l'on défini γ comme un paramètre de fréquence sans dimension. C'est simplement lié à la fréquence et au rayon du guide d'ondes par la relation :

$$\gamma = \omega a / c. \tag{18}$$

La puissance dans chaque mode est le vecteur de Poynting intégré sur la coupe transversale du guide d'onde :

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{P}_{nm} &= \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr \left| \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{nm} \times \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{nm}^* \right| \\
&= A_{nm} \int_0^1 \rho d\rho \left[J_{n-1}^2(\gamma_{nm}\rho) + J_{n+1}^2(\gamma_{nm}\rho) \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

où on a fait la substitution $\rho = r/a$. Les coefficients A_{nm} peuvent être choisis pour normaliser la puissance dans chaque mode. Cette normalisation est nécessaire pour faire l'analyse de « couplage de mode » (*mode matching* en anglais) que l'on utilise pour calculer la forme de rayonnement après avoir traversé une interface, comme, par exemple, l'ouverture d'un guide-d'ondes vers l'espace libre.

Un exemple particulier est le couplage vers le rayonnement d'une source ponctuelle. La diffraction à l'ouverture donne la tache d'Airy au champ électromagnétique. On trouve que le meilleur couplage est avec le premier mode, le TE_{11} . Les modes d'ordres plus élevés, avec multilobes ou asymétries, sont moins conformes à la tache d'Airy, et ils nuisent au couplage à la source ponctuelle. C'est pour cette raison que les cornet-antennes avec guide d'ondes circulaire sont conçus en général, pour ne transmettre qu'un seul mode de propagation (*single moded* en anglais). C'est pour avoir le meilleur rendement de l'ouverture, η_{ap} .

On a développé ici les modes de propagation dans un guide d'onde cylindrique, mais il n'y a pas de contraintes sur la géométrie d'un guide d'ondes. On utilise des guide d'ondes rectangulaires, et on peut aussi mettre des corrugations dans la surface, ou bien ajouter une couche de matériel diélectrique, ou bien, avoir un fil conducteur co-axial. Plusieurs cas sont analysés dans Marcuvitz (1986). Pour chaque variation de géométrie et paramètres électriques, les modes sont différents et pas forcément décrits par les fonctions de Bessel. Le nombre de modes qui se propagent dans le guide d'onde varie avec la configuration du guide d'ondes, et c'est ce pourquoi l'étendue du télescope toute seule ne suffit pas pour déterminer le nombre de modes qui se propagent dans le guide d'onde par derrière.

Lors de la section précédent (1.3.1) il a été mentionné que le facteur $n = 1/\eta_{ap}$ n'est pas forcément un entier. Pour éviter le conflit avec le principe fondamental d'un nombre entier de modes de propagation, on peut inventer le terme « nombre de modes effectif ». Ce terme n'a pas vraiment de sens. Il faut reconnaître que la logique qui mène à l'idée de modes de propagation est exactement la même qu'on utilise, par exemple, pour expliquer l'énergie de transition des molécules de gaz. Les molécules de différentes espèces ont chacune ses modes de vibrations et rotations. En sautant d'un mode vers un autre moins énergétique, la molécule émet un rayonnement d'une énergie définie par la différence entre les deux modes. C'est l'origine du spectre qui est la signature de différents espèces de matière. Ainsi on peut identifier, par exemple, le monoxyde de carbone ou l'ammoniaque dans le milieu interstellaire. On ne parle jamais de « modes effectifs d'énergie », ou l'équivalent, « fréquence effective de rayonnement ». Il n'y a pas de niveau d'énergie accessible entre modes, et par le même raisonnement, il n'y a pas un « nombre de modes effectif ». Le nombre de modes est forcément un entier.

1.3.3 Multimodes

Le cas multimode a été introduit dans Torchinsky (1990) pour l'analyse d'un nouveau instrument à l'époque, appelé SCUBA, qui a fonctionné au foyer du télescope James-Clerk-Maxwell pendant plusieurs années. On voulait toujours optimiser le rendement de

l'ouverture, mais, à la fois, on voulait utiliser le même système à très large bande spectrale. Le paramètre γ augmente avec la fréquence, et donc, aux fréquences les plus élevées de la bande, les modes des ordres au delà du TE_{11} peuvent se propager dans le guide d'ondes. L'analyse pour SCUBA calculait la dégradation due aux multimodes.

Les modes d'ordres élevés sont mal couplés au rayonnement d'une source ponctuelle, mais une source thermique, et largement étendue, peut exciter tous les modes qui se propagent dans le guide d'ondes. Dans le cas d'une source thermique et étendue, comme, par exemple, le fond diffus cosmologique, tous les modes qui peuvent se propager dans le guide d'ondes sont également excités par la source étendue et parfaitement thermique. C'est à dire que toute la puissance de la source thermique qui arrive sur l'ouverture est partagée parmi les modes capables de se propager dans le guide d'ondes. Ce principe a été exprimé dans **Torchinsky** (1990) et la même idée a été reprise peu après dans Murphy and Padman (1991).

Malheureusement, par la suite, vers 2009, un malentendu s'est introduit dans la littérature, et l'on fait la mauvaise interprétation que l'étendue du télescope, en fonction de la longueur d'onde, donne le nombre de modes qui se propagent (de Bernardis et al. 2009). C'est d'abord une mauvaise interprétation de l'Eq. 10, déjà mentionnée dans la Section 1.3.1. Ensuite, il faut comprendre que la puissance de rayonnement qui arrive sur l'ouverture du télescope est indépendant du nombre de modes qui se propagent par la suite. Enfin, cette puissance est partagée parmi les modes qui se propagent dans le guide d'ondes. Le facteur $n = 1/\eta_{ap}$ n'est pas le nombre de modes. C'est simplement l'inverse du rendement de l'ouverture.

1.3.4 Réseau phasé et synthèse d'ouverture

Deux techniques en radio astronomie que l'on confond souvent sont les réseaux phasés et la synthèse d'ouverture. Ils se basent sur le même principe, mais l'implémentation est différente. Un réseau phasé devient l'équivalent d'un grand radiotélescope qui fait une mesure d'un point dans le ciel, c.à.d. un « pixel » dans le ciel. La synthèse d'ouverture permet la création d'un cliché d'un champ-de-vue avec plusieurs pixels.

Réseau Phasé

Le principe d'un réseau phasé est illustré Fig. 3. Deux antennes visent la même source qui est à une très grande distance. Un front-d'onde est détecté par une antenne avant l'autre. Il y a un délai, τ_g , que l'on appelle le délai géométrique. Cela est défini par la séparation, D , entre les deux antennes, et l'angle de visé, θ :

$$\tau_g = \frac{D}{c} \sin\theta \quad (20)$$

Le but d'un réseau phasé est de combiner les signaux détectés par chaque antenne. Le plus simple, conceptuellement, est de faire l'addition des signaux. On peut compenser le

Figure 3: Une source ponctuelle à très grande distance vue par deux antennes. Quand la source se déplace, par exemple vers l'horizon (image de gauche vers image de droite) le temps de retard entre la réception du signal aux deux antennes change aussi. Ce délai est compensé par un câble plus ou moins long.

délat entre la détection aux deux antennes avec une longueur de câble. Avant de combiner les signaux, le signal de la première antenne doit d'abord traverser un câble avec une longueur égale à $D \sin \theta$. Ainsi la détection du signal est synchronisée entre les deux antennes.

Un réseau phasé fait la combinaison de plusieurs antennes, et la sensibilité du réseau augmente avec le nombre d'antennes. Le réseau devient l'équivalent en sensibilité d'une grande parabole avec une surface aussi grande que la somme des surfaces des antennes constituant le réseau. La résolution angulaire dépend de la séparation la plus large entre antennes. Ce qui donne une résolution plus fine que celle que l'on aurait avec une simple parabole.

Pour chaque ligne de visée dans le ciel, il faut mettre en place le câble avec la longueur qui convient à la direction nécessaire. Un tel système est réalisable avec des relais qui basculent le signal des différentes antennes à travers les câbles qui conviennent pour une direction de visée donnée. Un exemple de ce genre de système est le réseau décimétrique de l'Observatoire de Nançay, construit dans les années 1970.

Une solution alternative est de remplacer les câbles avec des circuits intégrés qui appliquent une modification de la phase du signal à chaque antenne. C'est une solution électronique plus compacte et plus commode avec l'avantage de pouvoir modifier plus facilement la synchronisation des signaux pour pouvoir changer la direction de visée du réseau rapidement. L'inconvénient est le fait que le circuit électronique qui fait la modification de phase est forcément contraint à une bande passante spectrale restreinte. Néanmoins, cette solution permet la réalisation d'un réseau à très grande échelle comme EMBRACE avec ses 4608 antennes (Torchinsky et al. 2016b, reproduit à la page 62).

Synthèse d'ouverture

Le traitement de signal pour faire la synthèse d'ouverture est plus complexe que celui

pour un réseau phasé, mais le résultat est une image d'une région étendue du ciel au lieu de simplement une mesure d'un point dans le ciel. Le développement présenté ici est librement inspiré de Thompson et al. (2017). La géométrie est illustrée Fig. 4. Elle est semblable à la configuration pour le réseau phasé (Fig. 3) mais on définit ici un système de coordonnées avec un point de référence dans le ciel que l'on appelle la référence de phase (*phase tracking reference* en anglais), et, par tradition, les coordonnées au sol sont nommées u, v, w avec u vers l'est, v vers le nord, et w vers le zénith.

Figure 4: La géométrie simplifiée d'un réseau d'antennes pour faire la synthèse d'ouverture.

Il sera utile d'exprimer le délai de réception du signal en unités de longueur d'onde. Ceci se fait en divisant Eq. 20 par la longueur d'onde, λ . La séparation entre les deux antennes, exprimée en nombre de longueurs d'onde, est $D_\lambda = D/\lambda$. Eq. 20 devient :

$$\nu\tau_g = D_\lambda \sin\theta \quad (21)$$

En général, dans le cadre de la géométrie de la Fig. 4 avec la référence de phase, on écrit Eq. 21 en termes de produit scalaire des vecteurs de position du télescope, \vec{D}_λ , et de la ligne de visée dans le ciel, \vec{R} :

$$\nu\tau_g = \vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R} = \vec{D}_\lambda \cdot (\vec{R}_0 + \vec{\sigma}) \quad (22)$$

À la place d'une sommation des signaux reçus par chaque antenne que l'on a fait pour le réseau phasé, ici on va multiplier les signaux, ce qui est plus efficace, et plus commode

à implémenter électroniquement. Le résultat est la corrélation entre les signaux des deux antennes. Le corrélateur fournit une réponse proportionnelle au produit des deux signaux :

$$F \propto \sin 2\pi\nu t \sin 2\pi\nu(t - \tau_g) \quad (23)$$

Avec l'application de quelques identités trigonométriques, on trouve :

$$F \propto \cos 2\pi\nu\tau_g - \cos 4\pi\nu t \cos 2\pi\nu\tau_g - \sin 4\pi\nu t \sin 2\pi\nu\tau_g \quad (24)$$

Pour une ligne de visée donnée, le délai géométrique, τ_g est constant. Dans ce cas, le premier terme de l'Eq. 24 est constant tandis que les autres varient rapidement. Même en suivant la source lors de son trajet dans le ciel, la variation du premier terme est négligeable par rapport aux autres. Ainsi, les derniers termes sont facilement filtrés et on peut simplifier Eq. 24 par l'expression :

$$F = \cos 2\pi\nu\tau_g \quad (25)$$

Le paramètre F de l'Eq. 25 est appelé la fonction de frange (*fringe function* en anglais).

La puissance reçue par chaque antenne depuis un élément du ciel est calculée, comme pour le développement du théorème de l'antenne (Section 1.3.1, Fig. 1, et Eq. 4). Ici, on l'exprime en termes des coordonnées avec le point de référence de phase indiqué par le vecteur \vec{R}_0 à la Fig. 4 :

$$dP = A_e(\vec{\sigma})I(\vec{\sigma})\Delta\nu d\Omega \quad (26)$$

La multiplication des signaux reçus par les deux antennes donne la réponse du corrélateur dans laquelle on retrouve la fonction de frange (Eq. 25). L'angle de visée est maintenant exprimé en terme du produit scalaire des vecteurs position, comme on a fait pour le délai géométrique (Eq. 22). Le calcul ici est fait pour une direction de visée, mais le pointage d'une antenne n'est pas infiniment fin. Une antenne a un faisceau qui reçoit le rayonnement principalement de la direction de visée, mais elle a une sensibilité, moindre, aux rayonnements venus d'autres direction. Cette sensibilité en fonction de la direction de rayonnement, $A(\vec{\sigma})$, est appelée le profil de l'antenne. Pour prendre en compte la réception de rayonnement de toutes les directions, pour un pointage donné, il faut faire une intégration sur les 4π steradians de tout le ciel :

$$r(\vec{D}_\lambda, \vec{R}_0) = \Delta\nu \int_{4\pi} A(\vec{\sigma})I(\vec{\sigma}) \cos \left[2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot (\vec{R}_0 + \vec{\sigma}) \right] d\Omega \quad (27)$$

Dans l'intégrale de l'Eq. 27 on peut sortir les termes qui ne dépendent pas du pointage dans le ciel. On applique encore une identité trigonométrique et la réponse du corrélateur devient :

$$\begin{aligned} r(\vec{D}_\lambda, \vec{R}_0) &= \Delta\nu \cos(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R}_0) \int_{4\pi} A(\vec{\sigma})I(\vec{\sigma}) \cos(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{\sigma}) d\Omega \\ &\quad - \Delta\nu \sin(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R}_0) \int_{4\pi} A(\vec{\sigma})I(\vec{\sigma}) \sin(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{\sigma}) d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Il sera utile de définir une quantité que l'on appelle la visibilité, en s'inspirant de l'intégrale dans l'Eq. 28 :

$$\mathcal{V} = |\mathcal{V}| e^{i\phi} = \int_{4\pi} A(\vec{\sigma}) I(\vec{\sigma}) e^{-i(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{\sigma})} d\Omega \quad (29)$$

Ensuite, Eq. 28 est exprimée en termes cette visibilité :

$$r(\vec{D}_\lambda, \vec{R}_0) = \Delta\nu \cos(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R}_0) |\mathcal{V}| \cos \phi + \Delta\nu \sin(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R}_0) |\mathcal{V}| \sin \phi \quad (30)$$

et on applique à nouveau l'identité trigonométrique pour $\cos(a + b)$:

$$r(\vec{D}_\lambda, \vec{R}_0) = \Delta\nu |\mathcal{V}| \cos(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R}_0 - \phi) \quad (31)$$

On voit dans l'Eq. 31 la fonction de frange dans la direction \vec{R}_0 , $F = \cos(2\pi\vec{D}_\lambda \cdot \vec{R}_0 - \phi)$.

Pour les coordonnées dans le ciel, on utilise les projections de direction l, m (*direction cosines* en anglais). Ce sont des vecteurs d'amplitude unité avec direction relative à la référence de phase (*phase tracking position*). La géométrie est montrée Fig. 5 (gauche et droite) et les projections de direction en termes du plan u, v sont les suivants :

Figure 5: Les projections de direction pour un point dans le ciel. À gauche : Les coordonnées dans le ciel sont l et m avec m vers le pôle. À droite : l'orientation des projections de direction par rapport au système de coordonnées u, v .

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \cos \psi \\ l &= \sin \psi \cos \delta_u \\ m &= \sin \psi \cos \delta_v \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Le produit scalaire des vecteurs dont on a besoin est maintenant exprimé en termes des projections de direction :

$$D_\lambda \cdot R = ul + vm + wn = ul + vm + w\sqrt{1 - l^2 - m^2} \quad (33)$$

et l'angle solide $d\Omega$ est :

$$d\Omega = \frac{dl \, dm}{n} = \frac{dl \, dm}{\sqrt{1 - l^2 - m^2}} \quad (34)$$

Le produit scalaire entre le vecteur des positions des antennes dans le plan $u - v$ et le vecteur de la référence de phase est simplement w :

$$D_\lambda \cdot R_0 = w \quad (35)$$

On peut maintenant revenir à la visibilité (Eq. 29) et utiliser les projections de direction l, m :

$$\mathcal{V} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(l, m) I(l, m) e^{-i2\pi(ul+vm+w\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2})} \frac{dldm}{\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}} \quad (36)$$

On va appliquer quelques simplifications pour continuer. D'abord, on considère que l'étendue de l'image est relativement petite, et on peut faire l'approximation que l et m sont petits :

$$w(\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}-1) \simeq -\frac{1}{2}w(l^2+m^2) \quad (37)$$

Ensuite, on considère que les antennes se placent au même niveau, c'est à dire :

$$\mathcal{V}(u, v, w) \simeq \mathcal{V}(u, v, 0) \quad (38)$$

Eq. 36 devient :

$$\mathcal{V} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(l, m) I(l, m) e^{-2i\pi(ul+vm)} \frac{dldm}{\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}} \quad (39)$$

On reconnaît dans l'Eq. 39 la transformée de Fourier, et il ne suffit que de prendre l'inverse pour arriver à la solution des intensités :

$$\frac{A(l, m) I(l, m)}{\sqrt{1-l^2-m^2}} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \mathcal{V} e^{2i\pi(ul+vm)} \, dudv \quad (40)$$

L'image qui résulte de la transformée de Fourier est de bonne qualité dans le cas d'un rapport signal sur bruit très élevé. Ce n'est pas le cas en général pour la radioastronomie. Il y a les imprécisions de chronométrages, ou de phases, entre les antennes, les gains différents entre antennes, et aussi les profils d'antennes, autrement dit, les lobes, d'antennes qui diffèrent entre antennes et qui, éventuellement, varient avec le pointage. C'est pourquoi l'image produite par la transformée de Fourier est baptisée avec l'appellation ignoble « *dirty image* » en anglais. La traduction en français serait, par exemple, « image pourrie », mais on dit simplement « transformée de Fourier directe ».

Il y a des astuces pour corriger, plus ou moins, les sources de bruits. On applique un algorithme de traitement du signal au niveau des mesures des antennes, c.à.d. dans le plan $u - v$. Le plus efficace de ces algorithmes est l'« auto-étalonnage » (*self calibration* en anglais). Pour appliquer cet algorithme, il suffit d'avoir une source forte et ponctuelle

dans le champ de vue de l'image. Dans ce cas, l'étalonnage de l'image peut se faire avec l'image elle-même, d'où le nom « auto-étalonnage » (voir, par exemple, Noordam and Hamaker (2018) dans *50 Years Westerbork*, Strom, van Ardenne, & Torchinsky, eds.).

Interférométrie bolométrique

Le développement précédent pour faire la synthèse d'ouverture ne considère qu'une longueur d'onde, et le résultat n'est donc valable que pour une bande spectrale étroite. Plus la bande spectrale devient large, plus la fonction de frange devient floue, et le résultat est de moins en moins acceptable. De plus, les composants électroniques, comme les amplificateurs et les corrélateurs, sont naturellement performants pour une longueur d'onde donnée. Pour le traitement d'une large bande spectrale en synthèse d'ouverture, en général, on divise la bande en canaux étroits et on a une chaîne électronique pour chaque canal. C'est la solution de « canalisation » (*channelization* en anglais). Cette solution fonctionne bien mais avec une multiplication non-négligeable de composants électroniques analogiques et numériques pour arriver à une bande spectrale très large.

Aux basses fréquences, la canalisation est performante et abordable. Surtout parce que le bruit du système est dominé par le bruit du ciel aux basses fréquences et non par le bruit instrumental. La largeur de bande désirée n'est pas non-plus hors de portée. Aux longueurs d'onde millimétrique, qui correspondent aux fréquences dans les centaines de GHz, la bande passante désirée, par exemple pour les observations du fond diffus cosmologique, est extrêmement large. En outre, dans ce régime spectral, le bruit est dominé par la technologie de détection et non par le bruit du ciel. On utilise des éléments électroniques, comme des bolomètres, qui doivent être refroidis aux températures à quelques milli-Kelvins du zéro absolu, et qui ne sont pas sensibles à la phase du signal. Tout cela rend difficile, voire impossible, la solution de canalisation.

Une autre solution est de faire optiquement la combinaison des signaux. En 1851, Hippolyte Fizeau décrit une configuration d'interféromètre dans laquelle la lumière est divisée pour être dirigée le long de deux tuyaux pour être recombinaée ensuite Fizeau (1851). Le but fut la mesure de la différence, si elle existait, entre la vitesse de la lumière traversant un milieu en mouvement. Les tuyaux avaient de l'eau qui coulait en sens opposé dans les deux tuyaux. Il n'a pas constaté d'interférence entre les deux faisceaux de lumière, et donc la vitesse de la lumière est inchangée par le mouvement du milieu que la lumière traverse.

Inspiré de l'interféromètre de Fizeau, l'instrument QUBIC (voir Sec. 2.3) utilise le même principe de combinaison optique pour implémenter une méthode semblable à la synthèse d'ouverture. Plusieurs cornet-antennes visent la même direction dans le ciel. Le rayonnement capté par les cornets passe ensuite par les guides-d'onde derrière les cornets, pour ensuite ressortir du cornet de l'autre côté du guide-d'onde. Les multiples faisceaux, comme la lumière des tuyaux de Fizeau, sont combinés par un jeu de miroirs et le résultat est mesuré sur une matrice de détecteurs dans le plan focal. L'image captée sur le plan focal est l'équivalent de la transformée de Fourier directe (Eq. 40) décrite plus haut.

La solution optique permet de sauter l'étape de mesures dans le plan $u - v$ pour aller directement vers l'image avec une large bande-spectrale. L'inconvénient est d'avoir sauté aussi la possibilité d'appliquer les algorithmes d'étalonnages dans le plan $u - v$. L'instrument QUBIC a résolu cette limitation en implémentant des écrans individuels pour chaque guide d'ondes dans la matrice de cornets-antennes (l'équivalent des tuyaux dans l'interféromètre de Fizeau). On peut fermer les écrans, sauf deux par exemple, pour faire l'image produite par cette paire de tuyaux. C'est l'équivalent de la corrélation entre deux antennes, c.à.d. une ligne de base, dans la synthèse d'ouverture en radioastronomie. À tour de rôle, on fait les mesures de chaque ligne de base et donc on « revient » aux coefficients de corrélation dans le plan $u - v$. Cela est rendu possible par une source artificielle de rayonnement millimétrique placée assez loin pour être vue comme une source ponctuelle. On fait l'étalonnage avec cette source, et ensuite on applique les corrections de phase et de gain aux observations du ciel.

2 Relevé des projets

Dans cette section, je présente un relevé des projets auxquels j'ai participé par ordre chronologique. Je note les publications qui en sont sorties.

2.1 Radioastronomie millimétrique et sub-millimétrique

2.1.1 JCMT : SCUBA et Spectroscopie hétérodyne

Le récepteur SCUBA pour *Submillimetre Common User Bolometer Array* fut parmi les premiers récepteurs en astronomie submillimétrique avec plusieurs détecteurs dans le plan focal. Il a été opérationnel sur le télescope James Clerk Maxwell à Hawaii pendant plusieurs années. J'ai été membre de l'équipe de développement travaillant principalement à la conception quasi-optique des cornets antennes pour SCUBA (**Torchinsky** 1990, 1991).

Mon intérêt scientifique avec SCUBA était la possibilité de faire un relevé du fond diffus cosmologique, et en particulier de chercher les effets d'avant plan qui pourraient modifier le signal cosmologique. À l'époque, la sonde COBE venait de publier ses résultats montrant un spectre thermique très précisément en accord avec la loi de Planck, et une morphologie extrêmement lisse avec des anisotropies seulement d'un part dans cent mille. Néanmoins, on attendait pouvoir détecter des anomalies dues aux lentilles gravitationnelles, et à l'effet Sunyaev-Zeldovitch qui est la diffusion Thomson des photons du fond diffus cosmologique. On proposait aussi la possibilité de découvrir une population de galaxies primordiales avec SCUBA en étant aidé par une amplification due à l'effet de lentille gravitationnelle par des amas de galaxies en avant plan (voir chapitre 3 dans **Torchinsky** 1991).

Toujours dans le domaine submillimétrique, mais cette fois pour un récepteur spectroscopique, j'ai développé un mélangeur hétérodyne pour des fréquences autour de 690 GHz. À l'époque au début des années 90, il est parmi les premiers récepteurs hétérodyne utilisant des jonctions supraconductrices (SIS junction, *Superconductor-Insulator-Superconductor*) à une fréquence aussi élevée (**Torchinsky** et al. 1993, 1994).

2.1.2 Odin

Le projet spatial Odin est un satellite suédois construit avec la participation de la France, le Canada, et la Finlande (**Torchinsky** et al. 2002; Kwok et al. 2004). Il a été lancé en orbite en 2001 et est toujours opérationnel. Odin est doté de cinq récepteurs dans le domaine spectral millimétrique et submillimétrique conçus dans le but de la détection spectroscopique de molécules, notamment l'oxygène (Larsson et al. 2007) l'eau (Lecacheux et al. 2003), l'ammoniac, et plusieurs autres (Hjalmarson et al. 2003). J'ai été responsable de la conception optique de l'instrument (**Torchinsky** 2000) et j'ai été beaucoup impliqué dans l'intégration, les tests, et la caractérisation de l'instrument avant le lancement (**Torchinsky** et al. 2000; Frisk et al. 2003; Olberg et al. 2003).

2.1.3 Herschel-HIFI et ALMA

La méthode d'analyse pour la conception optique d'Odin a été développée davantage pour faire des propositions d'architecture pour l'instrument HIFI (*Heterodyne Instrument for the Far Infrared*) sur la sonde Herschel Space Observatory (Belitsky and **Torchinsky** 1996; **Torchinsky** and Belitsky 1997; de Graauw et al. 1998; Whyborn et al. 1998), ainsi que pour ALMA (*Atacama Large Millimeter Array*) (Wild et al. 2000).

2.2 Radioastronomie basses fréquences

2.2.1 Arecibo

Le radiotélescope d'Arecibo à Porto Rico était pendant plus de 50 ans la plus grande surface collectrice en astronomie. Ce dernier a été, seulement très récemment, dépassé par le grand radiotélescope FAST en Chine. Arecibo est connu, entre autres, pour la mesure de la radiation par ondes gravitationnelles depuis un système binaire d'étoiles à neutron. Cette expérience qui a démarré en 1974 et couronné d'un prix Nobel pour Hulse et Taylor en 1993.

J'étais le chef de projet pour un nouvel instrument à Arecibo, *Arecibo L-band Feed Array* (ALFA). C'était le premier instrument multi-pixel pour Arecibo, conçu principalement pour faire des relevés du ciel pour cartographier l'hydrogène neutre de la galaxie et des galaxies relativement proches. ALFA était aussi utilisé pour faire des relevés de pulsars. C'est à cette époque que je me suis intéressé aux ondes gravitationnelles et la possibilité d'utiliser un réseau de pulsars pour détecter des ondes gravitationnelles éventuellement primordiales.

J'ai contrôlé les tests d'acceptation chez le fabricant, CSIRO en Australie, avant livraison de l'instrument, et j'ai été ensuite beaucoup impliqué dans l'installation, la mise en opération, et la caractérisation et l'étalonnage de l'instrument. J'ai participé aux premières observations avec l'instrument qui étaient dans le domaine de la recherche de nouveaux pulsars (Lorimer et al. 2006; Cordes et al. 2006; Deneva et al. 2009, mon implication est signalée dans les remerciements).

J'ai participé aux observations de la comète 9P/Tempel 1 avant et après sa collision avec la sonde « *Deep Impact* » le 4 juillet, 2005 (Howell et al. 2005) et le logiciel que j'ai développé pour ALFA continue d'être utilisé pour faciliter les analyses approfondies par la suite (Howell et al. 2007a,b, voir remerciements).

2.2.2 Square Kilometre Array – SKA

Une particularité de la radioastronomie à basse fréquence est le fait que le ciel est plus brillant que les sources individuelles. Si on avait des yeux sensibles au spectre radio, le ciel serait aussi brillant le jour et la nuit. Pour détecter une source de petite étendue et de faible intensité, comme une galaxie lointaine, il faut une très haute sensibilité, et une bonne résolution angulaire. La première difficulté est résolue avec une très grande

surface collectrice. La deuxième, avec un interféromètre étendu. Ainsi est née l'idée de faire un réseau d'antennes pour atteindre un kilomètre carré de surface collectrice. C'est le « *Square Kilometre Array* » (SKA) (pour l'histoire du projet SKA voir par exemple ma contribution dans le French SKA Whitebook Acero et al. 2017, Section 4.2.1).

La motivation scientifique de SKA a été au début principalement le relevé du ciel pour faire un catalogue de galaxies, mais l'immense capacité d'un tel instrument a vite attiré plusieurs idées scientifiques. Entre autres, SKA sera un instrument très puissant pour étudier la cosmologie et la gravitation, avec le relevé d'un milliard de galaxies, et avec les études des étoiles à neutron impulsives (pulsars) pour faire l'équivalent d'un réseau interférométrique mais pour les ondes gravitationnelles.

J'étais le *Project Scientist* pour le projet européen *Square Kilometre Array Design Studies* financé par le Sixième Programme Cadre européen (FP6). Dans ce rôle, il fallait avoir une connaissance de tous les projets scientifiques, et souvent présenter l'ensemble des projets (voir par exemple **Torchinsky** 2009, reproduit dans la Section 5, page 55). Je suis intéressé en particulier par l'énergie sombre et comment SKA peut éclairer ce mystère avec l'analyse des oscillations acoustiques de baryons dans la distribution des galaxies (**Torchinsky** and SKADS Consortium 2007). Mais SKA sera un instrument avec de multiples objectifs, et il faut prendre tout cela en compte pour formuler le cahier des charges de l'instrument (**Torchinsky** et al. 2016a). Un sous-ensemble des objectifs a été visé pour un prototype proposé en 2016. Ce projet, malheureusement jamais financé (van Cappellen et al. 2016), a eu comme but la cartographie par intensité (voir Section 2.2.3) et un relevé de sources impulsives.

Dans le cadre de l'étude européenne SKADS on a mis l'accent scientifique et technologique sur la révolution potentielle qu'offre un instrument capable de faire des grands relevés, profonds, et rapides. Pour ce faire, SKA est conçu avec un immense champ de vue de centaines de degrés carrés, pleinement échantillonné avec une résolution angulaire de quelques dizaines de secondes d'arc. Le volume de données généré sera au delà de toutes les données générées actuellement sur l'internet global.

La réalisation d'un instrument avec ces capacités est possible grâce du développement de l'électronique numérique. Au lieu d'avoir de grandes paraboles, SKA est conçu avec plusieurs millions de petites antennes reliées dans un immense réseau électronique. Le grand nombre d'antennes permet l'échantillonnage du champ de vue avec plusieurs « pixels » et la sensibilité de l'instrument est aussi augmentée par le grand nombre d'antennes. Cette technologie a été développée au cours de l'étude SKADS et présentée au projet international SKA (Bolton et al. 2008; Faulkner et al. 2010), et aussi aux conférences internationales (Faulkner et al. 2008; bij de Vaate et al. 2014). L'ensemble des études menées dans le cadre du projet SKADS est publié dans le livre « *Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA* » (**Torchinsky** et al. 2009).

Un prototype avec quelques milliers d'antennes a été développé et construit. Le prototype s'appelle EMBRACE pour « *Electronic MultiBeam Radio Astronomy ConcEpt* ». EMBRACE est le fruit d'un développement à ASTRON, Pays-Bas, avec une contribution clef de la Station de radioastronomie de Nançay. Notamment, au cœur de l'électronique

d'EMBRACE, il y a un circuit analogique intégré qui fait un traitement du signal en temps-réel pour imposer un déphasage au signal afin de sélectionner le pointage du réseau phasé (Bosse et al. 2010). Ce circuit intégré appelé « *beamformer chip* » faisait partie d'un programme de recherche et développement à la Station de radioastronomie de Nançay (Bosse et al. 2009).

J'étais responsable de la caractérisation d'EMBRACE. L'effort a démarré avec une stratégie rédigée avant l'installation du prototype (Torchinsky et al. 2008). Le plan comprenait des tests techniques ainsi que des observations scientifiques. EMBRACE a été installé d'abord sur le site à Westerbork aux Pays-Bas, et les premiers résultats sont publiés à la fin du projet SKADS en 2009 (Wijnholds et al. 2009; Olofsson et al. 2009).

Le projet s'est poursuivi après la fin du financement européen FP6, le prototype a été installé à Nançay en 2011. J'ai contribué au logiciel de pilotage d'EMBRACE (Taffoureau et al. 2012) avec en particulier l'interface entre l'instrument et l'astronome. J'ai intégré un système pour déterminer la position et la visibilité des sources astronomiques et des sources de calibrations (en général, des satellites GPS émettant en radio band-L). EMBRACE a fait des observations de pulsars, du soleil, du vestige de supernova Cassiopée-A, et de la galaxie Cygnus-A (Torchinsky et al. 2013, 2015). La capacité spectroscopique a été démontrée avec la détection de la galaxie M33 et la mesure de son profil spectroscopique à 21 cm de longueur d'onde montrant la rotation de la galaxie. Enfin, EMBRACE fonctionnait comme un véritable observatoire astronomique avec des observations quotidiennes programmées d'avance. La caractérisation détaillée d'EMBRACE est publiée dans Torchinsky et al. (2016b).

Lors de la rédaction du *EMBRACE Test Plan* (Torchinsky et al. 2008) une idée est évoquée, utiliser EMBRACE pour la détection de molécules. Un sondage du contenu moléculaire est nécessaire pour bien comprendre le milieu interstellaire et l'environnement des étoiles naissantes. On ne peut pas expliquer la formation d'étoiles par un simple modèle de condensation gravitationnelle d'un nuage de matière. L'énergie de reheating avec la compression, et l'énergie du moment angulaire, empêchent le nuage d'atteindre la densité nécessaire pour démarrer la fusion nucléaire. Paradoxalement, il faut des moyens pour extraire l'énergie du nuage avant qu'il puisse devenir une étoile. Pour comprendre le processus, il faut considérer tous les effets en jeu, comme le champ magnétique et le transfert d'énergie au niveau moléculaire, voire jusqu'à comprendre la chimie du milieu. Un sondage du contenu moléculaire est primordial pour comprendre la formation d'étoiles.

Il manque au prototype EMBRACE la sensibilité requise pour entreprendre un relevé moléculaire, mais un projet pilote est mené avec le grand radiotélescope décimétrique de Nançay (Olofsson et al. 2017). Ce projet servait comme stage de Master pour Laure Bouscasse, étudiante à l'Imperial College à Londres. Elle a poursuivi ses études ensuite avec une thèse doctorale à l'institut de radioastronomie Max-Planck à Bonn, et elle est actuellement en *post-doc* à l'Institut de radioastronomie millimétrique (IRAM) à Grenoble.

2.2.3 Energie sombre et les oscillations acoustiques de baryons

Parmi les multiples projets scientifiques prévus pour SKA, le relevé de la distribution d'hydrogène neutre est primordial. L'idée de faire un relevé de galaxies en trois dimensions avec la détection de la transition électronique à 21 cm de longueur d'onde remonte à une cinquantaine d'années (pour un résumé de l'histoire de SKA, voir ma contribution dans Acero et al. 2017, Section 4.2.1). La motivation pour un tel relevé est devenue encore plus pressante depuis la découverte de l'expansion accélérée de l'Univers.

Le SKA propose de faire un relevé d'un milliard de galaxies, avec l'identification des galaxies individuelles y compris leurs positions dans le ciel très précisément déterminées et le décalage vers le rouge cosmologique mesuré en haute précision avec la détection spectroscopique de la raie à 21 cm de longueur d'onde (voir par exemple **Torchinsky and SKADS Consortium 2007**). Ainsi on peut tracer l'évolution de la distribution des galaxies pour retrouver la signature des oscillations acoustiques de baryons pendant la période d'expansion accélérée de l'Univers.

Inspiré par les observations millimétrique du fond diffus cosmologique, il est proposé de faire un relevé du ciel avec le but de cartographier la distribution d'hydrogène neutre mais sans détecter les galaxies individuellement (pour une revue, voir par exemple ma contribution dans Acero et al. 2017, Section 2.1.7). L'idée est de faire effectivement une estimation de la masse d'hydrogène neutre dans un volume d'espace défini par l'étendu angulaire sur le ciel et dans la troisième direction, par une bande passante spectrale correspondant à une gamme de décalage vers le rouge cosmologique. De plus, ce qui importe pour l'analyse n'est pas la masse absolue de chaque volume d'espace, mais la différence entre la masse des différents volumes relevés. L'expérience devient effectivement semblable à l'analyse d'anisotropies dans le fond diffus micro-onde. Ce genre d'expérience est connu sous le terme de « cartographie en intensité ».

Un grand avantage de l'idée de cartographie en intensité est la possibilité de le faire avec un radiotélescope moins sensible que le SKA. Il y a grand un nombre de projets en cours dans le monde conçus pour faire cette expérience. Je suis impliqué dans le projet chinois TIANLAI, ce qui veut dire en chinois « musique du ciel » (Das et al. 2018). TIANLAI est composé de deux instruments indépendants. Il y a un réseau classique de paraboles, et un autre réseau composé de réflecteurs cylindriques qui sont moins coûteux à construire. En France, je suis impliqué dans le projet « Paraboles à Nançay » (PAON) mené par Résa Ansari du laboratoire Irène-Joliot Curie (IJCLAB) qui entreprend la recherche et le développement de technologie adaptés à ce projet (Ansari et al. 2020).

2.3 Le retour aux longueurs d'onde millimétriques – QUBIC

La détection de la polarisation de « modes-B » dans le fond diffus cosmologique sera la preuve expérimentale de la théorie de l'Inflation. Pour cette raison, un énorme effort est en cours dans le monde de la recherche en cosmologie pour mesurer cet effet. Parmi ces projets, il y a QUBIC qui est le « *Q & U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology* »

(Mennella et al. 2017; O’Sullivan et al. 2018a; de Bernardis et al. 2018; Mennella et al. 2019; Battistelli et al. 2020). QUBIC est une collaboration internationale depuis 2008 et est coordonnée par l’APC (CNRS-IN2P3/U. Paris Cité).

J’ai commencé mon implication dans le projet QUBIC en 2017 avec le développement d’un logiciel de contrôle de l’instrument, de l’acquisition, et de l’analyse des données pour caractériser les détecteurs du type « *Transition Edge Sensor* » (Salatino et al. 2018; Piat et al. 2019; Marnieros et al. 2020). Je suis aussi impliqué dans les efforts pour la cryogénie (May et al. 2018), et les considérations optiques (O’Sullivan et al. 2018b; Burke et al. 2018).

Début 2019, on m’a confié la responsabilité de l’étalonnage de QUBIC. Le projet a procédé ensuite à une longue campagne de tests approfondis en laboratoire dans laquelle on a démontré la faisabilité du concept d’interférométrie bolométrique et sa capacité de faire la spectro-imagerie. On a aussi démontré la fonctionnalité générale de QUBIC y compris le système cryogénique, les multiples mécanismes, l’utilisation d’une source de calibration artificielle, et la polarimétrie de très haute pureté ainsi que la capacité de faire la modulation de la polarisation avec la lame demi-onde. Ceci a abouti à la publication du document de calibration (**Torchinsky** et al. 2020) présenté à la revue de projet en janvier 2020.

Par la suite, la collaboration QUBIC a décidé de publier une série de papiers pour la plupart basés sur les résultats de la campagne de test élaborés dans le document de calibration. La motivation scientifique et les performances techniques attendues sont le sujet du premier papier (Hamilton et al. 2022). Le deuxième papier donne les détails de la spectro-imagerie (Mousset et al. 2022). Le troisième expose les résultats de la campagne de tests en laboratoire (**Torchinsky** et al. 2022), et le quatrième se concentre sur les performances des détecteurs (Piat et al. 2022). Ensuite, il y a la cryogénie (Masi et al. 2022), le système de la lame demi-onde (D’Alessandro et al. 2022), le système cornets et ses écrans mécaniques (Cavaliere et al. 2022), et enfin, le système optique de QUBIC (O’Sullivan et al. 2022). Ces papiers sont publiés dans « *Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics* » dans un numéro dédié à QUBIC.

QUBIC a été envoyé en juillet 2021 vers l’Argentine. Depuis août 2021, QUBIC est installé dans un laboratoire à Salta qui est à 150km du site d’observation sur le plateau La Pune à 5000 mètres d’altitude. Les contraintes pendant la pandémie de COVID nous ont obligé à travailler à distance, ce qui impliquait une surveillance par webcam et un accès à distance au système, et, surtout, l’encadrement de l’équipe locale. La haute compétence de l’équipe locale nous a permis de procéder assez rapidement à la réintégration de l’instrument et une répétition des tests qui ont été faits à l’APC. J’ai été pleinement impliqué dans cet effort, travaillant à distance à l’horaire argentin. Nous avons réussi à reproduire les résultats faits à l’APC, ce qui indiquait la bonne santé de l’instrument après son voyage à travers l’océan et plus de 1000km en camion. L’équipe locale à Salta a non-seulement réussi à re-intégrer l’instrument après le voyage, mais elle a aussi effectué des améliorations, notamment pour le système cryogénique et pour la lame demi-onde. Le travail à distance m’a obligé à améliorer le système de contrôle-commande,

et ainsi la pandémie m'a motivé à améliorer l'autonomie de l'instrument. Maintenant, QUBIC est pilotable et gérable avec beaucoup d'autonomie et de fiabilité.

En juillet 2022, toujours dans le laboratoire de préparation à Salta, QUBIC a réussi à faire une observation astronomique. Malgré la localisation non-optimale pour les observations à longueur d'ondes millimétriques, le laboratoire de Salta a ouvert ses portes pour offrir une vue limitée du ciel, mais suffisamment pour observer la lune. Comme pour l'instrument EMBRACE, QUBIC a choisi une technologie totalement novatrice, la développée et faite évoluer jusqu'au niveau pratique d'en faire un instrument scientifique. QUBIC est maintenant prêt pour la prochaine étape qui est l'installation sur le site, prévue pour octobre 2022, et le démarrage des observations scientifiques.

3 Enseignement

3.1 Projets de thèses

Je étais co-directeur de thèse avec Jean-Christophe Hamilton (APC/CNRS) de Louise Mousset. La thèse concerne l'étalonnage de QUBIC, et en particulier, la théorie et l'implémentation de spectro imagerie avec l'interféromètre bolométrique. Elle a beaucoup participé aux campagnes de mesures de QUBIC dans le laboratoire et a contribué à des analyses clés pour comprendre le comportement de l'instrument. Louise a notamment fait les observations des franges des résultants du système de l'interféromètre de Fizeau avec QUBIC, et elle a analysé ce résultat pour pouvoir préciser l'orientation de l'ensemble de cornets. Ce projet de thèse englobe tous les aspects d'un projet en astrophysique : la théorie et modélisation, la conception d'instrumentation, et l'acquisition et l'analyse de données dans le cadre de cosmologie. Louise a été coordinatrice, et a fait la plupart des analyses et rédaction pour la publication portant sur la spectro-imagerie avec QUBIC (Mousset et al. 2022).

Guillaume Stankowiak était étudiant de thèse travaillant sur QUBIC sous la direction de Michel Piat (professeur, UFR de physique, Université Paris Cité) et Jean-Christophe Hamilton. J'ai participé à son encadrement. Le projet de thèse concerne le système d'acquisition de données depuis les bolomètres. Le système est composé d'une partie d'électronique à température cryogénique utilisant des *superconducting quantum interference device* (SQUID) et un circuit intégré conçu par les ingénieurs de l'APC. L'autre partie, dite « chaude », fait l'acquisition numérique des données (voir par exemple Piat et al. 2019). Guillaume a participé à l'implémentation des campagnes de test, et a travaillé sur l'analyse des données. Il est un auteur principal pour la publication au sujet de la caractérisation des détecteurs et du système de lecture pour QUBIC (Piat et al. 2022).

Mathias Regnier a démarré ses études de thèse en septembre 2021 sous la direction de Jean-Christophe Hamilton et moi-même. Son projet de thèse porte sur le développement de l'algorithme pour transformer les données de QUBIC en cartes de ciel, avec, en même temps, la séparation des avants-plans du signal cosmologique. Mathias utilisera les mesures de QUBIC qui sont prises à la volée lors du balayage de l'instrument sur le ciel. Il faut reconstruire la carte du ciel à partir des données temporelles, dites, « *Time Ordered Data* ». La capacité de QUBIC à faire l'imagerie et spectroscopie en même temps permettra la soustraction des signaux parasites, en particulier, la poussière galactique. C'est un avantage considérable de l'instrument QUBIC.

Mathias va aussi travailler sur l'implémentation de l'analyse de l'auto-étalonnage (*self-calibration*). Ce sera la première fois qu'un instrument bolométrique utilisera cette méthode classique de radio-astronomie. La caractérisation de QUBIC sera ensuite à un niveau de précision inégalée parmi les instruments dédiés à la mesure de la polarisation du fond diffus cosmologique.

3.2 UFR de Physique et Ecole d'ingénieur Denis-Diderot

Une série de stages et travaux pratiques sont organisée par Michel Piat. Il a conçu le TP autour d'une expérience en cosmologie pour reproduire la première mesure du fond diffus cosmologique faite par Penzias & Wilson en 1965 et qui leur a conduit du prix Nobel en 1978. Le travail pratique du stage se passe dans une journée pendant laquelle on fait l'observation du ciel avec une parabole installée sur le toit du bâtiment Condorcet de l'Université Paris Cité. Je participe à l'encadrement de ce stage qui consiste à expliquer des concepts de cosmologie et de radioastronomie.

Je participe régulièrement aux jurys de fin de stage pour l'école d'ingénieur Denis-Diderot, aussi organisés par Pr. Michel Piat. Après un stage de six mois dans une entreprise, l'étudiant(e) soumet un rapport d'activité et fait une présentation. Je suis l'« expert externe » pour suivre l'étudiant durant son stage et pour aider Pr. Piat à évaluer l'étudiant(e). Ce stage de fin d'études suivi de l'évaluation est un composant important du cursus de l'école d'ingénieur Denis-Diderot.

3.3 Université Ouverte de l'Université Paris Cité

L'Université Paris Cité organise des cycles de formation destinés au grand public. Je participe au « Cycle du Cosmos » qui est une série de cours présentée par les chercheurs affiliés au laboratoire Astroparticule et Cosmologie (APC). Je me suis occupé d'un cours au sujet de l'histoire de l'hydrogène dans l'Univers **Torchinsky** (2020, 2021).

Mon cours sur l'histoire de l'hydrogène neutre est développé à partir des cours que j'ai donné à l'Institut Universitaire de Bourges de l'Université d'Orléans, et aussi à partir d'un cours de radioastronomie que j'ai donné pour les étudiants « Master » du Poly'Tech d'Orléans. J'ai aussi présenté ce sujet lors de l'école d'été de Goutelas (**Torchinsky** 2011).

Les sujets d'énergie noire, la masse manquante, et radioastronomie ont souvent été abordés lors de mes manifestations « Grand public ». C'est le cas par exemple dans « Dossier pour la Science » (**Torchinsky** and van Driel 2007). J'ai aussi abordé le côté philosophique, avec un peu de légèreté, en abordant la question de l'« avant Big Bang » dans le Bulletin Interne de l'Observatoire de Paris (**Torchinsky** 2014).

4 Futures directions de recherche

4.1 QUBIC

À moyen terme, mes activités de recherche se concentrent sur QUBIC. L'étape de test en laboratoire est le sujet d'une série de publications qui sont publiées dans un volume dédié du *Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics* et le journal associé d'instrumentation, *Journal of Instrumentation*. Je suis fortement impliqué dans la rédaction de la plupart des huit publications. Il s'agit de publications au sujets de la motivation scientifique et la performance prévue de QUBIC (Hamilton et al. 2022), la spectro-imagerie (Mousset et al. 2022), la caractérisation (Torchinsky et al. 2022), la chaîne de détection (Piat et al. 2022), la cryogénie (Masi et al. 2022), la lame demi-onde (D'Alessandro et al. 2022), le système de cornets avec écrans mécaniques (Cavaliere et al. 2022), et enfin la conception optique (O'Sullivan et al. 2022). Les résultats cités dans ces publications sont tirés du document de calibration livré pour la revue du projet en janvier 2020 (Torchinsky et al. 2020).

Tous les efforts jusqu'à présent ont portés sur l'intégration, les tests, et la caractérisation de l'instrument dans les laboratoires. Cela doit aboutir à une véritable prise de données sur le ciel pour pouvoir procéder à l'analyse astrophysique, et enfin une estimation du niveau maximal des « mode-B » de polarisation dans le fond diffus cosmologique. QUBIC, dans son état actuel, est un prototype dit « Démonstrateur Technologique ». Néanmoins, une fois installé sur son site d'observation à 5000 m d'altitude en Argentine, cet instrument sera capable de cartographier une partie du ciel et de procéder à une analyse astrophysique et cosmologique. C'est le sujet de thèse de Mathias Regnier, sous la direction de Jean-Christophe Hamilton et moi-même. La capacité de faire l'imagerie spectrale et le contrôle des effets systematiques avec l'interférométrie s'avèrent très puissants, et seront le moteur de futurs développements en instrumentation pour la détection des mode-B de polarisation du fond diffus cosmologique.

4.2 Le fond diffus cosmologique – « Stage-IV »

Le projet QUBIC se trouve dans le contexte d'un effort global pour le développement d'instruments pour la détection des « modes-B » de polarisation dans le fond diffus cosmologique. C'est la quatrième génération d'instruments, et on appelle cet effort le « *CMB Stage-IV* ». Il y aura notamment une série de télescopes appelée le « *Simons Observatory* » installée sur un plateau à 5000 m d'altitude au Chili qui est dédiée à la recherche de la polarisation « mode-B ».

QUBIC est le seul projet qui exploite l'idée d'interférométrie bolométrique avec tous ses avantages de contrôle et de minimisation des effets systématiques. Ce qui peut de plus jouer un rôle décisif, est la capacité de faire de la spectro-imagerie avec ensuite le filtrage des avant-plans qui nuisent à la détection des « modes-B » de polarisation. Un projet du type QUBIC, mais avec une augmentation conséquente de sa sensibilité, sera proposé pour

le « *CMB Stage-IV* ». Ce projet pourrait rejoindre l'effort Simons Observatory, ou bien, toujours dans le cadre d'une collaboration avec le « Stage-IV », on pourrait envisager une augmentation de QUBIC sur le site en Argentine.

4.3 Le fond diffus cosmologique à haute résolution angulaire

QUBIC vise directement le ciel avec une ouverture effective de 30 cm pour lui donner une résolution angulaire de 0.4° . Cette résolution angulaire est optimale pour étudier le spectre de puissance angulaire autour de $\ell = 100$, ce qui correspond au signal cosmologique de l'Inflation.

Une modification du rayonnement fossile par l'effet de lentille gravitationnelle faible qui se passe de multiples fois au cours du trajet des photons à travers l'Univers peut introduire une polarisation du type « mode-B ». Cette polarisation additionnelle est mélangée avec la polarisation primordiale et les deux sont confondues. Pour séparer les deux effets, il faut faire une analyse à haute résolution angulaire.

Une façon d'augmenter la résolution angulaire de QUBIC serait de mettre l'instrument au foyer d'une grande parabole. Sur le même site où se trouvera QUBIC, il y aura l'observatoire « *Large Latin American Millimeter Array* » qui sera équipé d'une parabole de 12 m de diamètre. Une étude est en cours pour développer l'idée de mettre un interféromètre bolométrique similaire à QUBIC au foyer de LLAMA, ce qui lui donnera une résolution angulaire d'environ 30 secondes d'arc. Avec une telle résolution angulaire, et avec les avantages de la technique d'interférométrie bolométrique, la combinaison LLAMA/QUBIC sera un instrument idéal pour étudier l'effet de lentille gravitationnelle faible.

5 Sélection de publications

Je présente ici une sélection de publications tirée des différentes étapes de ma carrière. Les publications portent sur SCUBA, le satellite Odin, SKA, le prototype SKA-EMBRACE, et QUBIC.

1. Analysis of a conical horn fed by a slightly oversized waveguide.....	31
2. 3d-Quasi-Optical Ray-Tracing for the Odin Radiometer	50
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5.1 Analysis of a conical horn fed by a slightly oversized waveguide

Le projet SCUBA était le premier instrument multi-pixel bolométrique dans le domaine millimétrique/sub-millimétrique. La conception optique est inspirée par la conception d'instruments pour l'infrarouge et le visible. C'est pourquoi on utilisait jusque là le cornet du type « Winston » qui est conçu comme le collecteur idéal de photons. Le profil du cornet Winston est parabolique pour que les rayons arrivant à l'ouverture du cornet de n'importe quelle direction soient réfléchis vers la chambre d'intégration au bout du cornet. C'est une analyse purement géométrique qui ne considère pas la diffraction. Dans ce papier, je présente un analyse « Quasi Optique » qui prend en compte la nature électromagnétique du régime sub-millimétrique et le fait que la taille des composants optiques sont à l'échelle de la longueur d'onde. Il s'agit de la première analyse, dite « multi-mode », dans le domaine des ondes millimétriques. Ce papier a été reconnu dans le volume très cité de Goldsmith (1998). L'analyse « multi-mode » a eu beaucoup d'applications dans l'astronomie millimétrique, notamment pour la sonde Planck (Murphy et al. 2001, 2010).

ANALYSIS OF A CONICAL HORN FED BY A SLIGHTLY OVERSIZED WAVEGUIDE

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Abstract

This paper discusses the case of a submillimetre conical feedhorn system which is overmoded due to an oversized waveguide, but is not in the geometric optics regime. The motivation for this system is to use the same feed as a multi-frequency receiver. Increased background loading is the greatest disadvantage in overmoded optics; and aperture efficiency also suffers due to non-optimum horn dimensions. The analysis is done using the Laguerre-Gauss beam expansion method.

KEYWORDS: OVERSIZED WAVEGUIDE, OVERMODED, CONICAL HORN,
QUASI-OPTICS

1 Introduction

Nearly thirty years ago Taub *et al.* [1] established the viability of using oversized waveguides. In that work an oversized circular waveguide was shown to propagate a TE_{11} beam mode without significant attenuation over a long distance. Note that although the guide was oversized, it was not overmoded. More recently, Crenn [2], and Belland & Crenn [3] have considered the problem of an oversized and overmoded circular waveguide, in which a Gaussian beam is propagated through the guide. Theirs is an analysis in the geometrical limit, and also a "slightly diffracted" beam. The present paper investigates the problem of a very diffracted beam (the horn is fed by a *slightly* oversized waveguide).

Feedhorn for incoherent detectors are generally designed to focus the maximum available power onto a bolometer which then absorbs it, regardless of phase. Often, the horn used to focus energy on the bolometer is an "Ideal Light Collector"

or Winston Cone [4,5]. However, optimization of aperture efficiency and reduction of unwanted background power entering the system requires the use of single moded optics. Hence, at submillimeter wavelengths, the antenna is a single moded feedhorn. The conical horn has the problem of differing E and H plane profiles and somewhat non-Gaussian antenna beam profile. This is normally overcome by corrugating the feed resulting in a highly Gaussian field with suppressed sidelobes [6,7]. Unfortunately, manufacturing corrugated feeds for use in the submillimeter waveband is extremely difficult due to their small dimensions, and this is especially prohibitive when many horn antennæ are required. This paper addresses the problem of aperture and beam efficiency in a conical feedhorn system for use in a total power detector.

Presently at the Royal Observatory, Edinburgh, a new receiver is being built for the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope (JCMT) on Mauna Kea, Hawaii. The Submillimetre Common User Bolometer Array (SCUBA) was originally intended to be a two-channel imaging array for simultaneous observations at 350 GHz ($855\mu\text{m}$) and 685 GHz ($438\mu\text{m}$). However, the astronomical community soon expressed disappointment that the receiver would not also take advantage of two other observing windows that Mauna Kea can offer: 428 GHz ($700\mu\text{m}$) and 857 GHz ($350\mu\text{m}$). Two options were proposed to give SCUBA this added flexibility. The possibility of including two additional arrays (four altogether) was quickly rejected as this would require complicated optics in order to split the beam into four paths. Instead, SCUBA now has a filter carousel which will allow the astronomer to choose the waveband at which she will observe[8]. Each array of bolometers is designed to have optimum efficiency at the original frequencies of 350 GHz ($855\mu\text{m}$) and 685 GHz ($438\mu\text{m}$) respectively. The added channels will operate at a non-optimum design, on the first two arrays, and thus the feeds at 428 GHz ($700\mu\text{m}$) and 857 GHz ($350\mu\text{m}$) will be overmoded.

Section 2 addresses the problem of synthesizing the field profile of the horn using cylindrical waveguide modes for the "source" functions and Gaussian beam analysis to find the far-field profile. The aperture efficiency and beam, or spillover efficiency, are discussed in Section 3, also using Gaussian beam analysis, and Table 2 lists the efficiencies of the waveguide modes for the particular case of $855\mu\text{m}$ conical feedhorn used at both its designed wavelength of $855\mu\text{m}$ and also at $700\mu\text{m}$. Section 4 discusses signal measurement, using a typical astronomical source as an example. The overall conclusion seems to be that the less than optimum efficiencies in the overmoded optics are still sufficient to make overmoded optics a viable method of increasing the flexibility of a receiver, if one is willing to lose out in terms of background loading. For the particular case of SCUBA, the filter carousel is a valid solution to the problem of increasing the instrument from a two to a four-waveband receiver.

2 Profile Synthesis

The far-field horn profile is determined using the method described by Ludwig [9] in conjunction with Gaussian beam analysis [10]. The usual TE_{nm} and TM_{nm} cylindrical waveguide modes are considered the "source functions" which are then components of the far field profile. Laguerre-Gaussian beam mode analysis is very useful for determining beam truncation and beam profile throughout an optical train. For these reasons, L-G beams are employed in this analysis instead of simply Fourier transforming the horn field to get the far-field profile through a telescope.

The electric fields of the TE_{nm} and TM_{nm} modes are the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{TE} = & \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} + J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{\mathbf{x}} \\ & + \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} - J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{\mathbf{y}} \end{aligned} \quad (1a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{TM} = & \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} - J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{\mathbf{x}} \\ & + \left[J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta} + J_{n+1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n+1)\theta} \right] \hat{\mathbf{y}} \\ & + J_n \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{in\theta} \hat{\mathbf{z}} \end{aligned} \quad (1b)$$

The power in each cylindrical wave mode is the integrated Poynting vector over the cross section of the guide:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{nm} &= \frac{1}{\pi a^2} \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr \bar{\mathbf{e}}_{nm} \times \bar{\mathbf{h}}_{nm}^* \\ &= \int_0^1 \rho d\rho \left[J_{n-1}^2(\gamma_{nm}\rho) + J_{n+1}^2(\gamma_{nm}\rho) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (1c)$$

and this will be used to normalize each waveguide mode to unit power. For the TE_{nm} modes, the γ_{nm} are the m^{th} zero of the first derivative *w.r.t.* the argument of Bessel function order n , and for the TM_{nm} modes they are the m^{th} zero of Bessel function order n .

The exact field distribution within the guide is a linear combination of the TE_{nm} and TM_{nm} fields. For a conical horn of small flare angle, the field at the horn mouth can be taken as the waveguide field propagated as a spherical wave from

Figure 1: The Conical Feedhorn System

the horn exit to the horn mouth. This gives the usual conical horn approximation of

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{\text{horn}} &= \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{\text{guide}} \exp(ikr^2/2L) \\ &= \sum_n \sum_m A_{nm} \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{\text{TE}} \exp(ikr^2/2L) + \sum_n \sum_m B_{nm} \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{\text{TM}} \exp(ikr^2/2L) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where k is the free space wave number $2\pi/\lambda$, and L is the axial length of the horn (see Figure 1).

Equation 2 is referred to as the “source” functions for generating the antenna beam profile [9]. The A_{nm} and B_{nm} are the Fourier coefficients of the field distribution in terms of the cylindrical waveguide modes, *viz.*

$$A_{nm} = \left\langle \bar{\mathcal{F}}_s \left| \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{\text{TE}} \exp(-i\frac{kr^2}{2L}) \right|_{\text{farfield}} \right\rangle \quad (3a)$$

$$B_{nm} = \left\langle \bar{\mathcal{F}}_s \left| \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{nm}^{\text{TM}} \exp(i\frac{kr^2}{2L}) \right|_{\text{farfield}} \right\rangle \quad (3b)$$

$\bar{\mathcal{F}}_s$ is the field of the emitting source in the far-field of the telescope. The far-field profile of Eq. 2 are determined by L-G beam expansion

$$\Psi_{nm} = N_{nm} \left(\frac{2r^2}{W^2} \right)^{n/2} L_{nm} \left(\frac{2r^2}{W^2} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{r^2}{W^2} + i\frac{kr^2}{2R} + i\Phi + in\theta + ikz \right) \quad (4a)$$

where the Laguerre polynomials are given by the generating function

$$L_{nm}(\zeta) = \frac{e^\zeta}{(n+m)!} \frac{d^m}{d\zeta^{n+m}} (e^{-\zeta} \zeta^m), \quad (4b)$$

and

$$W = W_o \sqrt{1 + (\lambda z / \pi W_o^2)^2}, \quad (4c)$$

$$R = z \left[1 + (\pi W_o^2 / \lambda z)^2 \right]. \quad (4d)$$

W_o is the beam waist radius which occurs at the focus of the L-G beam ($z = 0$), and Φ is the phase slippage, in addition to that of a spherical wave, relative to the fundamental L-G mode,

$$\Phi = (2m + n) \text{Tan}^{-1} (z\lambda / \pi W_o^2). \quad (4e)$$

N_{nm} normalizes the functions such that the power in a L-G beam mode is unity. That is,

$$1 = \int_0^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr 2\Psi_{nm} \cdot \Psi_{nm}^*$$

which yields the recursive result $N_{nm}^2 = n! \sum_{q=0}^m N_{n-1,q}^2$ with $N_{0m}^2 = 1/\pi W^2$.

The best fit L-G beam occurs when $R = L$, and choosing $W = 0.768a$ maximizes the power in the fundamental L-G mode [11]. This is a convenient choice because it means that fewer L-G modes are required to accurately describe the waveguide modes. The Bessel functions of the horn fields are now expressed as the summation of the L-G functions:

$$J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) e^{i(n-1)\theta + i\frac{kr^2}{2L}} = \sum_{p=0}^\infty \sum_{q=0}^\infty C_{pq} \Psi_{pq},$$

from which it follows that

$$C_{pq} = \frac{N_{pq}}{P_{nm} \pi a^2} \int_0^\infty \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr \left(\frac{2r^2}{W^2} \right)^{n/2} L_{pq} \left(\frac{2r^2}{W^2} \right) J_{n-1} \left(\gamma_{nm} \frac{r}{a} \right) \times \exp \left(-\frac{r^2}{W^2} - i\frac{kr^2}{2R} + i\frac{kr^2}{2L} + i(n-1)\theta - ip\theta \right) \quad (5)$$

The phase slippage (Eq. 4e) is contained within the C_{pq} . Clearly, from Eq. 5 the

C_{pq} are trivial unless $p = n - 1$. Similarly, the coefficients of the $n + 1$ terms in the horn field (Eq. 2) are determined.

The present analysis considers a feed to be “slightly” overmoded if a few of the cylindrical waveguide modes propagate unattenuated through the waveguide. For example, the feeding waveguide has radius a_g , which, at a given frequency of radiation, supports the first three modes: The TE_{11} , the TM_{01} , and the TE_{21} . That is, the dimensionless frequency of radiation, $\gamma = a_g\omega/c$, is within the range $3.054 < \gamma < 3.832$ (at which point the TE_{02} and TM_{11} modes propagate. See Table 1).

Table 1: **Beam Mode Cut-off**

Mode	$\gamma_{\text{cut-off}}$
TE_{11}	1.84118
TM_{01}	2.40483
TE_{21}	3.05424
TE_{02}	3.831706
TM_{11}	3.83171

Table 2 lists the first 21 L-G coefficients (C_{n-1m} , C_{n+1m}) for each the TE_{11} , TM_{01} , and the TE_{21} waveguide modes. The total power in the first m modes up to 21 is also listed. Note that after 21 L-G modes 98.4% of the TE_{11} power is included; over 100 modes would have to be summed before 99.5% of the power would be included [11] (see Figure 2). The aperture and spillover efficiencies listed in Table 2 will be discussed in the next section.

Figure 2: The aperture and spillover efficiencies computed are plotted against the number of L-G modes included in the sum (Eq. 11 and Eq. 12). P_m is the amount of power included in the first m L-G modes. Twenty modes is enough to get a reasonable estimate of efficiency. This example is for the case of the infinite length horn ($\varphi = 0$) in the focal plane of the telescope.

Figure 3: The aperture efficiencies of three conical horns in the telescope focal plane are compared. Each is assumed to be fed by a single moded waveguide when the horn has maximum aperture efficiency ($a_m = F\lambda$ when $\gamma = a_g\omega/c = 2.1$ in all three cases). The three horns are the infinite horn ($\varphi = 0^\circ$), the horn discussed in the text ($\varphi = 4.67^\circ$), and an optimum horn [12] (horn of maximum gain for a given length; here, in comparison with the horn discussed in the text, the optimum horn of the same length would have flare angle $\varphi = 8.58^\circ$).

3 Efficiencies

3.1 Aperture Efficiency

The aperture efficiency is the ability of the antenna to couple to a point source on the sky. A point source at infinity produces a plane wave at the telescope aperture and its field profile therefore has no azimuthal (θ) dependence. Hence, only a feedhorn profile also having such a 'symmetric' profile can couple to the point source. Of the first three cylindrical wave modes (Table 1), only the TE_{11} can contribute to the aperture efficiency. The point source field is diffracted into the Airy pattern at the focal plane,

$$\vec{E}_s = \frac{J_1(gr)}{gr} \hat{x}, \quad (6)$$

where J_1 is the Bessel function of first order, $g = \pi/F\lambda$, and F is the f/D ratio of the telescope (here it is assumed to be a Gaussian Beam Telescope, wherein all lenses or mirrors are separated by the sum of their focal lengths[13,14]). An ideal aperture efficiency can be calculated by coupling the point source field directly to the horn field. This results in the maximum possible aperture efficiency which would be attained with perfect optics. The Fourier coefficients of Eq. 1 are then

$$A_{11} = \frac{1}{\pi a^2 P_{11}^{TE}} \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr \frac{J_1(gr)}{gr} J_0\left(1.841 \frac{r}{a}\right) \quad (7)$$

The other coefficients of the first few waveguide modes are nought because only the TE_{1m} and TM_{1m} modes have a linearly polarized component to couple to the Airy profile, which is essentially a plane wave. For an infinitely long horn (*ie.* no phase correction at the horn mouth) Eq. 7 is maximized at $a = F\lambda$ for a coupling of $A_{11} = 0.865$ which gives the maximum possible aperture efficiency of $\eta_{Ap} = 0.748$ when the horn is placed at the image of the focal plane (compare this to $\eta_{Ap} = 0.837$ when the horn is in the aperture plane [11,12]).

For a practical horn, the focal plane does not occur at the horn mouth but at some distance within the horn, so Eq. 6 is first expressed as a sum of L-G beams at the waist ($z = 0$). The coefficients of the Airy profile in terms of the L-G beams can be calculated directly by taking the inner product of the Airy and L-G modes, but it is simpler to exploit the fact that L-G modes are unchanged by Fourier transformation except for a multiplicative term $(-1)^m$ [14] where m is the degree of the L-G mode, and note also that the beam waist radius at the aperture plane is related to that of the focal plane by

$$W_f = \lambda f / \pi W_{ap}. \quad (8)$$

Table 2a: Laguerre-Gauss Coefficients and Efficiencies

m	TE_{11}						
	C_{0m}	P_{0m}	η_{Ap}	η_B	C_{2m}	P_{2m}	η_B
0	0.93092	0.86662	0.70004	0.83743	0.22095	0.048819	0.032147
1	-0.00016319	0.86662	0.70001	0.83743	0.095791	0.057995	0.035396
2	-0.15625	0.89104	0.76961	0.84700	-0.016674	0.058273	0.035482
3	-0.078191	0.89715	0.75091	0.84886	-0.065197	0.062524	0.036768
4	0.014460	0.89736	0.75120	0.84892	-0.060891	0.066232	0.037704
5	0.058322	0.90076	0.74124	0.84982	-0.030233	0.067146	0.037902
6	0.055583	0.90385	0.75233	0.85051	0.0039529	0.067161	0.037905
7	0.027983	0.90463	0.74827	0.85068	0.028146	0.067954	0.038072
8	-0.0037052	0.90465	0.74807	0.85068	0.037652	0.069371	0.038353
9	-0.026542	0.90535	0.74721	0.85082	0.033882	0.070519	0.038558
10	-0.035721	0.90663	0.75055	0.85106	0.021389	0.070977	0.038634
11	-0.032304	0.90767	0.74666	0.85123	0.0054864	0.071007	0.038639
12	-0.020475	0.90809	0.74902	0.85130	-0.0092722	0.071093	0.038653
13	-0.0052673	0.90812	0.74857	0.85131	-0.019839	0.071487	0.038716
14	0.0089384	0.90820	0.74817	0.85132	-0.024824	0.072103	0.038810
15	0.019169	0.90857	0.74815	0.85138	-0.024270	0.072692	0.038895
16	0.024037	0.90914	0.74912	0.85146	-0.019241	0.073062	0.038946
17	0.023545	0.90970	0.74752	0.85154	-0.011361	0.073191	0.038963
18	0.018698	0.91005	0.74905	0.85158	-0.0023972	0.073197	0.038963
19	0.011056	0.91017	0.74814	0.85160	0.0060517	0.073233	0.038968
20	0.0023343	0.91017	0.74831	0.85160	0.012764	0.073396	0.038989

The C_{nm} are the coefficients of the cylindrical beam modes to the Laguerre-Gauss beam modes Ψ_{nm} . P_{nm} is the total power in the first m Gaussian modes. η_{Ap} is the aperture efficiency when the first m Gaussian modes are considered; and η_B is the beam (or spillover) efficiency when the first m Gaussian modes are considered. The total spillover of the TE_{11} mode when looking at an extended thermal source is the sum of columns 5 and 8, $\eta_B = 0.891$. These efficiencies are for the case of an infinite length (flare angle of 0) horn: see also Figure 3.

Table 2b: Laguerre-Gauss Coefficients and Efficiencies

m	TM_{01}				TE_{21}			
	C_{1m}	P_{1m}	η_B	η_B	C_{1m}	P_{1m}	η_B	η_B
0	0.63775	0.40672	0.34657	0.63384	0.22916	0.52516	0.023088	0.023088
1	0.12246	0.42172	0.35241	0.65926	0.17675	0.83756	0.034557	0.034557
2	-0.11974	0.43605	0.35800	0.66134	0.068877	0.88501	0.035785	0.035785
3	-0.13845	0.45522	0.36371	0.66748	-0.021223	0.88951	0.035898	0.035898
4	-0.063283	0.45923	0.36471	0.66948	-0.067628	0.93524	0.037047	0.037047
5	0.017204	0.45952	0.36479	0.66950	-0.072405	0.98767	0.038223	0.038223
6	0.063867	0.46360	0.36576	0.67002	-0.049955	0.10126	0.038708	0.038708
7	0.071188	0.46867	0.36682	0.67093	-0.016718	0.10154	0.038760	0.038760
8	0.050364	0.47121	0.36729	0.67150	0.014242	0.10174	0.038797	0.038797
9	0.017211	0.47150	0.36735	0.67164	0.035146	0.10298	0.039022	0.039022
10	-0.014682	0.47172	0.36739	0.67164	0.043279	0.10485	0.039346	0.039346
11	-0.036741	0.47307	0.36763	0.67176	0.039731	0.10643	0.039597	0.039597
12	-0.045636	0.47515	0.36798	0.67202	0.027843	0.10721	0.039713	0.039713
13	-0.042167	0.47693	0.36825	0.67226	0.011794	0.10735	0.039733	0.039733
14	-0.029681	0.47781	0.36838	0.67241	-0.0044648	0.10737	0.039736	0.039736
15	-0.012565	0.47797	0.36840	0.67245	-0.017868	0.10769	0.039782	0.039782
16	0.0049342	0.47799	0.36841	0.67245	-0.026531	0.10839	0.039881	0.039881
17	0.019464	0.47837	0.36846	0.67247	-0.029759	0.10927	0.040002	0.040002
18	0.028922	0.47921	0.36858	0.67255	-0.027860	0.11005	0.040102	0.040102
19	0.032490	0.48026	0.36872	0.67265	-0.021869	0.11053	0.040161	0.040161
20	0.030457	0.48119	0.36883	0.67275	-0.013229	0.11070	0.040182	0.040182

The C_{nm} are the coefficients of the cylindrical beam modes to the Laguerre-Gauss beam modes Ψ_{nm} . P_{nm} is the total power in the first m Gaussian modes. η_{Ap} is the aperture efficiency when the first m Gaussian modes are considered; and η_B is the beam (or spillover) efficiency when the first m Gaussian modes are considered. The spillover efficiency of the TM_{01} mode is $\eta_B = 0.738$, and for the TE_{21} mode it is the sum of columns 7 and 10, $\eta_B = 0.713$.

f is the focal length of the lens or mirror in the Gaussian Beam Telescope[14]. The integrals

$$\alpha_m = \frac{(-1)^m}{\pi(F\lambda/\pi)^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{F\lambda/\pi} r d\theta dr \Psi_{0m} \quad (9)$$

with the substitution of Eq. 8 in Eq. 1 are more easily evaluated than the focal plane integrals which extend from 0 to infinity in r . Once the α_m have been determined, this L-G beam must be propagated up to the horn mouth which is simply done by modifying the α_m by the phase slippage that occurs because the horn phase centre of radius occurs within the horn instead of at the horn mouth. Equations 1c and d can be inverted:

$$W_o = W [1 + (\pi W^2/\lambda L)]^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (10a)$$

$$z = R [1 + (\lambda L/\pi W^2)]^2. \quad (10b)$$

Employing the orthogonality of the L-G beams, the coupling coefficients of Eq. 1 are then

$$A_{11} = \sum_{m=0}^M \alpha_m C_{0m}, \quad (11)$$

and the aperture efficiency is $\eta_A = A_{11}^2$. Table 2a lists the aperture efficiency for the case of the infinite length horn, and Column 2 of Table 3 lists the α_m . Enough L-G modes must be included in the sum (M in Eq. 11) to get an accurate calculation of the aperture efficiency. After about 20 modes the result changes only in the fourth decimal place (the value after 100 modes is $\eta_A = 0.7483$, see Figure 2.)

An example is given here which corresponds to the $855\mu m$ feedhorn of SCUBA which has a length of $40mm$. In this case the telescope beam is F4 (after reimaging the F12 beam of the JCMT). The horn mouth radius $a_m = 0.956F\lambda$ at $\lambda = 855\mu m$ is less than the optimum $a_m = F\lambda$ to allow for the horn wall thickness of $\sim 300\mu m$ and to ensure that the horn centres are $2F\lambda$ apart (the Nyquist sampling rate is $F\lambda/2$ so the horns are an integer number of "Nyquist" units apart). The feed is single moded at $855\mu m$ and has L-G beam width at the horn mouth of $W = 0.768a = 2.51mm$; the waist is $W_o = 0.665a = 2.17mm$ which occurs at $z = 3.07a = 10.0mm$ behind the horn mouth; the phase slippage is $\Phi = 0.525(2m + n)radians$. This gives an aperture efficiency of $\eta_A = 0.703$.

When the same feed is used at $\lambda = 700mm$ then the horn mouth radius is $a_m = 1.17F\lambda$; the beam width at the horn mouth is the same $W = 0.768a = 2.51mm$;

but the waist is now $W_o = 0.627a = 2.05\text{mm}$ at $z = 4.08a = 13.3\text{mm}$ behind the horn mouth, and the phase slippage is $\Phi = 0.615(2m + n)\text{radians}$. The aperture efficiency in this overmoded case is $\eta_A = 0.676$. There are two sources of loss in an overmoded system. The aperture efficiency is reduced because the horn mouth is too large, and the background loading is increased significantly which degrades the signal-to-noise of the device. This second effect is discussed in section 4.

3.2 Spillover

The beam efficiency in a Cassegrain telescope is defined as the fraction of power in the antenna beam which intercepts the image of an extended source through the telescope aperture. A source is considered to be extended if its angular extent exceeds the beam size of the telescope. The fraction of power which does not see the source on the sky “spills over” the telescope secondary mirror and looks at the entire sky surrounding the telescope beam. For this reason, the beam efficiency as defined here is often termed “spill over efficiency” in radio astronomy [15].

$$\eta_B = \sum_{m=0}^M \frac{C_{n-1m}^2}{\pi a^2} \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr |\Psi_{n-1m}|^2 + \sum_{m=0}^M \frac{C_{n+1m}^2}{\pi a^2} \int_0^a \int_0^{2\pi} r d\theta dr |\Psi_{n+1m}|^2. \quad (12)$$

The C_{nm} are the coefficients of the L-G functions, and M is the total number of L-G modes which are considered in the sum to approximate the field profile through the optical train, and n is the order of the cylindrical beam mode (Eqs. 1a and b) supported in the feed. The final four columns of Table 3 list the beam efficiencies associated with each L-G mode (*ie.* the integrals of Eq. 12) for the case of the infinite length horn. Finally, performing the summation of Eq. 12, the beam efficiency for each mode is calculated (see columns 5 and 8 of Table 2a, and columns 4, 7, and 10 of Table 2b). The overall spillover efficiency of the feedhorn depends on the number of waveguide modes propagating through the system, and on the nature of the signal to be measured (see next section). For the feedhorn system described in section 3.1 the spillover of the system when it is single moded ($\lambda = 855\mu\text{m}$) is $\eta_B = 0.902$. The spillover associated with each waveguide mode in the overmoded feed ($\lambda = 700\mu\text{m}$) is 0.811, 0.615, and 0.568 for the TE_{11} , TM_{01} and TE_{21} respectively.

**Table 3: Laguerre-Gauss – Airy Coupling,
and Beam Efficiencies**

m	$\Psi_{0m} - \text{Airy}$	η_B			
	α_m	Ψ_{0m}	Ψ_{1m}	Ψ_{2m}	Ψ_{3m}
0	0.89877	0.96632	0.85212	0.65849	0.43964
1	0.10264	0.57907	0.38919	0.35410	0.36713
2	-0.25987	0.39179	0.39002	0.30666	0.25879
3	0.13714	0.30459	0.29772	0.30263	0.25049
4	0.011770	0.30402	0.25116	0.25245	0.25131
5	-0.098824	0.26439	0.25087	0.21651	0.22416
6	0.11543	0.22300	0.23780	0.21162	0.19471
7	-0.083778	0.21133	0.20904	0.21097	0.18323
8	0.031666	0.21124	0.18835	0.19796	0.18390
9	0.018706	0.20181	0.18319	0.17886	0.18231
10	-0.054093	0.18375	0.18323	0.16562	0.17267
11	0.069610	0.16851	0.17799	0.16169	0.15928
12	-0.066508	0.16219	0.16647	0.16194	0.14903
13	0.049638	0.16173	0.15438	0.15989	0.14487
14	-0.025242	0.16062	0.14690	0.15322	0.14476
15	-0.00065582	0.15523	0.14469	0.14410	0.14464
16	0.023238	0.14661	0.14472	0.13626	0.14171
17	-0.039341	0.13823	0.14341	0.13195	0.13585
18	0.047505	0.13289	0.13916	0.13087	0.12898
19	-0.047750	0.13100	0.13279	0.13097	0.12338
20	0.041211	0.13090	0.12643	0.13006	0.12030

The first 21 L-G coefficients of the Airy field pattern are listed for the case of the infinite length horn. (The waist, $W_o = 0.768a = 0.768F\lambda$, occurs at the horn mouth.) The spillover efficiencies in columns 3 to 6 are those associated with each L-G beam with $W = 0.768a$

4 Signal Measurement

In order to compute the signal coupled to the antenna by a particular source the spillover and the atmosphere transmission τ must be considered, as well as the aperture efficiency if it is a point source.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\text{meas}} &= \tau(\eta_B' \eta_{\text{Ap}} T_s' + \eta_B T_s) + (1 - \tau)\eta_B T_{\text{atm}} + (1 - \eta_B)T_{\text{atm}} \\ &= \tau(\eta_B' \eta_{\text{Ap}} T_s' + \eta_B T_s) + (1 - \tau\eta_B)T_{\text{atm}} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where T_{meas} and T_{atm} are the equivalent Rayleigh-Jeans temperatures which is measured by the antenna, and emitted by the atmosphere respectively. T_s' and T_s are the temperatures emitted by the point source and an extended thermal source within the telescope beam. In the first term of Eq. 13 the spillover η_B' is that associated with the part of the horn profile which couples to a point source (*eg.* column 6 of Table 2a for the infinite length horn).

An overmoded feed is most damaging to antenna efficiency because of increased background thermal loading. The Earth's atmosphere and any other black body or near black body source is an emission of random polarized radiation. Instantaneously, the antenna sees, on the average, radiation of any given polarization so each of the supported waveguide modes can couple to equal amounts of power. The spillover in this case is simply the average of those of the modes which propagate in the feed. For the feedhorn described in the last section $\eta_B = 0.902$, and when it supports the first two waveguide modes ($\lambda = 700\mu\text{m}$), $\eta_B = (0.811 + 0.615)/2 = 0.713$. The point source spillover is $\eta_B' = 0.860$ in the single moded case and $\eta_B' = 0.808$ in the overmoded case.

A typical calibrating source used from the JCMT might be Jupiter which emits as a point source black body of temperature ~ 150 K. The Earth's atmosphere is at ~ 275 K with transmission $\tau \sim 0.70$ at $\lambda = 700\mu\text{m}$. The first term of Eq. 13 gives the source signal measured by the antenna: $0.70 \times 0.808 \times 0.676 \times 150$ K ~ 55 K, and the rest gives the background loading: $(1 - 0.70 \times 0.713) \times 275$ K ~ 140 K. So in a given time t , the detector measures ~ 195 K of which $\lesssim 25\%$ is signal from Jupiter, and $\gtrsim 75\%$ is background loading. When the same feed is used as a single moded device, then the source signal is now $0.70 \times 0.860 \times 0.703 \times 150$ K ~ 65 K, and the background loading is $(1 - 0.70 \times 0.902) \times 275$ K ~ 100 K. So in the single moded case, Jupiter accounts for $\sim 40\%$ of the flux entering the detector. Comparing the two cases, $(40\%/25\%)^2 \sim 3$, implies that the integration time on the calibrating source Jupiter (the time required to obtain a given level of detection) is about 3 times longer if the feedhorn supports two waveguide modes.

5 Conclusions

A submillimetre feed was analyzed in order to estimate the aperture and beam efficiencies of a submillimetre astronomical receiver operating at non-optimum frequencies. The Submillimetre Common User Bolometer Array (SCUBA), to be installed on the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope, will measure flux from astronomical sources in four wavebands: 350 GHz (855 μm), 428 GHz (700 μm), 685 GHz (438 μm), and 857 GHz (350 μm). The two bolometer arrays mounted in the instrument are designed to operate with optimum efficiency at 438 μm and 855 μm . At the shorter wavelengths the arrays consist of non-optimized feeds and one must consider the higher order beam modes which are then permitted to propagate in the system.

Efficiencies in the Cassegrain telescope were computed using Gaussian Beam Analysis after first determining the horn E field profile using the cylindrical waveguide modes as the "source" functions. The aperture efficiency (point source efficiency) and the beam efficiency (spillover efficiency) were both considered, and a particular case of the detection of Jupiter as a calibrating source was discussed.

The analysis shows that the 855 μm array receiving 700 μm radiation suffers a 2% reduction in aperture efficiency from 70% to 68%, and a 20% loss in beam efficiency from 90% to 71%. This last dominates the reduction in feedhorn performance since the background is normally brighter than the source, and a reduction in spillover efficiency implies increased background loading.

In terms of integration times for the example of Jupiter, this means that the telescope must look at a point source for roughly three times the duration when the receiver is overmoded at 700 μm than it would if the antenna feed was optimized at that frequency. For source fluxes which are significantly smaller than that of Jupiter (as most interesting objects are), this difference between single and overmoded optics will become more severe as the background dominates more and more.

Overall, overmoded optics do reduce aperture efficiency as expected; nonetheless this may be an acceptable price to pay when a "quick & dirty" scheme for increasing the number of channels is desired on a receiver. In the case of the Submillimetre Common User Bolometer Array, this means the 700 μm channel can be added to the instrument without manufacturing an array of bolometers dedicated to that frequency, and it will operate reasonably well.

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References

1. Taub, J.J., Hindin, H.J., Hinckelmann, O.F., Wright, M.L., "Submillimeter Components Using Oversize Quasi-Optical Waveguide," *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory & Techniques*, vol. 11, pp. 338-345, September 1963
2. Crenn, J.P., "Optical theory of Gaussian beam transmission through a hollow circular dielectric waveguide," *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 21, pp. 4533-41, December 1982
3. Belland, P., Crenn, J.P., "Matching of a Gaussian Beam into Hollow Oversized Circular Waveguides," *Int. J. IR & MM Waves*, vol. 10, pp. 1279-87, October 1989
4. Winston, R., "Light Collection within the Framework of Geometrical Optics," *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, vol. 60, pp. 245-247, February 1970
5. Harper, D.A., Hildebrand, R.H., Stiening, R., Winston, R., "Heat Trap: An Optimized Far Infrared Field Optics System," *Applied Optics*, vol. 15 pp. 53-60 January 1976
6. Clarricoats, P.J.B., Olver, A.D., *Corrugated Horns for Microwave Antennas*, Peter Peregrinus Ltd. on behalf of IEE, 1984
7. Olver, A.D., Jun Xiang, "Design of Profiled Corrugated Horns," *IEEE Trans. Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 36, pp. 936-940, July 1988
8. Cunningham, C.R., Gear, W.K., "The Submillimetre Common User Bolometer Array," *Proc. of SPIE Symp. Astronomical Telescopes & Instrumentation*, February 1990
9. Ludwig, A.C., "Radiation Pattern Synthesis for Circular Aperture Horn Antennas," *IEEE Trans. Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 14, pp. 434-40, July 1966

10. Kogelnik, H., Li, T., "Laser Beams and Resonators," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 54, pp. 1312-29, October 1966
11. Murphy, J.A., "Aperture Efficiencies of Large Axisymmetric Reflector Antennas Fed by Conical Horns," *IEEE Trans. Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 36 pp. 570-575, April 1988
12. King, A.P., "The Radiation Characteristics of Conical Horn Antennas," *Proc. IRE*, vol. 38, pp. 249-51, March 1950
13. Goldsmith, P.F., "Quasi-optical Techniques at Millimetre and Submillimetre Wavelengths," *Infrared and Millimetre Waves*, vol. 6, pp. 277-343, New York: Academic, 1982
14. Padman, R., Murphy, J.A., Hills, R.E., "Gaussian Mode Analysis of Cassegrain Antenna Efficiency," *IEEE Trans. Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 35, pp. 1093-1103, 1987
15. Christiansen, W.N., Högbom, J.A., *Radiotelescopes*, Cambridge University Press, 1985

5.2 3d-Quasi-Optical Ray-Tracing for the Odin Radiometer

La sonde spatiale Odin est dotée de cinq radiomètres y compris quatre dans la bande submillimétrique autour de 500 GHz et un à 119 GHz. L'architecture optique est assez sophistiquée pour permettre la distribution du faisceau vers les 5 récepteurs. De plus, les quatre récepteurs submillimétriques sont des systèmes hétérodynes avec injection du référentiel dans la chaîne optique. L'architecture optique comprend donc un filtre dichroïque pour séparer le millimétrique et le submillimétrique. Ensuite, il y a des grilles de polarisation pour séparer les deux récepteurs submillimétriques de polarisations opposés. Il y a un mécanisme pour sélectionner les deux paires de récepteurs submillimétriques, et un autre pour sélectionner les trois sources de calibration dont une interne et les deux autres sur le ciel. Enfin, le système hétérodyne filtre la bande passante pour supprimer la bande latérale non-désirée. Ceci est fait avec des interféromètres du type « Martin-Puplett » qui intègrent des miroirs déplaçables.

Avec les multiples mécanismes et miroirs, l'architecture optique pour Odin est très complexe. J'ai pu réaliser la conception du système optique avec l'aide d'un logiciel que j'ai développé pour faire les calculs quasi-optiques au sein de l'environnement de Conception Assister par Ordinateur (CAD en anglais). Ce système permet la modélisation quasi-optique et donne les dimensions physiques, y compris les surfaces des miroirs, nécessaires pour réaliser l'architecture mécanique. Le système est brièvement décrit dans la publication suivante.

3d-Quasi-Optical Ray-Tracing for the Odin Radiometer

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ABSTRACT:

We describe the Odin radiometer optical layout and the 3-dimensional CAD system developed to define and analyze the system. Both the mechanical and optical design were done within the same CAD environment using a custom plug-in software for Quasi-Optical analysis and ray tracing. Odin has a complex optical layout with three dimensional beam foldings and a large number of optical elements. The optical/mechanical CAD system allows control over the definition of mirror and lens surfaces, as well as the mechanical support structure and apertures, bringing all elements into a single 3-dimensional model.

Odin Optical Layout:

The optical layout for the Odin radiometer is based on the prototype version described by Ordell[1], with some improvements introduced for the flight version. Odin has five receivers: four of which are submillimeter and one is millimeter wave. The four submillimeter mixers are arranged in cross-polarized pairs. Each pair looks at two Martin-Puplett diplexers, one for LO injection and one for side band rejection. Because of the arrangement of the grids in the diplexer tower, each mixer beam takes a different path through the diplexer. As a result, there are eight tuning mechanisms which move the right-angled roof-top mirrors that perform the beam polarization rotation. In Figure 1a, one can see how the beam comes out of one level of the diplexer tower and then is folded back into the next level by two mirrors. Those folding mirrors are profiled in order to contain or "re-collimate" the beam. In all, the beam goes through four focussing elements before being sent off to the telescope secondary mirror.

All the mirrors in Odin are off-axis ellipsoid mirrors in order to control aberrations [2]. In Figures 1a and b, the rings shown on the mirror surfaces are the physical locations where the incoming Gaussian beam intersects the surface of the mirror at edge tapers of 5dB, 15dB, 25dB, and 35dB. The CAD drawing of the mirror is accurately drawn with the surface profile we expect to manufacture, and we have used this to verify the mirrors by comparing the drawing to mechanical depth measurements of the mirror surfaces.

After the diplexer tower there is yet another mechanism: A simple rotating Dicke switch. Both sides of the Dicke switch are used such that one pair of mixers is viewing the astronomical source while the other pair is looking at the internal calibration source. We have a choice of calibration sources: one warm, and two cold. The two cold are simply looking directly at the cold sky (not through the telescope). We achieve this through one final mechanism which is a rotating switch mirror, making ten mechanisms in all in Odin. The mirror mounted on this last mechanism is also a profiled surface, and the axis

of rotation of the mirror is such that we don't introduce any aberrations. That is, we only reflect the beam to the designed beam reflection angle.

The 119GHz beam comes into the Dicke switch via a dichroic where it joins the submillimeter beam from the bottom level of the diplexer. In Figure 1b, the Gaussian beam for the 119GHz channel is drawn as a 3-dimensional surface of revolution. This method is useful for ensuring sufficient clearance throughout the optical path. For example, in Figure 1b, a mirror in the calibration chain has its bottom corner bitten off such that there is a clear path for the sky beam when the switch mirror selects that position.

Lenses with linear matching grooves

The 119GHz channel has two lenses in the optical path. In other parts of the optical design, off-axis ellipsoid mirrors have been used because they transform the phase front radius of an incident beam into the desired output beam with a spherical phase front radius and Gaussian amplitude distribution [2]. The corresponding surface of refraction which performs the same transformation is a cartesian oval [5]. On Odin, we have used single surface lenses in which the first surface is spherical and matched to the phase radius of the incident beam. There is therefore no transformation at the first surface. The second surface is a cartesian oval.

In order to reduce reflections at the surface of the lens, a matching layer of grooves has been machined into the surfaces of the lens. Circular grooves have the disadvantage of a mismatch where they do not line up, or exactly cross, the polarization vector of the receiver [6]. This effect can be reduced by using linear matching grooves that line up with the linearly polarized receiver beam. Machining of grooves into the lens surface was done by a Computer Numerically Controlled milling machine (see Figure 2). The program used to control the machine was produced by the Quasi-Optics plug-in software as a text output file containing the required Heidenheim control language syntax.

Quasi-Optics Software:

The Quasi-Optical analysis was achieved using a 3-dimensional Quasi-Optical ray tracing program developed by the author. The program currently runs as a plug-in to AutoCADTM [3], or other "AutoCAD fluent" software such as IntelliCAD98TM [4]. The plug-in performs the Quasi-Optic calculations in addition to drawing the entities. In the Odin drawings, all the beam envelopes shown are drawn to the 35dB edge taper of a Gaussian beam. These are hyperbolae, and in the case where a tube represents the beam, this is a surface of revolution formed by the hyperbola. For clarity, the 3-d beam is not shown everywhere because it would make a cluttered drawing, however they are in the drawing (some of them are on "frozen layers"). This three dimensional ray tracing has proven to be extremely useful in spotting areas where we might otherwise have truncated the beam. Odin has such a compact design with many beam foldings in all directions that it would be difficult to keep track of everything without a 3-d ray tracing.

REFERENCES:

1. Ordell, E, "The Quasi Optics of the Odin Satellite" Swedish Space Corporation report SSAD531-1, 1995
2. Murphy, J.A. "Distortion of a Simple Gaussian Beam on Reflection from Off-Axis Ellipsoidal Mirrors" Int. J. Infrared & Millimeter Waves, Vol.8, No.9, 1987, pp.1165-87
3. Autodesk corp, <http://www.autodesk.com>
4. Visio, <http://www.visio.com>
5. Cornbleet, S "Microwave and Geometrical Optics (Techniques of Physics, No 16)", Academic Press, 1994, ISBN 012189651X
6. Lamb, J. "Cross-Polarisation and Astigmatism in Matching Grooves," Int. J. Infrared and Millimeter Waves, vol.17, no.12, 1996, pp.2159-65
7. Goldsmith, P.F., "Quasioptical Systems: Gaussian Beam Quasioptical Propagation" IEEE press, 1998, ISBN 0-7803-3439-6

Figure 1: Isometric views of the Odin radiometer. The 119GHz beam is drawn as a 3-dimensional surface of revolution bounded by a hyperbola which is the 35dB edge taper envelope of a Gaussian beam.

Figure 2: A teflon lens with linear matching grooves machined into the profiled surface. The lens surface is a surface of revolution formed by a cartesian oval.

5.3 The Questions that Drive the Specifications

Le projet SKA est la réalisation d'un rêve qui remonte à un demi-siècle, jusqu'aux débuts de la radioastronomie. Il s'agit de la détection aux distances cosmologiques de la raie de 21 cm de longueur d'onde d'hydrogène neutre. Pour ce faire, il faut un radiotélescope avec une sensibilité qui nécessite une surface collectrice d'un kilomètre carré. C'est le réseau d'un kilomètre carré, « *Square Kilometre Array* ».

Bien que la détection d'hydrogène neutre est la première motivation pour le SKA, un tel instrument a énormément de possibilités. Le projet est vite devenu multi-disciplinaire, et le cahier des charges très compliqué pour satisfaire plusieurs domaines scientifiques. Il faut une large bande spectrale, mais à la fois avec une bonne résolution spectrale. On doit pouvoir cartographier le ciel, mais avec une bonne résolution angulaire, et en faisant la spectro-imagerie en même temps. La science des pulsars et des sursauts rapides exigent une résolution temporelle extrêmement précise. Les exigences des différents domaines scientifiques sont souvent incompatibles, et il faut donc trouver des compromis.

Les motivations scientifiques sont souvent posées en tant que questions fondamentales. Dans cette publication, je fais un relevé de toutes les questions fondamentales posées dans les différents domaines scientifiques, et je fais la synthèse des exigences pour le cahier de charges pour le SKA.

Cet article est publié dans les actes de la conférence à la fin du projet européen « *Square Kilometre Array Design Studies* » (SKADS) pour lequel j'étais le responsable scientifique, et l'éditeur principal pour les actes de la conférence.

The Questions that Drive the Specifications

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Abstract. The fundamental questions to be addressed by the Square Kilometre Array remain relevant today, despite the passage of time since the SKA Science book was published over four years ago. The answer to the questions of Dark Energy, Cosmic Magnetism, Gravitation in Extreme Fields, and the Epoch of Reionisation, all require observational statistics on a very large scale. As a result, the SKA is being designed mainly as a large survey machine. Survey requirements place specific demands on the technical definition of the SKA, and the cost of implementation puts restrictions on the ultimate capability of the SKA. At the same time, we must not trade-off too much of the versatility of the SKA because, as has been seen many times in the past, it is the unexpected discoveries which turn out to be the most important contribution of an instrument.

1. Introduction

The SKA will play a pivotal role in answering fundamental questions in physics which are currently the focus of the world-wide physics research community. The key science goals of the SKA fit into this global effort to focus on several inter related topics. These include discovering the nature of Dark Energy, the origin of magnetism in the universe, the limits of the General Theory of Relativity, and the formation of the first structure, and the first stars in the Universe. The SKA will also answer questions related to the origin and formation of complex molecules and planetary systems, leading to life on Earth. All these key science goals are described in detail in the SKA Science Book (Carilli & Rawlings 2004).

The SKADS whitepaper brings these scientific goals into the design of the SKA, and I will review the technical requirements demanded by each science goal, and how it translates into a global vision for the SKA.

The SKADS consortium, primarily through the effort in DS2, has made significant advances in sky simulations, and calibration considerations. This work is accessible to the global SKA community through the SKADS Simulated Skies database, and has already appeared in a number of publications. For example, see Wilman et al. (2008); Obreschkow et al. (2009a,b); Krause et al. (2009); Smits et al. (2009); Santos et al. (2008); Baek et al. (2009). A complete list of SKADS publications can be found on the SKADS website^a. The SKADS Simulated Skies tools and database are described in more detail by Levrier et al. (2010) and by Klöckner et al. (2010) in these proceedings.

2. The Cradle of Life

What conditions are necessary for the development of life?

We are here on the Earth, asking fundamental questions about the nature of the Universe, one of which is how we arrived at such a state that we can do such a thing. The development of

life on Earth is the result of a number of events in the history of the galaxy and solar system which finally led to the formation of an hospitable environment here on Earth. The questions on which we focus with the SKA are the following:

- How are planetary systems formed?
- Is the solar system a special case?
- How and where are complex (organic) molecules formed?

Once the SKA has its capability at 10 GHz and higher, it will be able to detect the gaps in proto-planetary disks forming around stars. These gaps are where planets are formed (Lazio 2004). It is only recently in the history of astronomy that planets have been detected orbiting other stars. So far, no Earth like planet has been detected. This is almost certainly due to the limitation of current technology, but the possibility remains that Earth is a special case where all the requirements come together to make an environment conducive to the development of life.

Long chain carbon molecules have already been detected in extraterrestrial environments. An example is methanol with a rotational transition emitting at 834 MHz. Others are acetaldehyde (at 1.1 GHz) acetamide (at 9.2 GHz) and cyclopropenone (at 9.3 GHz). Further possibilities are listed in Lazio et al. (2009).

Is there anybody out there?

The radio spectrum has traditionally been the regime where searches have been made for artificially generated signals from civilisations beyond the Earth. Using Earth as an example, there are a few emitters in the radio band, the most powerful of which is the Arecibo planetary radar. The Arecibo S-band radar is used for solar system studies and roughly a dozen times per year it beams a monochromatic, circularly polarised signal (see e.g. Campbell et al. 2003; Black et al. 2007; Carter et al. 2009), with frequency and time domain modulation (Magri et al. 2007) and powers of up to 1 MegaWatt for durations of several hours. For example, during the latter half of 2009, the Arecibo planetary radar operated during 29 sessions of duration averaging 3 hours each, and sometimes for as much as

^a <http://www.skads-eu.org/p/memos.php>

10 continuous hours (Hernandez 2009). Such a signal, distinct from any natural phenomenon, could be detected by an SKA type telescope thousands of light years away. If extra terrestrial scientists are studying their planetary system with an Arecibo-like instrument, then we could detect their radar, and there are many thousands of stars within the range of detectability of SKA. The advances made in the detection of extra solar planets, and soon the detection of extra solar planets in the habitable zone, make it possible to do long term targeted studies with the SKA.

3. Tests of Gravity using Pulsars

How right is Einstein about gravity?

Observational tests of General Relativity include the demonstration of the existence of gravitational waves (Taylor 1993), and a number of other effects have been observed by timing the orbital characteristics of pulsar-neutron star binary systems. In particular, the double pulsar system (Burgay et al. 2003; Lyne et al. 2004) demonstrates that the theory of General Relativity is correct to 99.95% (Kramer et al. 2006; Wex & Kramer 2010). More details of this can be found in these proceedings by Kramer & Smits (2010) on page 59 and references therein.

What is the strong-field limit at which GR is no longer the correct description of gravity?

Nevertheless, there remains a dichotomy between the quantum theory of physics, and the general theory of relativity. It is expected that at sufficiently large gravitational field strengths, General Relativity will no longer be the correct description of gravity. The SKA will be able to probe this limit by timing a pulsar in orbit around a black hole.

In order to find the most exotic pulsar binary systems which can be used for tests of General Relativity, the SKA will carry out a large survey of the galaxy finding all the observable pulsars, perhaps as many as a few tens of thousands (Smits et al. 2009). Amongst these will be exotic systems needed to carry out the tests.

Is there a gravitational wave background?

By correlating the measured times-of-arrival of pulses from millisecond pulsars distributed throughout the galaxy, it is possible to infer the passage of a gravitational wave through space where the Earth resides. The times-of-arrival will be slightly early for pulsars in one direction, and later in the opposite direction, with a delay profile that matches what is expected by a gravitational wave. This method of using timing of distributed pulsars is called the Pulsar Timing Array. It is sensitive to gravitational waves of frequency nHz which is not detectable by any other means.

The SKA may well find a background of gravitational waves and then we can ask: Is it stochastic? That is, is it caused by numerous individual events such as supernovæ and mergers. Or, is it a primordial background arising from the Big Bang itself. In that case, the SKA may be used to probe epochs before

the time the Universe cooled sufficiently to release the photons which are the Cosmic Microwave Background. This surface of last scattering is the earliest time which can be probed by observational methods which detect electromagnetic waves. Perhaps the SKA will be able to probe times before the surface of last scattering, and enlighten us on the nature of the primordial plasma.

4. The Epoch of Reionisation

When was "first light"?

In the early Universe, after the primordial plasma cooled to allow the creation of neutral material, there followed a long period in which the Universe contained only neutral material, almost entirely neutral hydrogen atoms. The only radiation present was the scattered photons left over from the surface of last scattering, also called the Epoch of Recombination, and observed today as the Cosmic Microwave Background. There was no source of visible light in the Universe during that period which we refer to as the Cosmic Dark Ages. The SKA will probe the Universe for highly redshifted neutral hydrogen gas in order to answer the fundamental questions in the history of the Universe:

- When did the first luminous objects form?
- How did they form, and over what period of time?

The first luminous objects must have emitted large quantities of energetic photons, not only in the visible wavelengths, but also at much higher energies. This radiation then went on to ionise the surrounding neutral medium, creating the largely ionised medium we observe today, which is why that period in the history of the Universe is called the Epoch of Reionisation.

The SKA will carry out a large survey of redshifted neutral hydrogen, giving a history of the evolution of reionisation in the Universe from the time when there was only neutral hydrogen gas to the formation of the first luminous objects. For more details see Zaroubi (2010); Santos et al. (2010) in these proceedings, and, for example, the introduction in Baek et al. (2009).

5. Cosmic Magnetism

What is the origin of magnetic fields in the Universe?

Magnetic fields play a major role in astrophysics at all scales. The formation of stars and planetary systems are intimately connected to the interplay of magnetic fields. Magnetic fields are essential for the protection of life on Earth from energetic charged particles in the solar wind. On galactic scales, magnetic fields are observed to influence, and even determine, the structure of galaxies. See the review in these proceedings on page 93 by Beck (2010).

Despite the obvious importance of magnetic fields to our understanding of the nature of the Universe, we still do not have a strongly supported theory for the origin of magnetic fields.

- Were magnetic fields always there? That is, are they primordial arising from the processes in the early universe?
- or

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- Were magnetic fields generated over the evolution of the Universe by the dynamo effect in numerous sources distributed throughout the Universe?

The SKA will do an extensive survey of Rotation Measures, recording on the order of 10 million Rotation Measures of sources distributed throughout the sky. This will give statistics on the overall picture of magnetism in the Universe, and we begin to have a handle on possible theories of the origin of magnetic fields. See Beck (2010) in these proceedings on page 93 for more details.

6. Large Scale Structure

What is the nature of Dark Energy?

Observational evidence from distances to super novae combined with statistical analysis on the anisotropies in the Cosmic Microwave Background have shown us that the Universe is undergoing a phase of accelerated expansion (Riess et al. 1998). The more recent analysis of data from the Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe puts a high precision on this expansion (Komatsu et al. 2009), and allows us to derive conclusions about the energy density of the Universe. The negative energy causing accelerated expansion is called Dark Energy and it appears to account for $\sim 70\%$ of all energy in the Universe.

The fact that Dark Energy remains an enigma despite its clear importance in the physics of the Universe has led to proposals of numerous experimental projects/ Many of the planned experiments are based on the detection of Baryonic Acoustic Oscillations (Blake & Glazebrook 2003). Acoustic oscillations in the primordial plasma left a signature on the subsequent formation of structure after the epoch of recombination when the Universe cooled sufficiently to form neutral matter and photons were free to propagate. This signature can be seen in the statistical analysis of the anisotropies in the Cosmic Microwave Background. It is also expected to be detected in the distribution of matter in later periods of the Universe.

The SKA will do an all-sky survey measuring simultaneously the position of galaxies, and their redshift by detection of the redshifted 21 cm forbidden transition of the neutral hydrogen. Over a billion galaxies will be detected, giving the possibility to bin the data and do the analysis in redshift slices. This will improve analysis, and ultimately lead to a high precision determination of the w parameter in the equation of state of the Universe. If $w = -1$, then the accelerated expansion of the Universe is entirely explained by the Cosmological Constant in the General Theory of Relativity. We will finally be able to answer the questions:

- Is Dark Energy just a geometrical feature of General Relativity?
 - (was Einstein wrong when he thought he was wrong about the Cosmological Constant?)

7. Transients

During most of the history of civilisation on Earth, the sky was thought to be mostly static. When viewed with the naked

eye, nothing in the heavens appears to change except for the movement of the seven classical planets: The Sun, The Moon, Mercury, Venus, Mars, Jupiter, and Saturn. The appearance of the occasional comet was of the utmost import, because of its rarity.

In more recent times, it has become clear that there are many periodic events in the Universe. Comets are understood to be regular visitors, and the modern era of observational astronomy has discovered transient events on time scales ranging from years, months, days, to subsecond events. Supernovæ explosions have afterglows slowly diminishing over a period of months. Many stars have intrinsic pulsations with periods on the order of days. On the shortest timescales, subpulses of the pulsar in the Crab Nebula have been observed with nanosecond duration (Hankins et al. 2003).

Astronomy is just beginning to get a global view of the various transient populations, and we can ask the fundamental questions:

- Is there a population of powerful, irregular, transient sources?
- What are they?
- How do they generate the energy they emit?

Also, as discussed above in the section on “Cradle of Life,” there is the possibility of artificially generated signals.

The topic of transients is developed in much more detail by Lazio (2010) on page 51 of these proceedings.

8. Exploration of the Unknown

Are we asking the right questions?

The scientific method is a process involving a question followed by studies to achieve an answer. This always leads to further questions and that is the path to discovery. Sometimes, however, we can be led astray by the questions we pose. A question may contain a hidden assumption which prevents us from moving towards the correct conclusion.

There have been a number of such examples in the past. One such is the attempt to measure the speed of the Earth with respect to the luminous aether at the end of the 19th century. With everything that was understood about wave propagation, it seemed unquestionable that electromagnetic waves must propagate through a medium, just as surface waves propagate through water, and pressure waves propagate through air. It was a significant step of understanding to imagine that there is no medium through which light propagates.

Perhaps the most famous example in modern scientific history is the question Einstein effectively asked himself before adding a cosmological constant to the General Theory of Relativity. “How can I modify the Theory of General Relativity to conform to the observed, static Universe?” At the time, the Universe appeared to be unchanging. Indeed, the idea of the static, eternal Universe, is deeply rooted in western thinking for nearly 3000 years. Einstein noted that his theory was not stable and added a cosmological constant to counteract the effect of gravity which, on its own, would bring about the collapse of the Universe. He was asking the wrong question. He

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might have asked himself, “What is the theory telling me about the Universe?” and then he could have predicted the expanding Universe given an initial condition of a big bang. Einstein referred to this as his greatest blunder.

In more recent history, telescopes have been built with a specific scientific goal in mind. In most cases, the telescopes become most well known for discoveries and studies completely different from their original science justification. There are a few famous examples.

The 2048 dipole aperture array telescope called the 4-acre array at the Mullard Radio Astrophysical Observatory of the University of Cambridge was built to study scintillation in the interplanetary medium due to the solar wind (Hewish 1974). It discovered pulsars, winning a Nobel prize for Anthony Hewish and Martin Ryle.

A horn antenna used in the 1960’s by Bell Labs engineers was originally designed for radio communications with the satellites Echo and Telstar (Wilson 1978). It was afterwards taken over by Bell Labs radio astronomers who wished to make a general survey of cosmic microwave radiation. While doing a precise characterisation of the horn antenna, this led to the discovery of the Cosmic Microwave Background winning a Nobel prize for Penzias & Wilson.

The 305m diameter Arecibo radar was originally conceived by William Gordon to study the ionosphere by measuring RADAR back-scatter from the ionosphere (Cohen 2009). Arecibo is best known for a number of discoveries including the first extra solar planet (Wolszczan 1991), and the long term timing study of the pulsar-neutron star binary system which demonstrated the existence of gravitational waves winning a Nobel prize for Taylor & Hulse (Taylor 1993).

All these examples show our limited ability to predict the most important results to come from an instrument. Often these discoveries came from the possibility of an instrument to be used in ways that were not considered when it was designed, but the design was sufficiently flexible to allow the instrument to be used in new ways. The design of the SKA must not be entirely optimised for the Key Science projects, and we have to maintain an element of flexibility in the capabilities of the instrument. This is where the most important discoveries will arise. It is the flexibility of the instrument, and the imagination of the next generation of astronomers to think of new ways to use the instrument, and to come up with the right questions to ask.

9. Specifications Overview

The science goals summarised in the last section cover various topics, but have in common the desire to understand fundamental aspects of physics and the nature of the universe. As a result, the required observations are necessarily global in nature. That is, in order to reach conclusions about the global properties of the universe, one must observe as much of the universe as possible. The result is a requirement to conduct large scale surveys.

Surveys serve two main functions. In one case, the statistics of the survey itself is the primary interest. This is the case for example for the Baryonic Acoustic Oscillations experiment, and the all-sky rotation-measure survey. In the second case,

the survey serves as a tool to discover extreme objects. This is the case for the pulsar survey looking for exotic binary systems to test gravity, or looking for isolated pulsars to use in the Pulsar Timing Array, as is the search for new classes of transient sources.

Surveys with the goal of discovering new objects require follow-up observations of the newly discovered objects. Such observations will often demand high angular resolution, pushing out the SKA baseline length requirement.

As part of the SKADS Virtual Telescope exercise, the instrument capabilities required by the SKA have been summarised in Table 1. The Epoch of Reionisation experiment and the Baryonic Acoustic Oscillations experiment are both well served by aperture array technology. A sparse array similar to LOFAR is required for the EoR experiment, while a dense array for the mid frequencies is necessary for the BAO experiment, providing the large field of view and subsequent mapping speed which is unequalled by any other technology. Other requirements include polarisation purity, necessary for the Cosmic Magnetism key project. The dynamic range cited here assumes a relatively quiet site in terms of Radio Frequency Interference, and depends more on the requirement of large field of view imaging. The longest baselines are necessary for follow-up observations such as VLBI of pulsars, detailed studies of new discoveries. Long baselines are particularly important when SKA Phase-D is online with its frequencies up to 10GHz and then the studies of protoplanetary disks can begin, as well as study of organic molecules in planet forming systems, and especially in solar system analogs. In general, however, it is the large surveys which drive the specifications, and these require more collecting area in the core rather than at long baselines.

10. Summary

The design of the Square Kilometre Array is motivated by a number of fundamental questions in physics and astronomy. These have been grouped together in five main topics.

For “The Cradle of Life” we ask “What conditions are necessary for the development of life?” leading us to build an instrument capable of detecting complex molecules, and detecting the early stages of planetary formation in stellar systems.

For “Tests of Gravity using Pulsars” we ask “How right was Einstein about gravity?” which requires an instrument capable of finding all the detectable pulsars in the galaxy and timing many of them in order to test the theory of General Relativity in extreme gravity fields, and in order to detect nanoHertz gravitational waves.

For “The Epoch of Reionisation” we ask “When was first light?”. This requires a low frequency instrument capable of surveying the whole sky with great sensitivity in order to measure the redshifted neutral hydrogen at different epochs in the early Universe.

For “Cosmic Magnetism” we ask “What is the origin of magnetic fields in the Universe?” In order to answer this question the SKA must be capable of doing a large survey of over 10 million Rotation Measures. This puts strict constraints on the imaging capability and polarisation purity of the instrument.

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For “Large Scale Structure” we ask “What is the nature of Dark Energy?” This leads to the requirement that we build an instrument capable of measuring the signature of the Baryonic Acoustic Oscillations in the distribution of matter in the Universe. This is to be done by a large survey of over a billion galaxies measuring simultaneously their positions and redshift. The SKA thus requires a very large field of view combined with high fidelity imaging and spectroscopic capabilities necessary to measure the weak signal of redshifted neutral hydrogen.

These are the original five Key Science topics on which the SKA focuses, but there has been more and more emphasis on the topic of the transient Universe where we ask “Is there a population of powerful, irregular, transient sources, and what is their nature?” The SKA will require not only the capability to measure events on short time scales, but to do so over a very wide field of view in order to have a better likelihood to catch those transient events, wherever they may occur.

All these fundamental questions arise from our current understanding of the Universe, but we could well be asking the wrong questions. Many past instruments have become famous for discoveries and for long term projects that were not imagined by the builders of those instruments. The SKA needs to have capabilities allowing it to make discoveries that we have not imagined. It will be used in ways that were not yet considered, by people who are now only school age, and by people not yet born. The SKA design must include capabilities which go beyond those strictly required by the key science topics outlined here and include an element of flexibility which will permit those future astronomers to make the discoveries that we have not imagined.

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References

- Baek, S., Di Matteo, P., Semelin, B., Combes, F., & Revaz, Y. 2009, *A&A*, 495, 389
- Beck, R. “Wide Field Polarimetry and Cosmic Magnetism,” 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4
- Black, G.J., Campbell, D.B., & Carter, L.M. 2007, *Icarus*, 191, 702
- Blake, C., & Glazebrook, K. 2003, *ApJ*, 594, 665
- Burgay, M., et al. 2003, *Nature*, 426, 531
- Campbell, D.B., Black, G.J., Carter, L.M., & Ostro, S.J. 2003, *Science*, 302, 431
- Carilli, C., & Rawlings, S. (eds) 2004, Elsevier
- Carter, L. M., Campbell, B. A., Hawke, B. R., Campbell, D. B., & Nolan, M. C. 2009, *Journal of Geophysical Research (Planets)*, 114, 11004
- Cohen, M.H. 2009, *J. Astronomical History and Heritage*, 12, 2, 141-152
- Hankins, T. H., Kern, J. S., Weatherall, J. C., & Eilek, J. A. 2003, *Nature*, 422, 141
- Hernandez, H., 2009, The Arecibo schedule, available at <http://www.naic.edu/vscience/schedule/scedfra2.htm>
- Hewish, A., Nobel lecture, 1974, The Nobel Foundation http://nobelprize.org/nobel_prizes/physics/laureates/1978/wilson-lecture.pdf
- IEEE Puerto Rico & Caribbean section, 2001, IEEE Global History Network http://www.ieeehgn.org/wiki/index.php?title=Milestones:NAIC/Arecibo_Radiotelescope%2C.1963&oldid=38928
- Klößner, H.R., Auld, R., Heywood, I., Obreschkow, D., Levrier, F., Rawlings, S. “SKA HI end2end simulation,” 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4
- Komatsu, E., et al. 2009, *ApJS*, 180, 330
- Kramer, M., et al. 2006, *Science*, 314, 97
- Kramer, M., Smits, R., “Pulsars - Enabling the gravitation KSP of the SKA,” 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4
- Krause, M., Alexander, P., Bolton, R., Geisbüsch, J., Green, D. A., & Riley, J. 2009, *MNRAS*, 400, 646
- Lazio, T.J.W. in “Science with the Square Kilometre Array” C. Carilla & S. Rawlings (eds) 2004, Elsevier
- Lazio, T.J.W. and the SKA Science Working Group, “The Design Reference Mission”, SKA Program Development Office, http://www.skatelescope.org/PDF/091001_DRM_v0.4.pdf
- Lazio T.J.W., “Radio Transients and Aperture Arrays,” 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4
- Levrier, F., Wilman, R.J., Obreschkow, D., Klößner, H.-R., Heywood, I., Rawlings, S., “Mapping the SKA Simulated Skies with the S^3 -Tools,” 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4
- Lyne, A. G., et al. 2004, *Science*, 303, 1153
- Magri, C., Ostro, S. J., Scheeres, D. J., Nolan, M. C., Giorgini, J. D., Benner, L. A. M., & Margot, J.-L. 2007, *Icarus*, 186, 152
- Obreschkow, D., Klößner, H.-R., Heywood, I., Levrier, F., & Rawlings, S. 2009, *ApJ*, 703, 1890
- Obreschkow, D., Croton, D., D eLucia, G., Khochfar, S., & Rawlings, S. 2009, *ApJ*, 698, 1467
- Riess, A. G., et al. 1998, *AJ*, 116, 1009
- Santos, M. G., Amblard, A., Pritchard, J., Trac, H., Cen, R., & Cooray, A. 2008, *ApJ*, 689, 1
- Santos, M.G., Ferramacho, L., Silva, M.B., “Fast Large Volume Simulations of the Epoch of Reionization,” 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4

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Table 1: Instrument requirements for the SKA over its construction stages, determined using the scientific requirements and costing exercise done within the SKADS project.

Parameter	units	Stage-A (2011)	Stage-B (2013)	Stage-C (SKA Phase 1: 2017)	Stage-D (SKA Phase 2: 2022)
Dish size	m	15	15	15	15
Dish geom. area	m ²	176.7	176.7	176.7	176.7
No. of dishes		25	75	620	2400
Total dish Area	m ²	~ 2650	~ 13250	~ 109500	~ 424100
Aperture Array: AA-hi	m ²	-	-	10000	610000
Aperture Array: AA-lo	m ²	-	-	-	$6.4 \times 10^6 (0.1/\nu)^2$ $\nu > 0.1$ GHz 6.4×10^6 $\nu < 0.1$ GHz
Aperture efficiency	%	80	80	80	80
High Freq	GHz	10	10	Dishes: 10.00 AA-hi: 1.00 AA-lo: -	Dishes: 10.00 AA-hi: 1.00 AA-lo: 0.45
Low Freq	GHz	0.7	0.7	Dishes: 0.80 AA-hi: 0.30 AA-lo: -	Dishes: 0.80 AA-hi: 0.30 AA-lo: 0.07
Inst. B/W	MHz	250	250	5000 $\nu > 0.8$ GHz 700 0.3 GHz $< \nu < 1.0$ GHz	5000 $\nu > 0.7$ GHz 700 0.3 GHz $< \nu < 1.0$ GHz
FoV	deg ²	$0.7(1.4/\nu)^2$	$0.7(1.4/\nu)^2$	$0.7(1.4/\nu)^2$ $(\nu > 0.8$ GHz) 250 $(\nu < 1.0$ GHz)	$0.7(1.4/\nu)^2$ $(\nu > 0.7$ GHz) 250 $(\nu < 1.0$ GHz)
System Temp	K	50	30	Dish: 30 AA-hi: 50 AA-lo: -	Dish: 30 AA-hi: 38 AA-lo: sky noise (min 50)
Sensitivity	m ² /K	54	373	1493 $(\nu > 0.8$ GHz) 320 $(\nu < 1.0$ GHz)	10^4 $(\nu > 0.8$ GHz) 10^4 $(0.3 < \nu < 1.0$ GHz) $A_{\text{eff}}/T_{\text{sys}}$ $(0.07 < \nu < 0.3$ GHz)
Polarisation	dB	-30dB	-40dB	-40dB	-40dB
Min. Baseline	m	30	30	30	30
Max Baseline	km	0.3	5	50	Dishes: 3000 AA: 180
Dish Concentration	%			AA-hi within 1 km	
25% filling factor	(dia)	50% (~ 100 m)	25% (~ 140 m)	-	-
10% filling factor	(dia)	100% (~ 180 m)	50% (~ 250 m)	-	-
< 1 km (diameter)				50%	dishes: 20 AA-hi: -30% AA-lo: ~15%
< 5 km (diameter)			100%	75%	dishes: 50 AA: 66%
< 180 km (baseline)				100%	dishes: 75 AA: 100%
< 3000 km (baseline)					dishes: 100
Configuration		correlated	correlated	beamform 20 dishes cor- related 100 stations	correlated with beam- formed dishes above 180 km baseline
Dynamic Range		10^5	3×10^5	10^6	$\sim 10^7$ $(\nu > 0.3$ GHz)

- Smits, R., Kramer, M., Stappers, B., Lorimer, D. R., Cordes, J., & Faulkner, A. 2009, A&A, 493, 1161
Taylor, J.H., Nobel lecture, 1993, The Nobel Foundation
http://nobelprize.org/nobel_prizes/physics/laureates/1993/taylor-lecture.pdf
Wex, N., & Kramer, M. 2010, arXiv:1001.4733
Wilman, R. J., et al. 2008, MNRAS, 388, 1335
Wilson, R.W., Nobel lecture, 1978, The Nobel Foundation
http://nobelprize.org/nobel_prizes/physics/laureates/1978/wilson-lecture.pdf
Wolszczan, A. 1991, BAAS, 23, 1347
Zarubi, S., "Probing the Epoch of Reionization with Low Frequency Arrays," 2010, in *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, S.A. Torchinsky et al. (eds), ASTRON, ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4

5.4 Characterization of a dense aperture array for radio astronomy

Bien qu'il soit intéressant de faire une étude approfondie d'un objet à distance cosmologique, il est essentiel de faire un relevé d'une grande tranche du ciel, voire tout le ciel, pour arriver à des conclusions sur les processus qui mènent à la formation de structure dans l'Univers. Une parabole avec un million de mètres de surface collectrice, si mécaniquement réalisable, aurait naturellement une résolution angulaire très fine. C'est parfait pour une observation profonde d'une source donnée dans le ciel, mais le champs-de-vue également limité n'est pas commode pour faire un grand relevé du ciel.

La solution technique est naturellement la synthèse d'ouverture avec plusieurs antennes moins grandes au-lieu d'une seule parabole énorme. Avec un réseau de paraboles distribué sur un grande surface, on peut construire une image du ciel avec une résolution angulaire définie par la distance maximale entres paraboles, et la superficie de l'image est limitée par le champs-de-vue de la parabole des membres du réseau. On peut pousser cette solution à l'extrême avec les paraboles remplacées par des simples antennes, chacune avec un champs-de-vue qui est effectivement le quart du ciel, ou plus. En remplissant la surface collectrice avec des antennes de ce type, on a un réseau avec la sensibilité de mesurer les sources à distances cosmologiques, mais, en même temps, on peut faire une grande image du ciel très rapidement.

Le grand défi de cette solution devient le nombre inédit de signaux à amplifier, numériser, et corrélér. Dans le cadre de l'étude européenne "Square Kilometre Design Studies" (SKADS) pour laquelle j'étais le responsable scientifique, on estimait que la technologie est réalisable en suivant le programme de développement proposé par la collaboration. Un jalon clef dans ce programme de développement est la réalisation d'un prototype, appelé "Electronic Multi-Beam Radio Astronomy ConcEpt" (EMBRACE). Le prototype est composé de 4608 antennes organisés dans un réseau carré d'une surface d'environ 70m². J'étais responsable de la caractérisation et l'évaluation du prototype EMBRACE, dont les résultats sont publiés dans l'article suivant. Ce système, complètement novateur, fonctionnait comme un véritable observatoire astronomique.

Characterization of a dense aperture array for radio astronomy

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ABSTRACT

EMBRACE@Nançay is a prototype instrument consisting of an array of 4608 densely packed antenna elements creating a fully sampled, unblocked aperture. This technology is proposed for the Square Kilometre Array and has the potential of providing an extremely large field of view making it the ideal survey instrument. We describe the system, calibration procedures, and results from the prototype.

Key words. instrumentation: interferometers – telescopes

1. Introduction

The Square Kilometre Array (SKA; [Dewdney et al. 2009](#)) will be the largest radio astronomy facility ever built with more than ten times the equivalent collecting area of currently available facilities. The SKA will primarily be a survey instrument with exquisite sensitivity and an extensive field of view, providing an unprecedented mapping speed. This capability will enormously advance our understanding of fundamental physics including gravitation, the formation of the first stars, and the origin of magnetic fields, and it will give us a new look at the variability of the Universe with a survey of transient phenomena.

A revolution in radio-receiving technology is underway with the development of densely packed phased arrays. This technology can provide an exceptionally large field of view, while at the same time sampling the sky with high angular resolution. The Nançay radio observatory is a major partner in the development of dense phased arrays for radio astronomy, working closely with The Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy (ASTRON). The joint project is called EMBRACE (Electronic MultiBeam Radio Astronomy Concept). Two EMBRACE prototypes have been built. One at Westerbork in The Netherlands (called EMBRACE@Westerbork) and one at Nançay (EMBRACE@Nançay, see [Fig. 1](#)). The EMBRACE prototypes are recognized as “Pathfinders” for the SKA project. Conclusions from the EMBRACE testing will directly feed into the SKA and will have a decisive impact on whether dense array technology is used for the SKA.

The date for selecting technology for the SKA is 2018. If dense arrays are not selected for the SKA, then the SKA will have a much reduced mapping speed compared to what has come to be expected by the astronomical community. It is therefore crucial that work on EMBRACE succeeds in showing the viability of dense arrays for radio astronomy.

Fig. 1. EMBRACE@Nançay is composed of 4608 Vivaldi antenna elements separated from each other by 12.5 cm, making it a dense array for frequencies above 1200 MHz. EMBRACE@Nançay measures 8.42 m × 8.42 m for a total area of 70.8 m².

The two EMBRACE stations began with an initial period of engineering testing on the partially complete arrays ([Olofsson et al. 2009](#); [Wijnholds et al. 2009](#)). EMBRACE@Nançay has been fully operational since 2011 and now performs regularly scheduled astronomical observations, such as pulsar observations and extragalactic spectral line observing ([Torchinsky et al. 2013, 2015](#)). EMBRACE system characteristics, such as beam main lobe and system temperature, are behaving as expected. EMBRACE has long-term stability, and after four years of operation it continues to prove itself as a robust and reliable system capable of sophisticated radio astronomy observations.

Fig. 2. EMBRACE@Nançay system architecture consists of a four level hierarchy of analogue beamforming starting with 4608 Vivaldi antenna elements leading finally to 16 inputs to each of two digital backends.

Table 1. Components in the beamforming hierarchy.

Component	Number summed per group	Summed by	Total number per system
Vivaldi antenna	4	beamformer chip	4608
beamformer chip	3	hexboard	1152
hexboard	6	tile	384
tile	4	CDC card	64
CDC card	16	RSP boards	16 (32)

Notes. The final component in the hierarchy of analogue beamforming is the CDC card. There are two sets of 16 CDC cards, one for RF Beam-A, and the other for RF Beam-B.

2. EMBRACE system description

EMBRACE@Nançay is a phased-array of 4608 densely packed antenna elements (64 tiles of 72 elements each). For mechanical and electromagnetic performance reasons, EMBRACE@Nançay has, in fact, 9216 antenna elements, but only one polarization (4608 elements) has fully populated signal chains. The orientation of the linear polarized elements at Nançay is with the electric field sensitivity in the north-south direction. The tuning range for EMBRACE was originally designed to be from 500 MHz to 1500 MHz, however, the extremely powerful digital television transmitter in UHF channel 66 at 834 MHz created problems of saturation and intermodulation of the analogue components, especially the beamformer chip. As a result, high-pass filters were added to the system to restrict the tuning range to frequencies above 900 MHz. For more details on EMBRACE architecture, see [Kant et al. \(2009, 2011\)](#)

2.1. Hierarchical analogue beam forming

EMBRACE@Nançay uses a hierarchy of four levels of analogue beamforming leading to 16 inputs to the LOFAR backend system used for digital beamforming ([van Haarlem et al. 2013](#)). An

overview of the hierarchy is shown in the frontend architecture diagram (Fig. 2) and Table 1 gives a summary of the total number of components at each stage of analogue beamforming.

The first level of beamforming is done for four Vivaldi elements within the integrated circuit “beamformer chip” developed at Nançay ([Bosse et al. 2010](#)). This chip applies the phase shifts necessary to four antenna elements to achieve pointing in the desired direction. The phase shift required for each Vivaldi element is calculated from the array geometry of a tileset (4 tiles) for a given pointing direction. In this way, the subsequent stages of analogue summing are done by simple combining. No further phase shifts are applied.

The beamformer chip forms two independent beams for each set of four antenna elements. The beamformer chip splits the analogue signal from the antennas into two signals and then applies different sets of phase shift parameters to each signal. The beamformer chip therefore has four inputs for four Vivaldi antennas, and two independent outputs. The independent outputs is what makes it possible for EMBRACE to have two independent fields of view, often referred to as RF Beams, which are named Beam-A and Beam-B.

The output of 3 beamformer chips is summed together on a “hexboard” and 6 hexboards make a tile. The EMBRACE array

at Nançay has a further analogue summing stage with 4 tiles making a tileset. This final stage is done on the Control and Down Conversion (CDC) card in the shielded container which is connected to the tiles via 25 m long coaxial cables.

2.2. Control and down conversion

The CDC cards are responsible for three important tasks (Bianchi 2009; Monari et al. 2009): 1) Frequency mixing the radio frequency (RF) for conversion to a 100 MHz bandwidth centred at 150 MHz; 2) 48 Volt Power distribution to the tiles; 3) Distribution of command and housekeeping data communication to the tiles. The RF, 48 Volt power supply, and ethernet protocol monitoring and control communication are all multiplexed on the coaxial cables connecting the tiles to the CDC cards (Berenz 2009).

The frequency down-conversion is done by heterodyne mixing in two steps. A first local oscillator (LO) is mixed with the RF signal of interest which is between 500 MHz and 1500 MHz. This LO is tuned within the range of 1500 MHz to 2500 MHz such that the upper side band frequency is precisely 3000 MHz. The resulting signal is in turn mixed with a second LO which is fixed at 2850 MHz resulting in the intermediate frequency (IF) centred at 150 MHz.

There are 3 signal generators used to supply the LO signal to the mixers in the CDC cards. The LO at 2850 MHz is split by a 3 dB power splitter to supply the Beam-A and the Beam-B system. This signal is in turn divided by a cascade of 3 dB power splitters to be distributed amongst the 16 CDC cards. Similarly, the tunable LO is split amongst 16 CDC cards. There is a separate signal generator providing the tunable LO for the Beam-A and the Beam-B electronics (16 CDC cards for each).

The fact that the LO is distributed amongst the CDC cards is a potential source of an undesirable artefact in the final signal. The distributed LO signals could radiate directly into the CDC cards, or possibly mixing products could have a component which is correlated between all the outputs of the CDC card leading to a correlator offset in the beamformed data of the whole array. This is discussed further in Sect. 4.

2.3. Digital processing

The output of the tilesets is fed into a LOFAR-type digital receiver unit (RCU) and remote station processing (RSP) system for digital beamforming (Picard et al. 2009). The RSP performs the digital beamforming of the entire array, producing pencil beams which are usually called digital beams. These digital beams can have pointings within the RF-beam produced by the individual inputs to the RCU. For EMBRACE@Nançay, the inputs to each RCU is the signal from a tileset with a beam width of approximately 8.5° (see Fig. 4 and Sect. 6).

Digital beamforming as described above is done in order to reduce the volume of data produced by the system. The alternative method of producing the antenna cross correlations has the advantage of providing a spatially fully sampled image of the entire field of view every data dump ($5.12 \mu\text{s}$). This however produces an enormous volume of data which cannot be managed by the acquisition system. As a result, the phased-array technique is used in the digital beamforming to produce multiple beams on the sky, not necessarily covering the entire field of view.

EMBRACE is a single polarization instrument but the LOFAR RSP system has the capacity to produce two outputs per digital beam which correspond to the two orthogonal linear

polarizations in LOFAR. These are called the *X* and *Y* beams. For EMBRACE, *X* and *Y* are two, possibly different, pointing directions within the field of view (the RF beam). This means that for each digital beam, there are two directions, and there can be any number of digital beams as long as the total bandwidth remains within the limit of RSP processing capacity (36 MHz for each RF beam for EMBRACE@Nançay). The dual pointing per digital beam is discussed further in Sect. 9.2.

Fast data acquisition from the RSP boards is done by the backend called the Advanced Radio Transient Event Monitor and Identification System (ARTEMIS) developed at Oxford University (Karastergiou et al. 2015; Serylak et al. 2013; Armour et al. 2012). ARTEMIS is a combined software/hardware solution for both targeted observations and real-time searches for millisecond radio transients which uses graphical processing unit (GPU) technology to remove interstellar dispersion and detect millisecond radio bursts from astronomical sources in real-time. The pulsar observations with EMBRACE@Nançay are targeted at known pulsars applying known Dispersion Measure and timing parameters, and for this reason the GPU are not used on the EMBRACE@Nançay ARTEMIS backend.

The ARTEMIS hardware is also used for recording raw data packets from the RSP boards containing the digitized beam formed wavefront data. This is used for the high spectral resolution observation of the extra galactic source M33 (see Sect. 9.2)

2.4. Statistics data

In addition to the high rate beamformed data produced by the RSP system, there are also slower cadence data produced at a rate of once per second: the crosslet statistics, the beamlet statistics, and the sub-band statistics.

The LOFAR RCU system digitizes and channelizes the 100 MHz wide RF bandpass into 512 so-called sub-bands, each of 195.3125 kHz bandwidth. The cross correlations of all tilesets are calculated once per second and are called crosslet statistics. The default mode of operation for LOFAR is to calculate the crosslet statistics for each sub-band in succession such that it takes 512 s to cycle through the full RF band.

Another possibility is to request a given sub-band, and the crosslet statistics are calculated each second for the same sub-band. This is the mode of operation used most often at EMBRACE@Nançay. The sub-band statistics is simply the sub-band total powers of the 100 MHz bandpass for each tileset. The beamlet statistics are the beamformed total powers for the full array (16 inputs for EMBRACE@Nançay) dumped at 1 s intervals, and are identical to the fast data integrated over 1 s.

2.5. EMBRACE monitoring and control software

The Monitoring and Control software for EMBRACE was developed at Nançay. An extensive Python package library on the Station Control Unit (SCU) computer gives scripting functionality for users to easily setup and run observations depending on various parameters such as, for example, the type of the target, pointing, frequency selection, etc. Integrated statistics data are acquired from the Local Control Unit (LCU) and saved into FITS files including header information with essential meta data including pointing information, timestamp, frequencies, etc. Raw data (beamlets) are captured from LCU Ethernet 1 Gbps outputs and saved into binary files (Renaud et al. 2011).

3. Calibration

3.1. First stage phase calibration

EMBRACE@Nançay has a hierarchy of four analogue beam forming stages. The first three are done on the tile boards, while the last one is done on the CDC card in the shielded container. The cables running from individual tiles to the CDC cards are 25 m in length, and there are phase perturbations between the various connectors and length of cable leading from each tile. This is calibrated out using an algorithm implemented in the Local Control Unit.

The phase correction between tiles in a tileset is measured by successively maximizing the output power from pairs of tiles. Initially, the required phase shift for each of the 72 antennas in the tile is calculated from purely geometrical considerations (i.e. antenna position and desired pointing direction). This results in a value between 0 and 360°, different for each antenna. Afterwards, an additional phase shift is added to all the antennas in the tile in order to compensate the imperfections in the components and cables. Finally, the phase shift to be applied to each antenna is quantized to 45° steps.

This procedure is done in 24 phase steps, each time incrementing the additional phase shift to be added to all the antennas in the tile by 15°. The step size of 15°, followed by quantization to 45° required by the beamformer chips, results in a slightly improved configuration for the tile. For example, if the phase shift required by geometry for a given antenna is 7°, and an additional phase shift of 15° is added, the result will be 22°, which is quantized to 0°. A nearby neighbour might require a phase shift of 8°, and an additional shift of 15° would result in a quantized step of 45°. In this way, the quantization as the final step after application of a global phase shift of 15° allows for different configurations of phase shifts amongst the 72 antennas.

The phase shift which gives the maximum result is then converted to a value from 1 to 8 corresponding to the 8 phase steps available in each beamformer chip. This process is repeated for each of three pairs of tiles in a tileset, with one tile acting as a reference in each case (Tile 0). At each iteration, two tiles are set in “no output” mode while the other two make observations at each of 24 phase shift settings (see example in Fig. 3). The calibration scheme is done in parallel for each of the 16 tilesets which make up the Nançay EMBRACE station.

Since the analogue beam steering is based on signal phase shifts and not true time delays, the corrections found are only strictly valid for the centre frequency. This does introduce an error in the off-centre sub-bands but it is small since the bandpass is narrow compared to the RF frequency, and it is mostly compensated in the digital phase calibration which is the next step in the observation.

A strong source is necessary for this calibration procedure because the source must be detectable by individual tiles, each with just over 1 m² of collecting area. For EMBRACE, the Sun is often used as a calibration source, as well as GPS satellites. In particular, the GPS BIIF series of satellites which use the L5 carrier centred at 1176.45 MHz are good calibration sources. Only the sub-bands that receive significant power will be usefully calibrated, but the commonly used GPS L5 carrier is broad enough to calibrate at least 61 sub-bands (~12 MHz, one full “lane”).

Once the necessary phase offsets for each tile have been measured, they are stored in memory and used for the subsequent observation. The phase offsets are also written to disk and can be used in future observations without going through the calibration procedure described here. The use of calibration tables is the default mode of operation and has been used successfully

Fig. 3. An example output of the RF calibration scheme for one tileset as described in the text. The response of tile pairs for each of the 24 phase steps applied to the second tile in the pair is shown within the three groups of vertical dashed lines. The response is clustered in groups of three corresponding to the constraint of the phase shift step size, however within each group of three there is some variation.

Fig. 4. Drift scan signals of the GPS BIIF-1 L5 carrier 2013-01-10 at 80° elevation in the north. Each line corresponds to a tile set and their half-widths, combined with the spacecraft’s drift rate, can be converted to a HPBW beam size of ~8.5° which is close to what is suggested by the standard formula $1.2 \times \lambda/D$ where D is the tileset side of 2.1 m. The drift peaks are aligned as a result of applying the necessary phase shifts to each tile.

without updating the tables over periods of many months (see for example the pulsar observations described in Sect. 9.3).

The measured phase offsets are different for different pairs of tiles, and have values within the full range of 0 to 360° which corresponds to apparent path length errors of up to half a wavelength ($-\lambda/2 < \Delta_{\text{path length}} < \lambda/2$). For example, at 970 MHz, the path length error for some pairs of tiles is as much as ~15 cm.

Figure 4 shows a drift scan of satellite GPS BIIF-1 and each line is the output from a different tileset. As can be seen, each

tileset is phased-up correctly, and they all show the satellite peak at the expected time. Gain equalization has not been applied, but may be implemented in the future (see Sect. 3.3). The data here are from the Sub-band Statistics. For more details on this observation, see Sect. 6.

3.2. Second stage phase calibration

The RSP digital electronics of EMBRACE described in Sect. 2.3 produce high speed beamformed data by combining the complex waveform voltages of each tileset and multiplying by a complex steering vector which gives the beamformed output in a desired pointing direction. The goal of the phase calibration is to determine the modification to the complex weights required to compensate for any instrumental offsets.

In order to describe the procedure for determining the phase calibrated pointing, matrix operations are used including the matrix dot product (denoted by the central dot) and element-wise multiplication of matrix elements, also called the Hadamard product, denoted by \odot . Complex conjugate of a matrix is denoted by a superscript asterisk and the transpose with a superscript T .

The RSP system produces the high cadence beamformed voltages by forming the dot product of a complex steering row-vector w with the complex voltage column-vector T received per tileset:

$$V = w \cdot T \quad (1)$$

The steering vector depends on the array geometry given by the tileset positions, and on the desired pointing in the sky given by the direction cosines (see for example Thompson et al. 2004). The steering vector must be modified further to take instrumental offsets into account.

The calibration procedure makes use of the fact that beamforming in a given direction can be done equivalently by combining the steering vector with the cross-correlation matrix X which is the correlations between tilesets, and this produces the beamformed power P ,

$$P = w \cdot X \cdot w^* \quad (2)$$

and we maximize P while pointing at a calibration point source.

The cross correlation between tilesets is calculated each second as described above in Sect. 2.4. This is not fast enough to produce the high speed beamformed data at $5.12 \mu\text{s}$ intervals, but the cross correlation data can be used to estimate phase errors between each tileset, per sub-band. Each second, the RSP returns a matrix with the cross correlations between tilesets at a given frequency sub-band.

If the tilesets are pointing at a strong point source, then it is possible to calculate an additional phase correction matrix which, when multiplied element wise by the measured correlation matrix X , results in the expected point source at the centre of the field of view. For an ideal instrument, this phase correction matrix would be simply the identity matrix. In a real system, there are various disturbances to the phase along the signal chain which varies from tileset to tileset (cables, filters, amplifiers, mixers, analogue-to-digital converters, etc.). These phase differences must be measured using a strong source in the sky, and calibrated for future observations.

We look for a phase correction matrix W_{cal} such that the element-wise product

$$X_{\text{cal}} = X \odot W_{\text{cal}} \quad (3)$$

results in the matrix X_{cal} which is the corrected correlation matrix fixed according to a theoretical model of centred point

source. This means that the X_{cal} elements are all real. W_{cal} may be further decomposed into a steering matrix W_{geom} giving the phase required to steer the beam in a given direction given the array geometry, and a correction matrix W_{cor} including the corrections of all other sources of phases errors. We then have

$$X_{\text{cal}} = X \odot W_{\text{geom}} \odot W_{\text{cor}}. \quad (4)$$

The phase relations between elements at a given i, j is thus

$$\arg(X_{\text{cal}}^{i,j}) = 0 = \arg(X^{i,j}) + \arg(W_{\text{geom}}^{i,j}) + \arg(W_{\text{cor}}^{i,j}). \quad (5)$$

W_{cor} can then be computed by a simple element wise division:

$$W_{\text{cor}} = X_{\text{cal}} / (X \odot W_{\text{geom}}) \quad (6)$$

which corresponds to the phase relation for given i, j indices:

$$\arg(W_{\text{cor}}^{i,j}) = -\arg(X^{i,j}) - \arg(W_{\text{geom}}^{i,j}). \quad (7)$$

A complete phase correction matrix W_{cal} can then be created with magnitude unity and with the phases required to correct the measured cross correlation matrix, including the steering step and the phase correction to be applied:

$$W_{\text{cal}} = W_{\text{geom}} \odot W_{\text{cor}}. \quad (8)$$

In order to use the calibrated steering matrix for the high cadence beamforming, it is necessary to convert it back to a steering vector. This is done according to the relation

$$W_{\text{cal}} = w_{\text{cal}}^T \cdot w_{\text{cal}} \quad (9)$$

and w_{cal} can be extracted using the method of Singular Value Decomposition (see for example Noble & Daniel 1977). It is this calibrated steering vector which is used by the RSP system to calculate the EMBRACE beamformed data at $5.12 \mu\text{s}$ intervals using Eq. (1).

As with the calibration of the tilesets described above in Sect. 3.1, these calibration parameters are saved to disk and can be used for future observations without the necessity of making a calibration measurement before each observation run. The calibration table measured once has been valid for many months, as discussed further in Sect. 9.3.

3.3. Redundancy gain calibration

A further digital calibration method based on the redundancy method (Liu et al. 2010) is used in post processing. This method is particularly well suited to EMBRACE given the inherent level of baseline redundancy. EMBRACE@Nançay is made of 16 tilesets placed on a regular 4×4 grid and therefore one point in the UV space is measured by several different baselines sharing a common length and orientation.

The problem becomes one of solving an ill-conditioned set of equations in which there are more equations than there are parameters to be determined.

$$X_{ij}^{\text{obs}} = X_{ij}^{\text{true}} w_i w_j^* + e_{ij} \quad (10)$$

where X_{ij}^{obs} and X_{ij}^{true} are respectively the observed and true cross correlations corresponding to baseline ij ; w_i is the complex gain of tileset i ; and e_{ij} is the noise affecting baseline ij . One solves this system for all X_{ij}^{true} and w_i , with baseline redundancy giving a redundant structure to X_{ij}^{true} (several baseline outputs modeled by the same true cross correlation). As shown in e.g. Liu et al. (2010) and Noorishad et al. (2012), there exist several

ways of implementing a redundancy calibration method which solves Eq. (10). We implemented a non-linear method based on a classical steepest gradient algorithm (see e.g. Marthi et al. 2014).

In addition to phase calibration, the redundancy method allows for an estimation and correction of gain amplitude disparity between tilesets, which is the main reason for its implementation. This equalization of tileset gains allows for optimization of beam shape features like symmetry, resolution and stability over time (see Sect. 6.2). It can also be used to clean the data from unwanted instrumental effects by comparison with an ideal square aperture model. Note however that this method is not intended to optimize the signal-to-noise which may require a different weighting of tilesets based on individual signal-to-noise ratios and side lobe levels.

The redundancy calibration is robust since it relies only on the similarity of the individual elements. The calibration quality depends only on the signal-to-noise. The point-like or extended nature of the source does not affect the result. It nevertheless requires the position of the source as an input for an absolute phase calibration, since the resolution of Eq. (10) is invariant with respect to a global shift of the sky (absolute calibration of gain amplitude will not be dealt with here). This can be done by adding dedicated constraints to the solver, for example with the implementation of a phase correction gradient minimization across the array, or the inclusion of a model of the observed source. (Liu et al. 2010; Noorishad et al. 2012).

The only limitations are thus expected at low signal over noise, or when individual elements have significantly different behaviour from each other. The latter cause may come from intrinsic inhomogeneities in the numerous system electronic components on the array itself, the mass production employing industrial techniques with good reproducibility should nevertheless strongly mitigate this risk. It may also arise from environmental effects, e.g. temperature inhomogeneities in the electronic components over the array. The self-heating of dissipating electronics seems however to ensure a rather stable and homogeneous temperature over the electronic boards that form the array. Finally mutual coupling between antennas could also be a source of disparity among the elements. Nothing so far indicates that such coupling is of importance on EMBRACE@Nancay, but the dense aspect of the array calls for caution on that point. An application of redundancy calibration on a relatively dense array can be found in Noorishad et al. (2012) where data from a LOFAR HBA station are analyzed near the critical wavelength λ_c defined by the minimum distance d_c between individual antennas. While those HBA arrays have been designed as “semi sparse” across their entire frequency band ($\frac{\lambda}{2} < d_c < 2\lambda$), EMBRACE has access to both semi-sparse regime ($F > 1200$ MHz) and truly dense regime ($F < 1200$ MHz). The possible mutual coupling effects will be investigated with further development of the system model (see Sect. 6.2), if needed a refinement of the model in Eq. (10) could be implemented to take mutual coupling into account.

4. Correlator offset

4.1. Description of the problem

Long duration tracking observations of weaker sources revealed an apparent power variation as a function of pointing direction that was highly repeatable between observations. After some analysis of this problem it was realized that the cross-correlation matrix data product contained time-invariant complex offsets that are much larger than white noise component when observing

Fig. 5. Power as a function of time while tracking Cassiopeia A, and tracking an empty sky position with the same declination. Note that the solid black line is the only on-source signal. Each tracking produces two curves due to the dual digital beams used as illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Source tracking strategy. Two digital beams are placed symmetrically within the FoV (tileset beam) following the same sky trajectory but with a time delay. One of them is centred on the source, the other is used as an off-position.

empty sky. As it turns out the “direction dependence” is only an artefact of applying a varying set of complex weights (while steering the beam to track a source) to a fixed non-changing pattern of complex numbers. That description of the problem was observationally confirmed by noting that the wobbly trace was present and exactly the same whether we tracked a real source or just empty sky, as long as we followed the same trajectory in the local sky. For strong sources, such as the Sun or satellite carriers, this additive contribution is completely negligible and does not become an issue, but by pure coincidence the amplitude of the variation is comparable to the continuum power of Cassiopeia A and Cygnus A (the two strongest extra-solar radio sources at low frequencies). This can be seen clearly in Fig. 5. It shows power versus time from a Cyg A tracking, and also tracking an empty position with the same declination but different RA. The average power difference in these two signals corresponds to the Cyg A continuum level (the real astronomical signal) but as is also evident, the magnitude of the *variation* in the signals is about of the same strength as the average power difference.

4.2. Strategies for correcting the correlator offset

An obvious quick method to get rid of the variation is to subtract the (solid) blue and red signals shown in Fig. 5 and in order to have that possibility, we routinely employ the scheme outlined in Fig. 6. The LOFAR-type backend is always outputting two digital beams (see Sect. 2.3) and we use one of them to track the source, and the other to observe an off position that follows the same trajectory on the sky. Both beams are placed symmetrically within the tileset FoV so that the gains within the two beams are the same.

Fig. 7. Correlator offset seen in sky images. The correlator offset problem discussed in the text is also manifested by blob-like features when imaging the tileset FoV. Here the *left and right upper panels* show FoV images of Cygnus A, and towards an empty sky position, based on uncorrected cross correlations. The *bottom panels* show the same data but with images created from cross correlations corrected by subtracting a reference matrix of complex constants (the same reference was used for both images). In the left bottom panel, Cygnus A is now clearly seen and at its expected position (offset from centre due to the scheme outlined in Fig. 6).

Such a measure is more similar to mitigating the symptom rather than curing the cause of the problem. Cross correlations are easily corrected by subtracting (per sub-band) a reference cross correlation slice measured towards empty sky and this can be done in post-processing. We subtract all slices in the dataset in question with the same reference slice that may have been measured weeks or months earlier while tracking a different part of the sky. With corrected cross correlations we can then create our own digital beams in any direction within the FoV by applying the required complex weights. This method cures the problem to a large extent as is demonstrated in Fig. 7.

But there are severe limitations to this approach: the maximum cadence for cross correlations is one matrix per second and then only for one and the same sub-band. For N sub-bands, the cadence is decreased further to one matrix every N seconds for each sub-band.

The high cadence data stream is unfortunately not straight forward to cure. It consists of beamformed complex voltages every $5.12 \mu\text{s}$ which is the vector product of a row weight vector and a column tileset voltage vector (see Sect. 3.2 Eq. (1)). The complex offsets seen in the cross correlations (conjugate products of tileset pair voltages) must in turn be caused by complex offsets in the individual tileset signals themselves. We then have

$$V_{sb} = \mathbf{w}\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{w}(\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{E}) \quad (11)$$

where V is the beamformed voltage for a given sub-band sb , \mathbf{w} is the steering vector, \mathbf{T} are the complex voltages received per tileset, \mathbf{S} is the true uncorrupted sky signal from each tileset, and \mathbf{E} is an error vector with complex constants. It is not possible to correct the complex voltages in post processing because they are the product of beamforming which is done in real time. We do

not have access to the individual tileset voltages for post processing. It may be possible to determine the error vector \mathbf{E} by using the 1 s cadence cross correlation data, but in order to use this, the backend must calculate a subtraction before applying the complex steering vector, and this is not possible within the current processing power of the LOFAR-RSP system.

One can note that having a constant amplitude and phase value added to the tileset signal for a given sub-band, that is changing in between tilesets, is equivalent to injecting a tone into the system at the particular frequency that is picked up differently per tileset (modified amplitude and phase). This “tone” – that appears to be always present as soon as the instrument is turned on, and which is *independent of the current analogue direction (beamformer chip settings)* – might be described as a waveform since the values for neighbouring sub-bands follow one another logically. It may also be of great importance to note that LOFAR data, which are produced by a virtually identical backend and deliver the same data products, do not at all suffer from this effect. This suggests an origin in the analogue side of the instrument which is of radically different design compared to LOFAR, one example being that EMBRACE has an additional IF stage and subsequent downmixing is using a common LO source for all CDC cards (see Sect. 2.2).

4.3. Investigation of the correlator offset

We have previously noted that the fixed error pattern in the baseline correlations is stable enough to allow subtracting it out using a template correlation matrix observed weeks or months earlier. Furthermore, the template can be observed when the frontends are internally phased up to an arbitrary direction on the sky. The correction usually improves the beamformed continuum time stability down to a level where the remaining variation is comparable to what is seen while staring at a fixed point.

During an observation, an artificial ondulation in the beamformed power trace is created by applying varying complex steering gains to static tileset signals that are erroneously correlated (see Fig. 5). In fact, there is no true temporal instability as one is first led to believe. Whereas the backend does not allow access to individual tileset signals in the digital domain, we continue to employ the 1-s integration correlation matrices to analyse the problem. Primarily we aim to understand the origin and behaviour of the problem that we refer to as “correlator offsets”.

In order to quantify the variability of the correlator offsets, we have selected one sub-band in a 3-day data set where correlations for all baseline pairs were sampled every second. The frontends were fixed to the same analogue beam steering through the observation. The observation was configured to let Cas A drift through the beam once per sidereal day thus regularly verifying that the system was operating normally. We chose portions of ten minutes every day, separated by exactly 24 h, well away from the Cas A drift signal and obvious transients, to study the daily fluctuations of correlator offsets and compare them to the thermal noise as measured during each 600 s sequence (Fig. 8). We find that the thermal 1-sigma scatter is 20–100 times weaker than the magnitude of the complex offsets. The large range is due to the varying offset magnitudes; the thermal scatter is rather constant over all baseline pairs. The magnitudes of the average daily change of the offsets were found to be comparable to the thermal scatter, meaning that the thermal scatter is 15–100 times smaller than the offset magnitude.

To study the long-term stability of the offsets, we make use of the quasi-continuous pulsar tracking observations at 970 MHz that have been conducted with EMBRACE@Nançay since 2013.

Fig. 10. Correlator offset for the High Band Antenna array of the LOFAR station at Nançay. Note that the plot scale is 3 orders of magnitude smaller than the corresponding EMBRACE plot. The outliers are all neighbour antennas indicating the offset is due to cross talk between those antennas.

Fig. 11. Sky images without and with a source in the field. Using the cross-correlation statistics data, interferometric images can be made at a given sub-band. **a)** A phantom point source can be seen in images produced from data pointing at “empty sky” and assuming zenith pointing. **b)** The image of the Sun has peak more than an order of magnitude larger than the phantom point source.

behaves as a constant signal which is common in all the tilesets and is correlated by the EMBRACE backend. One can see this by producing a skymap image in the usual manner while assuming the array is pointing at zenith. Figure 11a is an image of “empty sky” from a drift scan of the Sun after the source has left the field of view. There are no detectable sources in the field. The result is clearly an image of a point source, but with a much lower intensity level compared to an image of the Sun (Fig. 11b).

The point source of Fig. 11a can be seen at any time in the data as long as there is no strong source in the field of view. It is always the same, as already noted above, and is independent of the instrument pointing parameters. In order to create this stable, “phantom” point source, there must be a signal common to all the tilesets analogous to a source in the sky impinging a signal on

all the tilesets, but the signal must be internal to the instrument and independent of pointing parameters.

The frequency downconversion stage described in Sect. 2.2 uses signal generators and power splitters to provide the Local Oscillator (LO) signal to all the CDC cards. This LO distribution is an obvious candidate for the source of the phantom point source (i.e. the correlator offset). Although care has been taken to avoid having LO or mixing products within the RF band, it appears that the LO or mixing products are nevertheless modulating signals on the CDC card, possibly by radiating onto the CDC card.

5. Astronomical measurement of the embrace geometry

The 72 Vivaldi antennas within a tile are laid out in rows rotated 45° from the tile side so that the main diagonal has 12 elements separated by 12.5 cm. Then the 64 tiles in the array are placed side by side in a right-angle rhombus pattern with respect to the North-South meridian. Distances within tiles and tilesets are easily measured down to the necessary accuracy (fractions of a wavelength), and it turns out that the nominal values can be used, e.g. neighbouring tileset distances along a row can be assumed to be $2 \times 0.125 \times 12/\sqrt{2}$ metres apart. Thus it is easy to construct the 4×4 matrix of relative positions needed for the complex weight calculation in the beam forming procedure, however, such properties as overall tilt and rotation must also be known down to fractions of a degree to avoid problems with pointing offsets when tracking sources (compare with a minimum synthesized beam size of $\sim 1.1^\circ$).

The rotation was initially known within a few degrees which is sufficient for shorter observations because the digital phase calibration (see Sect. 2.3) will correct the error as long as the pointing direction does not change much compared to the position of the calibration source during the time of phase calibration.

In 2012, two independent efforts were made to more accurately measure the rotation, both mechanically and by using a celestial source. In the latter case we made use of the low cadence tileset cross correlations produced in the backend every second and dumped into FITS files by the control software. The Sun was tracked starting approximately mid-day (19 July 2012) from south to west thus spanning almost a quarter of the local sky. An image was made within the tilesets’ FoV every 10 min and by retroactively assuming different instrument rotations when computing the complex weights for the phase calibration and actual data imaging, we could iteratively converge towards the best number that kept the Sun’s maximum intensity pixel at the expected position throughout the measurement. The number arrived at with this method was $\Delta\Theta = -3.7^\circ$. Incidentally this exercise was also an important step in verifying that all sign and ordering conventions were consistent between the various coordinate frames and cross correlation data files.

The direct estimate of the physical rotation of the instrument was done by measuring positions of corner antennas in three dimensions with respect to a reference point at the observatory site. The resulting offset angles along the north-south and east-west lines were found to be $\Delta\Theta = -3.673^\circ$ and $\Delta\Theta = -3.714^\circ$, respectively. It should be noted that although these physical measurements were done about one month prior to the on-sky experiment described above, the result was not yet known to the observer during the data analysis. The on-sky result thus turned out

Fig. 12. Drift scan of Cas A at 1171.4 MHz in a bandwidth of ~ 1 MHz. The top image shows the full time span of the drift scan with a baseline fit. The bottom plot is a zoom to the main lobe with the baseline fit removed. The measured FWHM is 1.476 deg which is very close to the expected value of 1.466 deg.

to be an excellent blind verification of the geometric parameters of the instrument.

The tilt angle was found to be small, ca 0.06° , mostly about the north-south axis, estimated from a one centimetre height difference of two reference points separated by nine metres along the east-west direction.

Those results have been confirmed by another method based on a model point spread function fit on a point source sky map (see Sect. 6.2). This is a sampled rectangle aperture model, with physical rotation and tilt of the array as 2 of the free parameters to be optimized. The best fit performed on several observations gives a consistent result of $\Delta\Theta = -3.714^\circ \pm 0.0005$ for the rotation angle, and a tilt angle ranging from 10^{-4} to a few 10^{-3} deg.

6. Beam pattern

6.1. Beam pattern measurements

At the single tile level, the main beam was first seen to agree with expectations for a one metre square phased up array when bore sight drift scans of GPS L2 carriers were conducted in October/November 2009. This result is described in detail in Olofsson et al. (2009).

The fundamental properties of the tileset beams and the full array beam were quickly established after the installation of the hardware was finished and phase calibration schemes were implemented during the summer months of 2011.

Figure 12 shows an example of a drift scan of Cassiopeia A pointing at its maximum elevation point. The east-west HPBW

Fig. 13. Drift scan of the Sun across the stationary digital beam pointing reaches its maximum at the expected time. The sidelobe levels are below the 15 dB design criterion.

was computed by converting the time axis to an angular scale and performing a Gaussian fit to the normalized baseline subtracted signal.

Figure 4 shows the time signals from a satellite carrier drift scan for all individual 16 tile sets that constitute the array members in the final digital beam forming. The slight dispersion of the times of maximum signal is caused by the 45° quantization of the phase settings that are used to create (or “steer”) the analogue tile beams, and to measure the global phase offsets between tiles in a tile set (see Sect. 3.1).

Sidelobe levels (along the east-west direction) can be seen in the logarithmic intensity scale solar drift scan in Fig. 13. The first secondary lobes can be seen to be ≥ 15 dB down from the main lobe which is within design goals.

The 2D sidelobe pattern at the smallest spatial scales could conveniently be studied once algorithms were in place to read and analyse the raw cross correlations data product. Figure 14 shows a narrow band instantaneous radio image of a point source (GPS satellite) in linear and logarithmic units. This can be compared with the simulated pattern (see Sect. 6.2). Note that the sky projection used (collapsing the azimuth/elevation sky position onto a flat plane by taking the cosine of the elevation) falsely leads to a beam shape that is independent of elevation, whereas on the sky the beam gets elongated in the up-down dimension at low elevations due to the shortening projected baselines (zero at the horizon). The pattern is repeated along the NW–SE and NE–SW axes due to the symmetry of the tileset grid and the resulting ambiguity that arises when phase-shifting exactly one whole wavelength on the shortest baselines (2.1 m) to create the image pixels.

6.2. Beam pattern simulation

When pointing towards an unresolved source, the cross correlation statistics data (once per second, per sub-band) gives access to a full 2D measurement of the point spread function (PSF) of the instrument.

We fit a sampled rectangle aperture model to the cross correlation data with array length dimensions a and b , rotation and tilt angles of the array respectively rot and $tilt$, field of view width fov , and power offset $P0$ as free parameters, following

Fig. 14. Snapshot image of the GPS BIIF-1 satellite on 2012-09-05 at 1175 MHz. The angular range covered approximately corresponds to two times the tileset FoV. Note that for the full up instrument beam layout, the pattern shown is tapered by the larger scale tileset main beam which is outlined in Fig. 4.

the theoretical square aperture:

$$\text{PSF}(\theta, \phi) = (1 - P0) \left[\text{sinc}^2\left(\frac{k\theta a}{2\pi}\right) \text{sinc}^2\left(\frac{k\phi b}{2\pi}\right) \right] + P0 \quad (12)$$

where θ and ϕ are angles with respect to the centre of the field of view, and taken along two great circles on sky that have been rotated by an angle *rot* and tilted by an angle *tilt* with respect to the celestial meridian.

When periodized, this model may be seen as an ideal case where the array would behave exactly as a sampled square aperture with independent and identical receivers on its whole surface. It is thus taking limitations such as diffraction-limited resolution, overall beam shape, or PSF aliasing into account, but neglects other possible influences like gain variations across the array or mutual coupling. As already discussed in Sect. 3.3, those latter effects could nevertheless explain some fine effects, and the gain variations are corrected by the redundancy method.

Figure 15 shows both observed PSF and a best-fit as contour plots of an interferometric image in one sub-band, during the observation of a GPS satellite. Two cases are presented: one with phase-only calibration, and one where the complex gains of each tileset has been corrected by redundancy-based calibration on the same source. The root mean square residual amplitude between redundancy calibrated data and best-fit model is less than 0.3%, and about twice as large in the phase-only calibration case.

One may note the periodization of an underlying PSF pattern corresponding to a perfectly sampled UV plane. Since our sampling is here limited to tilesets, and given the total size of the array, this periodization leads to an aliasing effect that tends to increase the Side Lobe Level (SLL). Our model takes it into account by periodizing the expression given in Eq. (12), with an angular period corresponding to the field of view $\frac{\lambda}{d_{\min}}$, where λ is the observed wavelength and d_{\min} is the minimum separation between two tilesets. As a result, the observed SLL is bigger than the expected one for a fully sampled rectangular aperture (-13.2 dB of expected attenuation for the first side lobe (Johnson et al. 1993), -11.9 dB when summing the first and second side lobes), as seen in Fig. 16.

Fig. 15. Contour plot (dB scale, 0 at maximum amplitude) of the interferometric imaging in one sub-band and after a phase-only calibration (*top panel*), and a full redundancy-based calibration (*bottom panel*), for a GPS satellite observation with EMBRACE@Nançay. Observed data are shown as dashed contours, while the best-fit rectangle aperture model is shown as continuous ones. The periodization of the main pattern is due to sampling of the UV plane, here the equivalent of 3 fields of view is shown.

This limitation is expected, given the relative small size of EMBRACE@Nançay. We may extrapolate our model for a larger array, with higher spatial resolution and thus less of these aliasing effects. Figure 17 shows the modeled PSF for an EMBRACE-type station with 50 times longer sides (2500 times bigger area). The remaining aliasing contribution to the first side lobe level is of the order of 0.4 dB.

After redundancy calibration, the observed Full Width Half Maximum (FWHM) is smaller than theoretically expected,

Fig. 16. 1D Diagonal of 2D interferometric PSF (dB scale, 0 at maximum amplitude), for both GPS observation and best-fit model.

Fig. 17. 1D Diagonal of 2D interferometric PSF (dB scale, 0 at maximum amplitude), for an EMBRACE-like array with 50 times larger side length (about 400 m side length), following the square aperture model best-fit parameters.

reflecting the over-estimated best-fit length and width. By comparison, the phase calibrated data (no gain amplitude correction between tilesets) shows an asymmetric rectangular aperture model, with one side length as expected and another one underestimated, reflecting the degraded spatial resolution in this direction along the side. The behaviour of tileset amplitude gain corrections given by the redundancy method shows this can be interpreted in terms of an apodization effect. For these observations, the tileset gains repartition over the array is indeed close to a bilinear function, with a gradient aligned with one side of the square array. Before gain amplitude correction, the array thus behaves with a smaller effective area, and a degraded angular resolution in one direction. This kind of regular pattern in gain correction over the array’s tilesets is sometimes encountered, but it may vary from observation to observation. The origin is not yet fully understood, but the redundancy calibration can correct for the gain variation. Starting from a corrected array, one can then choose a tileset apodization scheme (complex weights) that will suit the desired trade-off between SLL and FWHM.

On the other hand, the best-fit SLL on fully calibrated data is also bigger than the expected one for a realistically sampled square aperture by about 0.1 dB (see Figs. 15 and 16). This residual may be interpreted in terms of mutual coupling, and a simple toy model allows an estimate of the strength of these couplings between closest elements on the order of a few percent at most. That interpretation will be further investigated. If the coupling origin is confirmed, a more precise quantification at different frequencies and line of sight as well as the possibility for correcting it will be tested Censier et al. (in prep.).

Fig. 18. This drift scan of the Sun used 6 beams of EMBRACE@Nançay pointing along the trajectory of the Sun across the sky (inset top right).

7. Multibeaming

Figure 18 shows a drift scan of the Sun using the multibeam capability of EMBRACE@Nançay. Six beams were pointed on the sky along the trajectory of the Sun, including three partially overlapping beams. The result shows the Sun entering and exiting each beam and the off-pointed beams are approximately 3 dB down from the peak, as expected.

8. Noise performance and efficiencies

8.1. Sensitivity/efficiency

The system noise cannot be directly determined without filling the whole beam pattern with two known noise sources (such as cold sky and a hot load that covers the entire array) which is not practical for an instrument such as EMBRACE, however, the *ratio* of noise and efficiency can be determined while observing small sources with known flux densities or known brightness temperature distributions.

For instance, the expected main beam brightness temperature from the Sun is

$$T_{mb} = T_b^{\text{Sun}} \times \eta_{bf} \quad (13)$$

where η_{bf} is the beam filling factor for a disk-shaped source of size θ_S and a Gaussian HPBW main lobe θ_B :

$$\eta_{bf} = 1 - e^{-\ln 2 \theta_S^2 / \theta_B^2} \quad (14)$$

Given a linear receiver in the Rayleigh-Jeans regime and a switched measurement with total power values (or spectra) “on” and “off”, the antenna temperature should be

$$T_A = T_{\text{sys}} \frac{\text{on} - \text{off}}{\text{off}} \quad (15)$$

if we neglect the CMB and atmospheric contributions which are small in this context. By using the relation $T_A = \eta_{mb} T_{mb}$ we can now put everything together to find a simple expression for the ratio of system temperature and main beam efficiency:

$$\frac{T_{\text{sys}}}{\eta_{mb}} = \frac{T_b^{\text{Sun}} \eta_{bf}}{N_p} \quad (16)$$

where N_p is shorthand for the normalized raw power (on-off)/off.

Unfortunately, the Sun is highly variable at decimeter wavelengths and longer where the chromosphere and later the corona is starting to dominate over the photosphere. There are no telescopes that monitor the Sun in the low L -band range on a daily basis and we are forced to use interpolations for “Quiet Sun” brightness temperatures and accept that the result may be uncertain by up to $\sim 50\%$.

For small sources with relatively well known flux densities, one can more directly arrive at another performance measure, namely the ratio of system noise and aperture efficiency. The latter is simply the effective collecting (A_{eff}) area over the physical area (A_{phys}), which can be measured by comparing observed power from a source with its intrinsically available power over the instrument as given by the flux density multiplied by the bandwidth. The resulting expression is

$$S_{\text{source}} = \frac{2kT_{\text{sys}}}{\eta_a A_{\text{phys}}} N_p \quad (17)$$

where T_{sys}/η_a is the sought quantity. Often the entire fraction in Eq. (17) is used instead:

$$\frac{2kT_{\text{sys}}}{\eta_a A_{\text{phys}}} \triangleq \text{SEFD}$$

where SEFD refers to “System Equivalent Flux Density”.

An additional complication in the case of a dense aperture array is that the cross sectional area goes down for elevations progressively away from zenith and this can be viewed either as a decrease in physical area, or as a decrease in η_a . Theoretically, if each Vivaldi element was truly isotropic and the array perfectly dense, the received power should decrease proportionally to the projected area, i.e., as $\sin(\text{el.}) \times A_{\text{phys}}$. In reality it does not follow such a curve and it is of interest to try to characterize its elevation dependence. Since the beam pattern is not circular symmetric, the preferred manner to do this would be to track a source along fixed azimuths from zenith to low elevation. No sources follow such sky trajectories¹ and we will have to draw tentative conclusions based on results interleaved between our stronger sources (Sun, GPS, Cas A, Cyg A).

Lastly, it can also be of interest to compare the performance between the different hierarchical stages in the interferometer. Here, we restrict ourselves to compare the area efficiency of a single tileset to that of the whole array.

As can be seen, there is a difference of approximately a factor of two and we could attribute this to an additional “array efficiency” as defined in Thompson et al. (2004). Using that formalism, the η_a used previously for the full array would then be replaced with $\eta_a \eta_{\text{array}}$ where η_a now is the tileset value.

8.2. Elevation limit due to the forest

Figure 19 shows the normalized intensity for a number of observations as a function of elevation at three frequencies, using either of the two RF beams. The trends at high elevations seem mostly linear and we have tried to extrapolate these trends in order to phenomenologically estimate the value at zenith (noted at the right edge of the plots).

As comparisons to the actual measured values, we have drawn two lines. The upper dashed line is the trend the received

¹ It is worth noting that a satellite in low Earth orbit with an isotropic transmitter would be a rather good approximation due to its swift passage across the sky.

Fig. 19. Received intensity as a function of elevation for CasA and CygA at three frequencies. The vertical red lines indicate 45° elevation which is the nominal scan angle limitation for EMBRACE. The effect of the treeline is also visible at elevations below 45°.

power would follow at lower elevations if the instrument was a perfectly flat, fully sampled, infinitely thin, isotropic 2d array (i.e., having a geometric cross section fall-off as the cosine of elevation). The lower dashed line is simply a 1st order polynomial that goes through the estimated peak value, and the origin (i.e., assuming zero power at zero elevation).

When analysing the Cygnus A measurements, we consistently noted that results appear more erratic below a certain elevation when the source is setting. We have previously mostly only observed at low elevations in the south and a theory was advanced that obstruction from local vegetation could create the observed effects. An inspection of the treeline around the instrument confirmed that trees in the north west block the view up to elevations of circa 45°, whereas the view to the north east – where the source is rising – is clear down to much lower elevations.

8.3. Stability

It is already clear that the stability is such that we can successfully subtract data to get rid of systemic patterns (see Sects. 4 and 9.2). We have also tried to estimate the Allan variance although we cannot shield the instrument from the outside world. Preferably one would like to expose the instrument to a constant signal source such as a hot load. The results achieved, where we clearly still have some variability due to external sources, should thus be considered a conservative limit to the true Allan variance.

In Fig. 20, we show the Allan variance for a constant pointing stretching over three days where the total power was sampled every second. Values for six different beamlets are shown from a bandpass of 61 beamlets (beamlet = sub-band here since all beamlets were pointing in the same direction). The lower panel shows the same type of analysis but for the difference signal of two digital beams. This could be considered a measure of what is sometimes referred to as the “spectroscopic” Allan variance which normally shows better stability than the raw total power signal. To further improve the lower limit to the best-case Allan variance time we also removed a small number of relatively narrow strong features from the time signal. These signals occurred with a period of exactly one solar day and must hence be of terrestrial origin and as can be seen they had an effect on the Allan

Fig. 20. Allan variance as a function of time. This observation was performed as a three-day drift scan of Cas A pointing at $\sim 79^\circ$ elevation due south. The signals from the daily Cas A passages have been removed. In the lower panels also a few strong signals have been removed that occurred on a solar day basis (those could be due to any kind of human activity such as a transmitter that is scheduled to turn on or increase its power for a short while every day, or artificially induced changes to the instrument environment such as variations in the AC power grid).

variance down to time scales < 10 s. The lower panel demonstrates with some confidence that the Allan time of the system (where drift noise starts to dominate over thermal noise) is better than 30 s.

9. Astronomical sources

9.1. Cassiopeia A

Cas A is one of our two good candidates for absolute efficiency estimations due to its constant flux (on short time-scales) and being a point source for EMBRACE. A detailed flux model over frequency and time for Cas A (which is an expanding supernova remnant that fades over time in the radio) has not been presented since Baars et al. (1977) who assembled observations during the 1950's, 60's, and 70's and calculated fading rates over a large set of frequencies and extrapolated an equivalent flux density spectrum for the epoch 1980. The 1980 values are still sometimes used today and they severely overestimate the current flux density of Cas A. On the other hand, if one uses the fading rates of Baars et al. (1977), valid some 50 yr ago, to extrapolate from 1980 to a much later time, one significantly *under* estimates the flux because there is ample proof that the fading rates have decreased.

In our observations of Cas A and Cyg A in 2012, we noted that Cas A seemed to be $\sim 10\%$ stronger than Cyg A at 1176 MHz. This assumes that the system and ambient noises were constant between the measurements which may not be true but we find it unlikely that it varied by more than 10%. According to the flux model by Baars et al. (1977), the flux for epoch 2012.6 at this frequency should be lower than that of Cyg A. Since no large span absolute flux spectrum of Cas A has been measured in recent years, our approach to this conflict is to still use the 1980 model spectrum from Baars et al. (1977), but extrapolate using the few more recent estimates for fading rates that can be found in the literature, notably at 927 MHz (Vinyajkin & Razin 2004) and 1405 MHz (Reichart & Stephens 2000), and made linear interpolations to find fading rates for the frequencies observed with EMBRACE@Nançay. Although it does not perfectly fit with our observed $S_{\text{CasA}}/S_{\text{CygA}}$, it does agree better than either using the Baars model propagated to the 2010's or than directly using the 1980 spectrum ignoring any fading during the last 30 yr.

It should be noted that, according to Reichart & Stephens (2000), fading rate decrease is only seen at lower frequencies (the transition being anywhere between $\lambda \approx 4\text{--}10$ cm). Furthermore, according to them, the fading rate of 0.6–0.7% per year previously seen at 7.8 GHz and above, now appears to apply to all frequencies down to a few 10ths of MHz.

9.2. Spectral line observation of Messier 33

With a relatively modest collecting area, strong distinct spectral signatures are restricted to artificial sources such as satellite carriers, and the Milky Way HI line at 1420.4 MHz. The latter is distributed throughout the entire sky and mostly lacks clear unique features on spatial scales of the array beam. An example of an early EMBRACE HI observation – at a time when tilesets could not yet be phased up to form an array beam – was to point all tileset beams to a certain longitude in the galactic plane and verify that the resulting spectra had the Doppler components expected in that slot of the plane compared to published surveys.

The Triangulum galaxy (M33) is the most distant object that can be observed with the naked eye in the optical (under very good conditions). It is an ideal source to observe with EMBRACE due to its size (about 1° diameter, i.e., slightly smaller than the synthesized beam) and its radial velocity ($v_{\text{LSR}} \approx -200$ km s $^{-1}$).

For atomic hydrogen 21 cm observations (the strongest astronomical spectral line within the EMBRACE bandpass by orders of magnitude), the latter fact is very fortuitous; the line-of-sight orientation of the M33 disk leads to a relatively narrow line profile (FWZI ~ 200 km s) that is clearly separated from the much stronger local Milky Way foreground which lie at an LSR velocity near zero in the direction of M33. Most other nearby spiral galaxies overlap with the galactic foreground and are weaker due to larger distances. The nearby M31 (Andromeda) overlaps marginally with local gas but is much larger and closer to edge-on orientation and would be more suitable for one-dimensional mapping observations with EMBRACE.

During the summer of 2013, M33 was observed both at the coarse sub-band spectral resolution (1 sub-band = 195 kHz = 41.2 km s $^{-1}$) as a preparatory test, and then at high resolution by capturing the stream of UDP packets for half an hour (160 Gbyte in total) and channelizing each sub-band 16-fold. The two digital beams that are always present in the backend output (referred to as the X and Y directions due to its LOFAR heritage) were employed to create FoV symmetric on- and off-beams in a manner

Fig. 21. *Top left:* raw averaged spectra (blue = on, red = off). Note that the horizontal axis has increasing frequency to the right. The galactic foreground is visible in both positions around channel 470. *Mid right:* coarsely calibrated spectrum with four offset sub-bands corrected by adjusting their level to that of neighbouring sub-bands. Also shown in green is a second order baseline fit. *Bottom left:* baseline subtracted spectrum where obvious spikes have been interpolated out. A comparison with the LAB survey spectrum is shown in golden/yellow. The detailed line shape agreement is excellent apart from a portion that is obviously associated with an unstable sub-band. Note that the galactic foreground has mostly been subtracted out in the EMBRACE spectrum with only a negative residual remaining.

described in Fig. 6. A spectrum was subsequently created in the simplest way possible; by coaveraging all data for each position separately before off-position subtraction and normalization, and then multiplying by a constant factor so that our result matches a template spectrum we retrieved from the LAB survey (Kalberla et al. 2005)² convolved to the EMBRACE array beam size.

The result and several steps in the process are illustrated in Fig. 21. This approach yields overall rather benign baseline shapes indicating that much weaker signals can probably be detected. The sub-band “staircasing” and spikes/perturbations may be caused by external or internal RFI. The first portion of Fig. 21 clearly shows that raw channelized spectra are not dominated by thermal noise but rather a static square wave pattern originating in the polyphase filter stage earlier in the chain (an identical effect is seen in channelized single station LOFAR spectra). The (on-off)/off operation appears to remove this pattern extremely effectively.

9.3. Pulsar PSR B0329+54

Figure 22 demonstrates over 9 h of tracking the pulsar PSR B0329+54. Its pulsed signal is clearly detected after several minutes, and the array continues tracking, measuring continuously the pulsar, except where RFI has been filtered at 21 500 s. The array was configured with a bandwidth of 12 MHz (62 beamlets) centred at 1176.45 MHz. The array was phased-up using the GPS BIIF-2 satellite, and the phase parameters were applied for the observation of PSR B0329+54. The high data rate output from the RSP boards is read by a data acquisition system running the Oxford ARTEMIS pulsar processing software (Serylak et al. 2013).

Fig. 22. PSR B0329+54. The pulsar is detected after several minutes as shown in this dynamic plot folded at the pulsar period of 715 msec. The figure was plotted using PSRCHIVE software (Hotan et al. 2004; van Straten et al. 2012).

9.4. Daily observations

In November 2013, EMBRACE@Nançay began a long term campaign of observation of pulsar B0329+54. EMBRACE@Nançay has been running autonomously and performing the pulsar observation every day centred at two frequencies: 970 MHz and 1176 MHz (Nov. 2013 to Aug. 2014) and 970 MHz and 1420 MHz (Aug. 2014 to present). Since August 2014, EMBRACE@Nançay has been using saved calibration tables which greatly simplified the observation planning. There is no need to plan for a calibration run before each observation. In August 2015, drift scans of Cas A and Cyg A were added to the daily observational programme. EMBRACE@Nançay is now operating in the manner of a facility instrument, doing pre-planned observations, and running a long term observational campaign.

10. Summary and future work

The technology of dense aperture array uses a large number of antenna elements at half wavelength spacings to fully sample the aperture. EMBRACE@Nançay is the first fully operational demonstrator of this technology which is large enough to make interesting radio astronomical detections.

One of the main concerns with the dense aperture array technology is the high system complexity which could complicate operations and some have expressed doubt that operating such a complicated instrument might not be feasible for a

² <http://www.astro.uni-bonn.de/hisurvey/profile/>

facility observatory but EMBRACE@Nançay has clearly shown that dense aperture array technology is perfectly viable for radio astronomy. We have demonstrated its capability as a radio astronomy instrument, including astronomical observations of pulsars and spectroscopic observations of galaxies. We have also demonstrated its multibeam capability.

While the system setup is complex, once implemented, EMBRACE@Nançay behaves with remarkable stability. System issues, such as the correlator offset, are characterized and corrections applied to the data are valid in the very long term and need not be remeasured frequently. EMBRACE@Nançay has been in operation for four years with little or no change in its performance. In particular, calibration tables used for phase calibration continue to be valid over at least a period of 6 months.

The dense aperture array technology has the advantage of relatively low cost fabrication being composed of large numbers of small components which can be easily shipped and assembled on site. After an initial period of commissioning, the system will operate with reliability and with predictable and stable performance.

An important disadvantage of the dense aperture array technology is its relatively large power requirement. The large number of analogue electronic components associated with the signal chain of each antenna element, together with the digital processing requirements for beamforming and/or aperture synthesis, makes a system which is rather power hungry. A number of solutions are being studied to reduce the overall power consumption (bij de Vaate et al. 2014), including the use of high speed digital samplers which will eliminate the frequency down-conversion stage and not only reduce overall power consumption but will also solve the problem of correlator offset due to a distributed Local Oscillator signal.

Dense aperture array technology is a viable solution for the SKA, offering the benefit of an enormous field of view together with great flexibility for system setups, including multibeaming with multiple and independent observation modes. The SKA built using dense aperture array technology will be the most rapid astronomical survey machine.

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References

- Armour, W., Karastergiou, A., Giles, M., et al. 2012, *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XXI*, 461, 33
- Baars, J. W. M., Genzel, R., Pauliny-Toth, I. I. K., & Witzel, A. 1977, *A&A*, 61, 99
- Berenz, T. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 039
- Bianchi, G., Morawietz, J., Mariotti, S., et al. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 041
- bij de Vaate, J. G., Torchinsky, S.A., Faulkner A. J., et al. 2014, SKA Mid Frequency Aperture Arrays: Technology for the Ultimate Survey Machine, in Proc. URSI General Assembly Beijing, China, 16–23 August
- Bosse, S., Barth, S., Torchinsky, S. A., & Da Silva, B. 2010, Proc. European Microwave Integrated Circuits Conference (EuMIC 2010), 27–28 September 2010, Paris, France, 106
- Braun, R., & van Cappellen, W. 2006, Aperture Arrays for the SKA: Dense or Sparse? SKA Memo 87 [[arXiv:astro-ph/0611160](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0611160)]
- Dewdney, P. E., Hall, P. J., Schilizzi, R. T., & Lazio, T. J. W. 2009, *Proc. IEEE*, 97, 1482
- Hotan, A. W., van Straten, W., & Manchester, R. N. 2004, *PASA*, 21, 302
- Johnson, R. C. 1993, *Antenna Engineering Handbook*, 3rd edn. (McGraw-Hill)
- Kalberla, P. M. W., Burton, W. B., Hartmann, D., et al. 2005, *A&A*, 440, 775
- Kant, G. W., van der Wal, E., Ruiter, M., & Benthem, P. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 037
- Kant, G. W., Patel, P. D., Wijnholds, S. J., Ruiter, M., & van der Wal, E. 2011, *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propagation* 59, 1990
- Karastergiou, A., Chennamangalam, J., Armour, W., et al. 2015, *MNRAS*, 452, 1254
- Liu, A., Tegmark, M., Morrison, S., Lutmirski, A., & Zaldrriaga, M. 2010, *MNRAS*, 408, 1029
- Marthi, V. R., & Chengalur, J. 2014, *MNRAS*, 437, 524
- Monari, J., Perini, F., Mariotti, S., et al. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 040
- Noble, B., & Daniel, J. W. 1977, *Applied Linear Algebra*, Prentice-Hall (Englewood Cliffs, NJ)
- Noorishad, P., Wijnholds, S. J., van Ardenne, A., & van der Hulst, J. M. 2012, *A&A*, 545, A108
- Olofsson, A. O. H., Torchinsky, S.A., Chemin, L., et al. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 042
- Picard, P., Renaud, P., Taffoureau, C., et al. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 038
- Renaud, P., Taffoureau, C., Picard, P., et al. 2011, Monitoring and Control of EMBRACE, a 4608 Elements Phased Array for Radio Astronomy, Proc. Astron. Data Analysis Software Systems, Paris, 6–10 November
- Reichart, D. E., & Stephens, A. W. 2000, *ApJ*, 537, 904
- Serylak, M., Karastergiou, A., Williams, C., et al. 2013, *IAU Symp.*, 291, 492
- Singh, H., Sneha, H. L., & Jha, R. M. 2013, Mutual Coupling in Phased Arrays: A Review, *Int. J. Antennas and Propagation*, ID 348123
- Thompson, A. R., Moran, J. M., Swenson, G. W. Jr. 2004, *Interferometry and Synthesis in Radio Astronomy*, 2nd edn. (Wiley-VCH)
- Torchinsky, S. A., Olofsson, A. O. H., Karastergiou, A., et al. 2013, SF2A-2013: Proc. Annual meeting of the French Society of Astronomy and Astrophysics, 439
- Torchinsky, S. A., Olofsson, A. O. H., Censier, B., et al. 2015, *J. Instr.*, 10, C07002
- van Haarlem, M. P., Wise, M. W., Gunst, A. W., et al. 2013, *A&A*, 556, A2
- van Straten, W., Demorest, P., & Osłowski, S. 2012, *Astron. Res. Technol.*, 9, 237
- Vinyajkin, E. N., & Razin, V. A. 2004, ArXiv e-prints [[arXiv:astro-ph/0412593](https://arxiv.org/abs/astro-ph/0412593)]
- Wijnholds, S. J., Kant, G. W., van der Wal, E., et al. 2009, Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA, Limelette, Belgium, eds. S. A. Torchinsky et al., 043

5.5 QUBIC III: Laboratory Characterization

En début 2019, on m'a confié la responsabilité de l'étalonnage de QUBIC. Le projet a procédé ensuite à une longue campagne de tests approfondis dans laquelle on a démontré la faisabilité du concept d'interférométrie bolométrique et sa capacité de faire la spectro-imagerie. On a aussi démontré la fonctionnalité générale de QUBIC y compris le système cryogénique, les multiples mécanismes, l'utilisation d'une source de calibration artificielle, et la polarimétrie de très haute pureté ainsi que la capacité de faire la modulation de la polarisation avec la lame demi-onde. Ceci a abouti à la publication du document de calibration (**Torchinsky** et al. 2020) présenté à la revue du projet en janvier 2020.

Par la suite, la collaboration du projet QUBIC a décidé de publier une série de papiers pour la plupart basés sur les résultats de la campagne de test élaborés dans le document de calibration. Le troisième papier de la série, reproduit ici, expose les résultats de la campagne de test en laboratoire.

QUBIC III: Laboratory characterization

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Abstract. We report on an extensive test campaign of a prototype version of the QUBIC (Q & U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology) instrument, carried out at Astroparticle Physics and Cosmology (APC) in Paris. Exploiting the novel concept called bolometric interferometry, QUBIC is designed to measure the CMB polarization at 150 and 220 GHz from a high altitude site at Alto Chorillo, Argentina. The prototype model called QUBIC Technological Demonstrator (QUBIC-TD) operates in a single frequency band (150 GHz) and with a reduced number of baselines, but it contains all the elements of the QUBIC instrument in its final configuration. The test campaign included measurements of the synthesized beam and of the polarization performance, as well as a verification of the interference fringe pattern. A modulated, frequency-tunable millimetre-wave source was placed in the telescope far-field and was used to simulate a point source. The QUBIC-TD field of view was scanned across the source to produce beam maps. Our measurements confirm the frequency-dependent behaviour of the beam profile, which gives QUBIC the possibility to do spectral imaging. The measured polarization performance indicates a cross-polarization leakage less than 0.6%. We also successfully tested the polarization modulation system, which is provided by a rotating half wave plate. We demonstrate the full mapmaking pipeline using data from this measurement

campaign, effectively giving an end-to-end checkout of the entire QUBIC system, including all hardware subsystems, their interfaces, and the software to operate the whole system and run the analysis. Our results confirm the viability of bolometric interferometry for measurements of the CMB polarization.

Keywords: CMBR detectors, CMBR experiments, CMBR polarisation, gravitational waves and CMBR polarization

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1 Introduction

The detection of primordial B-mode polarization in the cosmic microwave background (CMB) is the subject of a worldwide effort due to its importance as a confirmation of the inflationary model of cosmology. A clear detection of polarization B-modes in the CMB at degree angular scales, distinguished from B-modes incurred by foreground effects (including lensing), is evidence of primordial gravitational waves expected during the inflationary phase in the earliest moments of the universe. For an overview see Kamionkowski & Kovetz [1].

From an observational point of view, the linear polarization of the CMB is described by the Q and U Stokes parameters than can be transformed mathematically into the scalar E and B-modes respectively corresponding to the curl and curl-free part of the polarization field on the sky. E-modes have been well measured to be of order $\sim 1 \mu\text{K}$ [2–4], as expected from the theory, while the B-mode component will be an even weaker signal, at least an order of magnitude below the E-mode [5]. As a result, the measurement of B-mode polarization is a difficult exercise of extracting a signal buried deep within other signals, be them astrophysical foregrounds or instrumental systematics mixing Q and U observables resulting into a leakage of the large E-modes into the small B-modes.

The QUBIC instrument uses a novel technology, called Bolometric Interferometry, that combines the high sensitivity offered by bolometers to the signal purity from interference fringes measurement. QUBIC has degree-scale angular resolution in order to target the primordial CMB B-mode polarization. The instrument is designed with particular attention to the limitation and control of systematic effects [6]. See also in this series of papers O’Sullivan et al. [7] for the optics design, Masi et al. [8] for the cryogenics design, and Piat et al. [9] for the detectors and readout electronics. QUBIC uses the technique of interferometry which leads to the possibility of doing “self-calibration”, a procedure that

ensures fine control of instrumental systematic effects [10]. Furthermore, the resulting frequency-dependent beam profile on the sky leads to the possibility of doing spectral imaging (see Mousset et al. [11] in this series of papers). Bolometric interferometry is the marriage of techniques bringing together the great sensitivity and large bandwidth of bolometers and the instrumental control and high fidelity imaging of aperture synthesis. Using this innovative approach, any residual systematic effect in the data will be largely independent from those in other experiments, thus providing a unique dataset in the context of the worldwide experimental effort.

This article describes the laboratory characterization and calibration phase QUBIC has undergone. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of the Q & U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology (QUBIC) Technological Demonstrator instrument including an introduction to the concept of bolometric interferometry. The laboratory setup is described in section 3 with particular attention given to the placement and alignment of the calibration source. This is followed by section 4 describing various measurement results and analysis. Section 4.1 presents the measured bandpass of QUBIC. Section 4.2 shows the measured response to modulated polarization using the rotating half wave plate (HWP), a critical element to assess the system polarization performance. In section 4.3 we discuss the measurement of interference fringes on the focal plane using the mechanical switches in the horn array to select baselines. In section 4.4 we show measurements of the QUBIC synthesized beam, and in section 4.5 we demonstrate the results of the QUBIC mapmaking pipeline by generating a “sky” map of the calibration source using the calibration information determined from our measurements. Finally, some concluding remarks are given in section 5.

2 The QUBIC instrument

QUBIC is an imaging interferometer which measures “visibilities” which are the complex (amplitude and phase) correlations between each antenna pair (baseline). In radio astronomy, the visibilities are recorded directly. A “correlator” digitizes the signals and multiplies pairs of signals to produce a stream of complex numbers, each of which corresponds to the cross correlation product of an antenna-pair. Channelization of the spectral bandpass permits signal processing of individual, very narrow bands, and for each channel the signal is nearly monochromatic. In radio astronomy, large bandwidths are achieved by adding more digital electronics.

2.1 Bolometric interferometry

A bolometric interferometer takes advantage of the high sensitivity and large bandwidth of bolometers while also benefiting from the calibration technique possible with an imaging interferometer. The QUBIC focal planes are populated with transition-edge sensor (TES) bolometers (see Piat et al. [9] in this special issue for more details). The spatial sampling of the sky is generated by placing a cluster of back-to-back horns that behave effectively as electromagnetic nozzles. This horn cluster creates the $u - v$ sampling of the aperture plane equivalent to what is done by a distribution of antennas in a radio array. For the bolometric interferometer, instead of sampling the signals and computing the cross correlations between antenna pairs, the interference pattern is imaged.

A single image of the interference pattern has all the information convolved together resulting in observing the sky through a synthesized beam. The shape of this synthesized beam is given by the combination of all individual baselines (all pairs of horns). The bolometric

interferometer ends up being a synthesized imager observing the sky through its synthesized beam just the same way as a classical imager observes the sky through the beam formed by the telescope. For calibration and instrumental systematic effects studies it is however crucial to extract the individual visibilities. By blocking all horns except two, we would measure the interference pattern of that baseline. For technical reasons in the QUBIC Technological Demonstrator (QUBIC-TD), only two horn shutters can be shut at a time, but by making a series of measurements with different pairs of horns blocked, the result is equivalent to having all horns blocked except two [10]. The 20×20 cluster of horns in the QUBIC Full Instrument (QUBIC-FI) has 400 horns making $n(n-1)/2 = 79800$ baselines which are needed to be observed individually for self-calibration. The QUBIC-TD, whose tests are reported in this paper, has a smaller horn array with 64 horns in an 8×8 square array giving 2016 baselines.

The main parameters which determine the general performance of the bolometric interferometer are the number of baselines and the number of detectors. Performance of the bolometric interferometer improves as the number of baselines increases since this improves the application of self-calibration by increasing the number of parameters. It also leads to a more sharply defined synthesized beam. A larger cluster of horns provides more baselines, but this in turn must be sampled by a larger array of detectors in the focal plane. A larger horn cluster is also effectively a larger telescope aperture which increases the power throughput of the system. Increasing the number of detectors therefore not only improves the sampling of focal plane but also improves the sensitivity of the instrument by detecting more power. As a result, the overall performance of the bolometric interferometer is not simply a function of the number of detectors in the focal plane. It also depends on the number of baselines formed by the horn array which must be large enough to match the surface covered by detectors in the focal plane.

An additional feature of bolometric interferometry is the possibility to do spectral imaging. The synthesized beam is predicted to vary in a well-understood way with frequency. In particular, the beam secondary lobes are closer to the central lobe for higher frequency of incident radiation while the central lobe remains in the same place across the spectral band. As a result, the time ordered data (TOD) effectively samples different electromagnetic frequencies as the beam passes over the same point in the sky. An important objective of our calibration campaign was to verify this behaviour with the QUBIC-TD.

This spectral selectivity can be deconvolved in the data post processing. The spectral resolution improves with the number of baselines as the synthesized beam has finer secondary lobes with a larger cluster of horns. Spectral imaging is an innovative feature of bolometric interferometry which gives QUBIC an important advantage over other CMB imagers (see Hamilton et al. [12] and Mousset et al. [11] for details) and the expected frequency dependence of QUBIC's synthesized beam has been confirmed (see section 4.4).

2.2 Design overview

QUBIC employs an optical system consisting of back-to-back horns that select the relevant baselines and an optical combiner focusing on a bolometric focal plane. The optical combiner forms interference fringes while the bolometers average their powers over timescales much larger than the period of the light waves. This is therefore the optical equivalent of a wide-band correlator in classical interferometry. The instrument operates at cryogenic temperatures thanks to a large cryostat described in Masi et al. [8].

A schematic of the design of the QUBIC-FI is shown in figure 1 and the main instrument parameters are listed in table 1. The QUBIC-TD has the same optical layout and differs

Figure 1. Schematic of the QUBIC-FI instrument (above) and sectional cut of the cryostat (below) showing the same sub-systems in their real configuration. The second detector array is not shown in the CAD rendered image below.

Parameter	QUBIC-TD	QUBIC-FI
Frequency channels	150 GHz	150 GHz & 220 GHz
Frequency range 150 GHz	[131–169] GHz	[131–169] GHz
Frequency range 220 GHz	—	[192.5–247.5] GHz
Window Aperture [m]	0.56	0.56
Number of horns	64	400
Number of detectors	248	992×2
Detector noise [$\text{W}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$]	2.05×10^{-16}	4.7×10^{-17}
Focal plane temp. [mK]	300	300
Sky Coverage	1.5%	1.5%
Synthesized beam FWHM [degrees]	0.68	0.39 (150 GHz), 0.27 (220 GHz)

Table 1. QUBIC main parameters

only in the number of horns and detectors, and it lacks the dichroic and second focal plane for 220 GHz. The sky signal first goes through a 56 cm diameter window made of ultra high molecular weight polyethylene followed by a series of low-pass filters cutting off frequencies outside the desired band. The window is not anti-reflection coated. The filters are Cardiff metal mesh filters (see O’Sullivan et al. [7] for details).

The next optical component is the stepped rotating HWP which modulates incoming polarization (see D’Alessandro et al. [13] for details). The HWP is a metal-mesh device as described by Pisano et al. [14]. A single linear polarization is selected just after polarization modulation by a wire-grid. In this scheme, any unwanted cross-polarization which might be introduced by components later in the optical chain do not affect the result since the bolometers absorb all radiation, independent of polarization.

The next optical device in the QUBIC-FI is an array of 400 back-to-back corrugated horns made of an assembly of two 400-horn arrays, composed of 175 aluminium platelets (0.3 mm thick) chemically etched to reproduce the corrugations required for the horns to achieve the required performance. The horn mouth diameter is 12 mm and the spacing between horn centres on a row is 14 mm. For the QUBIC-TD, there are only 64 horns. Both front and back horns are identical with a field of view of 13 degrees FWHM with secondary lobes below -25 dB [15]. An array of mechanical shutters (RF switches) separates the two back-to-back horn arrays in order to be able to close or open horns for self-calibration (see section 4.3). The shutters are spring loaded and activated by applying a voltage to an induction coil. As a result, the shutter requires continuous electrical current in order to remain closed. This dissipates some heat such that it is only possible to activate a maximum of two shutters at a time without over heating the horn array which is maintained at 1 K.

The back-horns directly illuminate the two-mirror off-axis Gregorian optical combiner [7] which focuses the signal onto the two perpendicular focal planes in the QUBIC-FI and only one focal plane in the QUBIC-TD. In the QUBIC-FI, a dichroic filter splits the incoming waves into two wide bands centred at 150 GHz for the on-axis focal plane and 220 GHz for the off-axis focal plane. The QUBIC-FI focal planes are each equipped with 992 NbSi TES [9] cooled to 320 mK using a double-stage $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ sorption cooler [8]. The QUBIC-TD has only 248 TES.

A schematic view and CAD model of the cryostat can be seen in figure 1. The cryostat weighs roughly 800 kg and is around 1.6 m high with a 1.4 m diameter. The QUBIC-TD

Figure 2. Layout for the calibration source relative to the QUBIC instrument.

includes all the critical elements of the QUBIC-FI, thus making the test campaign presented here representative of the complete configuration. The QUBIC-TD uses the same cryostat, cooling system, filters and general sub-system architecture as the QUBIC-FI but with only 64 back-to-back horns and smaller mirrors to match the illumination of the 8×8 horn-array. It has a single 248 TES bolometer array operating at 150 GHz. The QUBIC-FI will have improved performance because of the increased size of the horn cluster and the increased number of detectors, as explained in section 1. Also, the QUBIC-FI detectors will be background-limited. The QUBIC-TD detection chain is currently not background-limited because of aliasing in the readout system [9]. The QUBIC-FI will have increased sampling frequency and will add Nyquist inductors to mitigate this effect.

Throughout this paper, we use our in-house Python-based software called `qubicsoft`¹ for data analysis, and for hardware control and monitoring. The `qubicsoft` package is also used for data simulations, except where otherwise indicated.

3 Calibration source

3.1 Setup for QUBIC-TD

Characterization of the QUBIC-TD instrument is done primarily using a frequency-tunable monochromatic point source in the far-field. This permits measurement of the bandpass (section 4.1), the polarization performance (section 4.2), the measurement of interference fringes (section 4.3), and the beam point spread function (PSF, section 4.4 and section 4.5). This section describes the optical setup used to characterize QUBIC-TD.

The setup is shown in the sketch of figure 2. The calibration source points at a flat mirror which redirects the beam into the QUBIC cryostat window. There is an 11 m optical path putting the calibration source effectively in the far field (see section 3.2).

¹<https://github.com/qubicsoft>.

Figure 3. *Left:* photo of QUBIC looking along the line-of-sight from the calibration source. The reflection of the window is clearly visible in the flat mirror. *Right:* the flat mirror is mounted on a scaffold at a height of 3.7 m and has a finely adjustable tilt angle using a system composed of a long screw.

The flat mirror is an aluminium sheet mounted on a scaffolding at a height of 3.7 m (photo in figure 3). The tilt angle of the flat mirror can be adjusted by a long screw ensuring precise selection for the correct tilt angle.

Alignment of the system was accomplished using a laser temporarily mounted at the window of the QUBIC cryostat, pointing normal to the window (photo figure 4). The laser light is reflected from the flat mirror to the calibration source where a small flat mirror was fitted to the front of the calibration source feedhorn. The laser reflects from the mirror at the feedhorn mouth and returns to the large flat mirror and finally to the QUBIC cryostat window. In the photo (figure 4), one can clearly see the spot of the laser on the corner of the laser mounting structure on the window. The alignment is therefore precise to within a fraction of a degree which is well within the tolerance necessary to have the calibration source visible to the QUBIC-TD.

The calibration source system is composed by the source itself together with a dedicated electronic subsystem supporting its operations. The calibration source was purchased from Virginia Diodes Incorporated (VDI) electronics² and is composed of a synthesizer providing frequencies around 10 GHz followed by a two-stage multiplication chain. A coaxial cable from the synthesizer connected by standard SMA connectors leads to the first of two multipliers

²<https://vadiodes.com>.

Figure 4. Photo of the alignment procedure. The laser is mounted orthogonal to the cryostat window and shines towards the flat mirror, sending the light to the calibration source feedhorn at the other side of the room. A small mirror fitted to the mouth of the feedhorn sends the laser light back on the same path to the cryostat window. The laser spot is clearly visible on the laser mount structure. The inset, top-right, shows a close-up of the calibration source with a mirror mounted on the horn mouth and the laser spot within the area of the horn mouth.

which are in a waveguide-coupled chain. Together, they multiply the base frequency by 12 resulting in frequencies around 150 GHz. The signal is transmitted by rectangular waveguide after the final multiplier to a profiled corrugated feedhorn. The range of the system is between 130 GHz and 170 GHz with a frequency tuning resolution of 144 Hz. The nominal output power is +9 dBm and it can be modulated with a maximum amplitude of 1.25 dB. The frequency is configured via USB connection by a nearby Raspberry Pi mini computer (see photo figure 5).

A signal generator provides a square wave at around 1 Hz which is used to modulate the amplitude of the calibration source. The Raspberry Pi configures the signal generator, selecting the amplitude, offset, frequency, shape, and duty cycle. A directional coupler at the waveguide before the entrance to the corrugated feedhorn provides a port for monitoring the output power of the calibration source. The horn return loss is less than -30 dB, as reported by the supplier of the horn, Custom Microwaves Inc.,³ and therefore the monitoring of the output power variation at the end of the multiplier chain is a reliable method for monitoring the power variation in the calibration source output power illuminating the aperture of QUBIC-TD. A probe on this port provides a voltage which is a function of the output power. This voltage is sent to an analogue-to-digital converter (ADC) board integrated in the

³<https://custommicrowave.com>.

Figure 5. Photo of the VDI millimetre-wave source. The electronics include a signal generator for modulating the calibration source with a square wave. The output power monitor of the calibration source is sent through an amplifier and then digitized by an ADC board integrated in the Raspberry Pi (seen suspended on the cables below the calibration source).

Raspberry Pi mini computer which broadcasts the data on the internal network along with a timestamp for each sample. There are approximately 300 samples per second. A command line interface written in Python is used to configure the calibration source setup. This system accepts commands via network socket and can be easily interfaced by the graphical user interface called `QubicStudio`.

There is an important difference in the background loading for the QUBIC-TD in the lab compared to an on-sky measurement. The lab background loading is of the order of 300 K, while a measurement on the sky will have background loading of the order of a few tens of K. In order to reduce the laboratory background loading, the QUBIC-TD is equipped with a neutral density filter (NDF) mounted at the 1 K stage. The NDF transmits 9% of all incoming radiation. This reduces the 300 K ambient temperature background to about 27 K which approximates what is expected from the sky at the 5000 m above sea-level observing site. As a result, the loading on the bolometers in the laboratory measurements with the NDF approximates what it will be at the observing site without the NDF.

A second difference between the setup in the lab and the planned setup for the instrument at its observing site is the power received by the calibration source. The VDI millimetre-wave source emits significant power. In the laboratory setup, it is placed at a distance of 11.4 m, while at the observing site, the calibration source will be mounted on a tower 40 m distant from the base of the QUBIC telescope, giving an optical path length of approximately 60 m. This means that the calibration source detected in the lab is roughly 30 times more powerful than

in the setup planned at the observing site. For this reason, Eccosorb material AN72 is placed at the calibration source feedhorn mouth in order to attenuate the signal to approximately 3% across the band (see Schillaci et al. [16] for a measurement of attenuation by Eccosorb).

Figure 6 shows the signal response of all the TES detectors in the QUBIC-TD array. The source was set at 150 GHz and was modulated with a square wave with 3 second period (0.333 Hz) and a 33% duty cycle. The period was chosen to be significantly longer than the expected time constant of the TES bolometers, and with a non-symmetrical duty cycle (1/3, 2/3) in order to easily distinguish the OFF and ON cycles. Figure 7 shows in detail the signal measured by a typical well-behaved TES together with the modulation signal measured by the power monitor. There is a clear correlation between the two and the time constant can be estimated to be of the order of 40 ms. A detailed analysis of the QUBIC-TD bolometer response is given in Piat et al. [9].

While the APC laboratory is not equipped as an anechoic environment (see figure 3), our measurements show no evidence of reflection effects from the surroundings. The mapping of the beam did not show unwanted artefacts (see, e.g., figure 16 in section 4.4, and also the result of the mapmaking algorithm, figure 18, in section 4.5). Nevertheless, it is possible that low-level reflections may have contributed some extra noise to the image. The diffuse features around the peaks may be due to reflections in the lab, or they are possibly due to instrumental imperfections that can be dealt with at the map-making stage once they are measured. These maps are expected to be improved when the measurements are made at the observing site where external reflections will be at a much lower level, while instrumental artefacts remain the same.

Another possibility for reflections might come from the face-to-face setup of the calibration source and the QUBIC window. This could lead to standing-waves but a number of parameters mitigate this possibility. The long optical path between the cryostat window and the calibration source imposes significant attenuation of the signal after reflection, and multiple reflections will have insignificant power. The mouth of the feedhorn at the calibration source subtends an angle of approximately 0.05 degrees, therefore exposing negligible area to the cryostat window for reflections. Finally, a layer of Eccosorb AN72 was placed in front of the calibration source feedhorn mouth for further attenuation. If we use purely geometric optics reasoning, which gives an upper limit to the magnitude of standing waves, we can simply compare the area of the two face-to-face surfaces. The QUBIC-TD window has a diameter of 56 cm and the calibration source feedhorn has a diameter of 1 cm. The ratio of the areas of these surfaces is less than 0.03%. Therefore the power is attenuated by 0.03%, without considering the attenuation by the Eccosorb and by the distance between the two surfaces. This is below our measurement precision. For example, the bandpass measurement of figure 10 in section 4.1 shows no evidence of standing waves.

3.2 Optical modelling of the calibration source as viewed by QUBIC

For an accurate analysis of the instrument performance, it is important to have a simulation of the expected pattern on the focal plane. For this purpose, we use optical modelling with the source set at the same distance (11.4 m from the QUBIC-TD window) as in our experimental setup. The comparison between measurement and model is done regardless of the distance to the calibration source, however it is also useful to have the calibration source sufficiently in the far-field so that it appears as an unresolved point source resulting in the focal plane pattern being the PSF of the instrument. The PSF has several sharp features with which to

Figure 6. The first measurement of the calibration source by QUBIC. Each box in the plot shows a 20 second timeline for the detector in that position in the focal plane. The vertical axis for each plot is in arbitrary power units, scaled for the minimum and maximum of each plot. The signal is clearly seen in most pixels, corresponding to the good pixels in the array (see Piat et al. [9] for a discussion on the bolometer array performance). The curves in blue and black differentiate the two read-out electronics chains (128 detectors per read-out electronics box). The black, filled-in “pixels” in the bottom-left are empty positions. The QUBIC-FI will have four arrays equivalent to this one in order to make a roughly circular focal plane for each frequency channel.

compare. Once in the far-field the focal plane pattern does not vary significantly with the distance to the calibrator.

Using the software package MODAL (Maynooth University, see O’Sullivan et al. [7] for details about optics modelling), a model of the 150 GHz source was positioned 1 m and 10 m from the aperture. For each position the following quantities were determined:

- the incident radiation over the horn array.
- the horn output (at a distance of 60 cm) for two arbitrarily chosen horns in the 8×8 horn array.

Figure 7. Overlay of the signal detected by a TES detector of the QUBIC array (blue curve) together with the modulated calibration source signal as measured by the calibration source power monitor (red curve).

- the resulting PSF on the focal plane formed from the radiation for all 64 horns in the array.

Both the amplitude and phase of the incident field from the calibrator source were investigated at the input of the horn array. It can be seen in figure 8 that at a distance of 10 m, the amplitude and phase of the calibrator beam is quite uniform over the horn array.

Investigating the output of different horns in the array provides another insight into the coupling to the incident source radiation. Incident radiation couples with the horn and excites it, causing it to emit a beam which is approximately a 12.9° Gaussian beam in the far-field. For an on-axis source in the far-field of the instrument, the radiation over the array is uniform and the coupling the same for all of the horns, meaning that all the horns will emit a Gaussian-like beam of the same amplitude and the same phase. If the incident radiation is not uniform over the array, as is the case for the source at 1 m, then it will not couple to the horns in the same way and the horn output will be different. When the source is farther away, the coupling across the array becomes more uniform. All of the horn beams have the same profile. The difference in coupling can be seen as the difference in the peak intensity. With the calibration source at 10 m distance, the beams from the two sample horns are similar.

The PSF calculated for some of the calibrator source distances investigated are shown in figure 9 [17]. With the source placed 1 m from the array, the image on the focal plane has more relative power spread throughout the image and a less clearly visible cross-like structure compared to the image with the source further away. A source distance of 10 m shows a pattern that resembles the expected PSF figure 9 (middle). This implies that the source distance of 11.4 m is sufficiently faraway for the calibrator to be used to measure the PSF of the TD. An optical path of 11.4 m was achieved by placing the source on a lab wall and using a mirror to reflect it into the QUBIC-TD aperture.

Figure 8. Simulated beam pattern amplitude (left) and phase (right) from the source over the horn array of QUBIC when the calibrator source is placed 1 m (top) and 10 m (bottom) from the aperture, with the position and size of the horn array shown in black.

Figure 9. Simulated intensity of the interference pattern on the QUBIC focal plane when observing the calibration source at various distances from the instrument aperture. Clockwise from top-left: source at 1 m, source at 11.4 m, source at infinite distance, difference between the source at 11.4 m and at infinity. The colour bar gives the normalized intensity at each distance. The peak residual is 0.025.

4 Measurement results and analysis

4.1 Spectral response

The spectral response was measured using the calibration source (see section 3). The calibration source was modulated with a 1 Hz sine wave modulation and was stepped through frequencies across the band from 120 GHz to 180 GHz, taking 60 seconds of data at each frequency setting. The calibration source output power was measured independently by a zero-bias detector at the output of the amplitude multiplication chain, as described in section 3. Synchronized demodulation of the calibration source output and the bolometer response provides a high signal-to-noise measurement which also accounts for any spectral variation in the calibration source output power. Figure 10 shows the measured profile. The error bars are statistical and calculated from the uncertainty in the demodulation of the calibration source signal. The spectral response is flat to within 1.5 dB inside the range 136 GHz to 173 GHz, and drops by ~ 2.5 dB at the nominal band edge of 130 GHz.

The calibration source is designed to operate between 130 and 170 GHz (shown as the white region bordered by vertical dashed lines in figure 10). Its use below and above these limits was not characterized by the supplier, Virginia Diodes Incorporated (VDI) and it should not be used to make quantitative conclusions due to uncertainty in the tuning frequency and in the level of the output power outside the designed spectral range. Nevertheless, we operated the calibration source outside its nominal range, to obtain a qualitative behaviour of the spectral response of the instrument below and above the desired frequency range. We also placed a layer of Eccosorb material AN72 at the mouth of the calibration source corrugated feedhorn in order to attenuate the high power output of the source. This provides 25 dB of attenuation with a spectrally flat profile ($\pm 1\%$ across the band), as measured by a vector network analyser at the laboratory of the University of Milan.

The QUBIC-TD optical path includes 13 multi-mesh blocking filters manufactured by QMC Instruments Ltd – Thomas Keating Instruments Ltd⁴. These are particularly important in the laboratory environment which has a background thermal loading at room temperature, in contrast to what will be the situation for the instrument when it is on the observing site and pointing at the sky with a background thermal loading on the order of 10 K. The 13 filters are distributed along the optical path inside the cryostat and are heat sunk to the different temperature stages between 300 K and 0.3 K. For more details on the optical design see O’Sullivan et al. [7] and for the cryogenic design, see Masi et al. [8]. In order to further attenuate the 300 K environment in the laboratory, the QUBIC-TD has a neutral density filter which is a thermally evaporated gold layer on a $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ mylar substrate. It was tested to give a 9% transmission at room temperature. The combined filter profile is shown as a brown-dashed curve in figure 10 and includes all the filters in the optical train as well as the horn waveguide cut-off profile. The back-to-back horn array has a waveguide “throat” section with a diameter that creates a low-frequency cut-off at 125 GHz. Details of the horn array are described in Cavaliere et al. [15].

The measured spectral profile differs from the expected profile at the band edges with additional suppression at the low frequency end, and additional transmission at the high frequency end. The difference is ~ 2.5 dB excess suppression at 130 GHz and ~ 4.5 dB at 173 GHz. The differences will be investigated in future measurements, however, this does not have a significant effect on the overall performance of the QUBIC-TD. In particular, the

⁴<http://www.terahertz.co.uk/>.

Figure 10. Bandpass of the QUBIC-TD. This was measured by stepping through the frequencies of the calibration source and measuring the relative power on the TES at each frequency. The expected profile from the combined effect of filters and the horn array is shown as the brown-dashed curve. Note that the calibration source performance is uncertain outside the band 130 GHz to 170 GHz (area shown in grey, and see main text).

measured bandpass falls well within the atmospheric window between the 119 GHz oxygen line and the 183 GHz water line.

4.2 Half wave plate polarization rotation test

A functionality test of the HWP rotator mechanism was carried out while, at the same time, the calibration source was operating. The calibration source, composed of a rectangular waveguide and a corrugated horn, is linear polarized with cross-polarization less than -30 dB, as quoted by the supplier of the corrugated horn, Custom Microwaves Inc.⁵ Measurements were taken at each of the 7 evenly spaced positions of the HWP from 0° to 90° (spacing of 15°). Figure 11 shows the signal for a TES near the centre of the focal plane at different HWP orientations (shown in different colours). The peak-to-peak amplitude clearly shows repeatable variations with HWP position. The HWP orientation in position #3 rotates the calibration source polarization such that it is orthogonal to the polarizing grid (see figure 1 and section 2). Figure 12 shows a subset of 4 seconds of the calibration source signal measured by a TES near the centre of the focal plane with the HWP in position #1 and in position #3. There are 180 seconds of data at each of the 7 HWP positions, giving high signal-to-noise and the small error bars seen in figure 13.

The amplitude at each position is plotted and fitted to a sine curve, with the amplitude normalized, as shown in figure 13. The signal in each case is measured by the RMS of the TES data while the source was modulated. The measurement is the source modulation amplitude together with the RMS of the noise, quadratically added. As a result the minimum value is dominated by noise. The maximum signal occurs when the HWP is between position 6 and 7. This measurement represents a direct measurement of the cross-polarization response of the QUBIC-TD. The cross-polarization contamination at 150 GHz for the TES near the centre of the focal plane is compatible with zero to within 0.4% at 95% confidence level. We

⁵<https://custommicrowave.com/>.

Figure 11. Peak-to-peak amplitude of the detected calibration source for different HWP positions as measured with a TES near the centre of the focal plane. The 7 positions are spaced by 15° in order to span 90° between position 1 and position 7.

Figure 12. Close-up view of the peak-to-peak amplitude of the detected calibration source for the HWP in position #1 (top) and position #3 (bottom) as measured with a TES near the centre of the focal plane. The black curve is the power of the calibration source as measured by the power monitor (see section 3). It is plotted over the measured response of the bolometer (top, red curve for position #1 and bottom, green curve for position #3). The HWP in position #3 rotates the incoming calibration source polarization such that it is orthogonal to the polarizing grid. This is seen in the low level of modulation in the signal.

Figure 13. Amplitude of the detected calibration source at 150 GHz as measured with a TES near the centre of the focal plane for the HWP in the different positions and fitted to a sine curve.

use the definition of cross-polarization described by eq. 1 of Ludwig [18]. The full analysis for all working detectors in the focal plane gives a median value of 0.61% at 95% confidence level [13].

The calibration source can be modulated with a choice of modulation frequency, amplitude, and total power output (see section 2). The power offset and amplitude can lead to saturation of the TES detectors, as shown in figure 14. The detector in this case is saturated at HWP positions which rotate the calibration source polarization closer to co-aligned with the polarizing grid. The amplitude plotted in figure 14 is the normalized amplitude such that the HWP rotation curve fits a sine curve with peak-to-peak amplitude of 1. A sine curve fitting the lower part of the curve but not the upper part of the curve is an indication of saturation. Figure 14 is used to determine optimal calibration source settings so that the detector is not saturated at any HWP position. Saturation is calculated using the saturation parameter as described in D’Alessandro et al. [13] (eq. 9.2). For the TES in figure 13 the saturation level is less than 0.23%.

As polarization is selected before the horn array (see section 2), the cross-polarization leakage is independent of the location in the focal plane. Therefore, the cross-polarization leakage is expected to be the same for all TES. The example shown in figures 13 and 14

Figure 14. Same as figure 13 but with the calibration source set at various power output levels. The effect of saturation is evident for the source at high power. The HWP angle of maximum signal damping is consistent between all the measurements.

are for a TES near the centre of the focal plane which has the best signal-to-noise for this measurement due to the pointing.

The cross-polarization contamination was measured with the calibration source tuned to 150 GHz. This is therefore a measurement at a single, essentially monochromatic frequency. Future test campaigns will measure the cross-polarization contamination at frequencies across the band in order to determine the integrated response of the system for the full bandpass.

4.3 Self-calibration and the measurement of fringes

Self-calibration is a technique developed for aperture synthesis in radio interferometry. This technique evolved from the original idea in the 1970’s of “phase-closure” [19–21] to become in the early 1980’s “self-calibration” [22, 23]. See Cornwell & Fomalont [24] for a detailed overview. Precise knowledge of the calibration source is not required, as long as it is a strong and stable point source. The large number of baseline visibilities allows us to solve for many unknowns, including the gain and phase corrections of each detector, without requiring knowledge of the source amplitude.

In order to advance towards the full analysis of self-calibration, a key component is the ability to measure fringes with QUBIC. If fringes can be measured with a horn pair, then the full analysis can be done once the fringe measurement is done for all horn pairs. By measuring the fringe pattern of a single pair of horns we demonstrate the feasibility of doing self-calibration with the bolometric interferometer.

The QUBIC-TD successfully measured fringes between a pair of horns (figure 15 left). The measured fringe pattern in figure 15 (left) is the interference pattern of one baseline which corresponds to a set of two horns. It is the derived image after analysing measurements of images with all horns open, with two horns closed, with one horn closed, and with the other horn closed. This measurement takes approximately 30 minutes, cycling through the switch

configurations (horn ‘a’ open, horn ‘b’ open; horn ‘a’ closed, horn ‘b’ open; horn ‘a’ closed, horn ‘b’ closed; horn ‘a’ open, horn ‘b’ closed). Each configuration is measured for 20 seconds, and the timeline is co-added (folded by the cycle period). The result is the equivalent of having all horns closed except the two of interest, as was shown in Bigot-Sazy et al. [10]. It is necessary to make the measurement in this way because of the limitation required on heat dissipation. Only a maximum of two switches can be activated (closed) at a time, as described in section 2 (and see Cavaliere et al. [15] for full details). As a result, it is not possible to close all horn switches except for the two of interest. However, using the analysis steps described above, figure 15 (left) is the result of interference between a single pair of horns.

The fringes are expected to be fainter in proportion to the distance to the centre of the focal plane (figure 15 right). This is not the case here because of saturation of the TES detectors. As a result, the fringe amplitude appears to be relatively constant, or near zero where saturated detectors were subtracted from one another. The problem with saturation is mainly related to the high power of the calibration source. The calibration source can be attenuated by its bias voltage, which is used for signal modulation (see, for example, figure 14 in section 4.2). It can also be attenuated by moving the HWP, as seen in figure 13 of section 4.2. Future tests will explore methods to attenuate the calibration source while still having enough signal-to-noise to measure the secondary lobes of the synthesized beam.

It is worth noting that the difficulty with saturation of TES is more problematic for the analysis of fringes than for the analysis of the HWP presented in section 4.2. This is because the HWP measurements were done with a single TES at a time. This allows us to test the HWP performance with optimal settings on a given TES, and thus separate the HWP performance from the TES performance. The fringe measurement requires constructing an image on the focal plane, and this necessitates the use of multiple TES. The TES manufacturing is not perfectly homogenous (see Piat et al. [9] for details) and the optimum bias settings vary somewhat from TES to TES. The electronics supplying the bias settings for the TES can only supply the same bias to all 128 TES configured by each ASIC. As a result, some of the TES are not optimally biased, and saturation could be a problem for some while not for others. A solution to the problem is to make a sky map of the fringes, in the same way we made the map of the synthesized beam. In order to do this, a map must be made for each horn-switch configuration (single horns open/closed and pairs open/closed). This will be time consuming, but it is done with the artificial calibration source, and so can be done during times when QUBIC is not measuring the sky. Eventually, we will build a data base of maps with all the horn configurations.

4.4 Synthesized full beam reconstruction

The QUBIC-TD synthesized beam maps were measured at five frequencies in the range 130 GHz to 170 GHz by tuning the VDI calibration source (see section 3) in steps of 10 GHz from 130 GHz. For each frequency measurement the calibration source was modulated at a period of 1 second with a sinusoidal profile, and the TES signal was demodulated in post processing. QUBIC-TD was configured to point at an elevation angle of 35° and to scan across azimuth at a constant rate from -25° to $+25^\circ$. The elevation angle was then increased by 0.2° and a new azimuth scan at constant rate was done in the reverse direction from $+25^\circ$ to -25° . Each azimuth scan takes nearly 8 minutes, and an entire beam map at a given frequency is completed in 22 hours and 30 minutes. This matches well with the cryogenic hold time of the cryostat. The entire beam map measurement was preprogrammed in a script executed by the QUBIC instrument control software `QubicStudio`.

Figure 15. Fringes on the QUBIC TES array. *Left:* measured fringes corresponding to the baseline between horns 25 and 57. The fringes are clearly visible as bright, diagonal lines across the detector array. *Right:* simulation of the expected fringe pattern for the same baseline pair generated by `qubicsoft`. The measured fringe locations correspond with the simulated image. The amplitude of the fringe lines are expected to become fainter with distance from the centre of the focal plane. This was not measured because of saturation of the detectors. Pixel intensities are the same arbitrary units scaled to the peak of the measurement for both images.

Figure 16. Measured maps of the synthesized beam for one TES detector. The multi-lobe synthesized beam is shown here for 130 GHz, 140 GHz, 150 GHz, 160 GHz, and 170 GHz. An animated version of this plot with comparison to simulation can be viewed online at <https://box.in2p3.fr/index.php/s/bzPYfmtjQW4wCGj>.

The result of the beam mapping measurement campaign is a series of maps for each TES pixel in the detector array. This is 244 maps for each frequency for a total of 1220 maps. Figure 16 shows example maps for one TES detector at five frequencies. The main lobe and secondary lobes are clearly visible and are at the expected locations. Figure 17 shows the maps of figure 16 in a single representation with three frequencies, 130 GHz, 150 GHz, and 170 GHz, assigned to colours red, green, blue.

The secondary lobe locations depend on the frequency of the incident radiation while the main lobe is always at the same place. Figure 17 shows a cut across the beam maps of figure 16. The secondary lobes are closer to centre for higher frequencies, as expected. This result is the first hardware demonstration of the capability of a bolometric interferometer to operate as a spectral imager (see Mousset et al. [11] for a detailed analysis).

4.5 Map making with measured synthesized beams

Using the relative location and amplitude of all the peaks in the synthesized beam for each of the TES, we can now project the data onto the sky using optimal map-making to deconvolve from the effect of the multiple peaks. In addition, by exploiting the spatial separation of secondary peaks and the dependence of their location on the frequency of radiation, the

Figure 17. Multichroic representation of the maps of figure 16. Each frequency is assigned a colour, 130 GHz (red), 150 GHz (green), and 170 GHz (blue). The plot above shows the coincident central lobe for each frequency and the secondary lobes which are closer to centre as frequency increases. The plot below is the cross-cut along the diagonal from bottom-left to top-right of the image on the left. The peak at 170 GHz is truncated because of detector saturation.

analysis of the TOD leads to spectral imaging as described in detail in Mousset et al. [11]. Spectral discrimination is necessary to disentangle foreground contamination. When observing the sky, this will result in an unbiased CMB map as is shown using simulations in Mousset et al. [11].

We have performed this exercise with the calibration data in order to obtain an image of the point-like artificial calibration source projected onto a sky-map. The calibration source was set to emit at 150 GHz and using the alt-azimuth mount, QUBIC-TD was scanned across the source in azimuth and elevation. TOD are obtained for each bolometer. We then apply our spectral imaging map-making algorithm with five sub-bands to a selection of 26 bolometers that do not exhibit saturation. The synthesized beam for each bolometer is realistically modeled in our map-making through a series of Gaussian profiles whose amplitudes, widths and locations are fit from a measured map of the synthesized beam for each bolometer (see figure 16 for an example of the maps from one bolometer). The frequency evolution of this

Figure 18. Calibration data with the source at 150 GHz projected on the sky using our map-making software to deconvolve from the multiple peaked synthesized beam and separate the physical band of the instrument into 5 sub-bands. The spectrum of the central pixel, in arbitrary flux units, is shown at bottom and matches the expected performance of spectral imaging by analysis of the TOD and applying the frequency dependence of the QUBIC beam as described in Mousset et al. [11].

synthesized beam assumes linear scaling with wavelength. We were able to reconstruct a map of the point-like artificial calibration source as well as its location in frequency space. The resulting image is shown in figure 18. The reconstruction onto 5 sub-bands exhibits the expected point-like shape in the central frequency sub-band containing the emission frequency of the source at 150 GHz. The calibration source, which was tuned to 150 GHz, is fainter in adjacent bands, and not visible in the furthest bands. Our measurement matches the spectral resolution predicted by the Rayleigh criterion (see Mousset et al. [11], section 3.2 equation 3.1) shown as the blue line in figure 18 (bottom).

The successful mapmaking with the measured synthesized beam is effectively an end-to-end checkout of the entire QUBIC system. In order for this exercise to be possible, all subsystems, interfaces between subsystems, and all associated software must be functioning correctly. This includes scientific and housekeeping data acquisition, telescope pointing control, and control and synchronisation of all subsystems. The software needed to make this measurement includes the system control software, the data acquisition software, data archiving and reading, and finally data analysis software together with comparison to system simulation software. The resulting map of figure 18 shows that all subsystems are functioning correctly, and all subsystems are correctly managed and synchronized together into the overall system.

5 Conclusion

QUBIC-TD underwent an extensive campaign of testing in the laboratory at APC in Paris. Using an artificial millimetre-wave source in the telescope far-field, functional tests were carried out and several performance parameters were successfully measured. Our measurement

of the frequency-dependence of the synthesized beam is in excellent agreement with the theoretical prediction. This result, for the first time, opens up the possibility to use bolometric interferometry to perform spectral imaging. Based on these results, which were carried out on a single calibrating point source, preliminary simulations of QUBIC spectral imaging in presence of more realistic diffuse signals are very encouraging (Mousset et al. [11]). The spectral response has the required bandpass profile for operation in the 130 GHz to 170 GHz band. The polarization performance has less than 0.4% cross-polarization contamination at 150 GHz. These measurements confirm that bolometric interferometry is a viable method for the measure of CMB B-mode polarization. In particular, the measured polarization performance makes us confident that QUBIC will be one of the most competitive experiments in terms of polarization purity.

Deployment of QUBIC-TD on the scientific site of Alto Chorillo at 5000 m altitude in Argentina is expected by the end of 2022 for in-situ commissioning and preliminary data taking, as a precursor of the QUBIC full instrument. QUBIC will provide a clean polarization map of the sky and together with spectral imaging, will have excellent separation of foreground sources.

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References

- [1] M. Kamionkowski and E.D. Kovetz, *The Quest for B Modes from Inflationary Gravitational Waves*, *Ann. Rev. Astron. Astrophys.* **54** (2016) 227 [[arXiv:1510.06042](#)] [[INSPIRE](#)].
- [2] J. Kovac, E.M. Leitch, C. Pryke, J.E. Carlstrom, N.W. Halverson and W.L. Holzapfel, *Detection of polarization in the cosmic microwave background using DASI*, *Nature* **420** (2002) 772 [[astro-ph/0209478](#)] [[INSPIRE](#)].
- [3] SPT-3G collaboration, *Measurements of the E-mode polarization and temperature-E-mode correlation of the CMB from SPT-3G 2018 data*, *Phys. Rev. D* **104** (2021) 022003 [[arXiv:2101.01684](#)] [[INSPIRE](#)].
- [4] J. Alves, T. Forveille, L. Pentericci and S. Shore, *Planck 2018 results*, *Astron. Astrophys.* **641** (2020) E1.
- [5] BICEP and KECK collaborations, *Improved Constraints on Primordial Gravitational Waves using Planck, WMAP, and BICEP/Keck Observations through the 2018 Observing Season*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127** (2021) 151301 [[arXiv:2110.00483](#)] [[INSPIRE](#)].

- [6] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC Technical Design Report*, [arXiv:1609.04372](#) [INSPIRE].
- [7] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC VIII: Optical design and performance*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 041 [[arXiv:2008.10119](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [8] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC V: Cryogenic system design and performance*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 038 [[arXiv:2008.10659](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [9] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC IV: Performance of TES bolometers and readout electronics*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 037 [[arXiv:2101.06787](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [10] M.A. Bigot-Sazy, R. Charlassier, J.C. Hamilton, J. Kaplan and G. Zahariade, *Self-calibration: an efficient method to control systematic effects in bolometric interferometry*, *Astron. Astrophys.* **550** (2013) A59 [[arXiv:1209.4905](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [11] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC II: Spectro-polarimetry with bolometric interferometry*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 035 [[arXiv:2010.15119](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [12] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC I: Overview and science program*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 034 [[arXiv:2011.02213](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [13] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC VI: cryogenic half wave plate rotator, design and performances*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 039 [[arXiv:2008.10667](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [14] G. Pisano, M. Ng, V. Haynes and B. Maffei, *A broadband metal-mesh half-wave plate for millimetre wave linear polarisation rotation*, *PIER M* **25** (2012).
- [15] QUBIC collaboration, *QUBIC VII: The feedhorn-switch system of the technological demonstrator*, *JCAP* **04** (2022) 040 [[arXiv:2008.12721](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [16] A. Schillaci, E. Battistelli, G. D’Alessandro, P. de Bernardis and S. Masi, *On the emissivity of wire-grid polarizers for astronomical observations at mm-wavelengths*, *Infrared Phys. Tech.* **58** (2013) 64 [[arXiv:1212.3969](#)] [INSPIRE].
- [17] D. Burke, *Design and Analysis of the Optical Beam Combiner and Corrugated Feed Horns for the QUBIC Instrument*, *Maynooth Theses* (2021).
- [18] A.C. Ludwig, *The definition of cross polarization*, *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propagat.* **21** (1973) 116.
- [19] J.A. Hogbom, *Aperture Synthesis with a Non-Regular Distribution of Interferometer Baselines*, *Astron. Astrophys. Suppl. Ser.* **15** (1974) 417 [INSPIRE].
- [20] D.N. Fort and H.K.C. Yee, *A Method of Obtaining Brightness Distributions from Long Baseline Interferometry*, *Astron. Astrophys.* **50** (1976) 19.
- [21] A.C.S. Readhead and P.N. Wilkinson, *The mapping of compact radio sources from VLBI data*, *Astrophys. J.* **223** (1978) 25.
- [22] T.J. Cornwell and P.N. Wilkinson, *A new method for making maps with unstable radio interferometers*, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **196** (1981) 1067.
- [23] T.J. Pearson and A.C.S. Readhead, *Image formation by self-calibration in radio astronomy*, *Ann. Rev. Astron. Astrophys.* **22** (1984) 97 [INSPIRE].
- [24] T. Cornwell and E.B. Fomalont, *Self-Calibration*, in *Synthesis Imaging in Radio Astronomy II*, G.B. Taylor, C.L. Carilli and R.A. Perley, eds., *ASP Conf. Ser.* **180** (1999) 187.

6 Références

Références avec S.A. Torchinsky comme auteur ou co-auteur

- F. Acero, J. T. Acquaviva, and 176 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** French SKA White Book - The French Community towards the Square Kilometre Array. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1712.06950, December 2017.
- R. Ansari, J. E. Campagne, and 15 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Design, operation and performance of the PAON4 prototype transit interferometer. *MNRAS*, 493(2):2965–2980, April 2020. doi: 10.1093/mnras/staa345.
- E. S. Battistelli, P. Ade, and 137 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC: The Q & U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology. *Journal of Low Temperature Physics*, 199(1-2):482–490, February 2020. doi: 10.1007/s10909-020-02370-0.
- V. Yu. Belitsky and **S.A. Torchinsky**. *A Design for the HET Receiver on FIRST*, March 1996. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3726756>. Proposal submitted 6 March 1996 for the optics design of the Heterodyne Instrument (later named HIFI) for the Far Infrared Space Telescope (later renamed Herschel).
- J. G. bij de Vaate, P. Benthem, R. Witvers, R. van den Brink, Y. Zhang, and **S.A. Torchinsky**. Mid frequency aperture array technology developments for the SKA. In *2014 16th International Symposium on Antenna Technology and Applied Electromagnetics (ANTEM)*, pages 1–2, 2014.
- R. Bolton, G. Harris, and 15 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** SKADS Benchmark Scenario Design and Costing - 2. Technical report, SKA Organisation, 2008. URL https://www.skatelescope.org/uploaded/10006_111_Memo_Bolton.pdf.
- S. Bosse, M. L. Grima, and 19 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** R&D at Nançay for radio astronomy detectors and systems. In P. Kern, editor, *EAS Publications Series*, volume 37 of *EAS Publications Series*, pages 127–134, January 2009. doi: 10.1051/eas/0937015.
- S. Bosse, S. Barth, **S. Torchinsky**, and B. Da Silva. Beamformer asic in uhf-l band for the square kilometer array international project. In *The 5th European Microwave Integrated Circuits Conference*, pages 106–109, 2010.
- D. Burke, D. Gayer, and 132 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Optical modelling and analysis of the Q and U bolometric interferometer for cosmology. In *Terahertz, RF, Millimeter, and Submillimeter-Wave Technology and Applications XI*, volume 10531 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 105310G, February 2018. doi: 10.1117/12.2287158.

- F. Cavaliere, A. Mennella, and 129 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC VII: The feedhorn-switch system of the technological demonstrator. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):040, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/040.
- G. D'Alessandro, L. Mele, and 127 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC VI: Cryogenic half wave plate rotator, design and performance. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):039, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/039.
- Santanu Das, Christopher J. Anderson, and 45 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Progress in the construction and testing of the Tianlai radio interferometers. In Jonas Zmuidzinas and Jian-Rong Gao, editors, *Millimeter, Submillimeter, and Far-Infrared Detectors and Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*, volume 10708 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 1070836, July 2018. doi: 10.1117/12.2313031.
- P. de Bernardis, P. Ade, and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC: Measuring CMB polarization from Argentina. *Boletín de la Asociación Argentina de Astronomía La Plata Argentina*, 60:107–114, August 2018.
- Thijs de Graauw, Nick D. Whyborn, and 39 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Heterodyne instrument for FIRST (HIFI): preliminary design. In Thomas G. Phillips, editor, *Advanced Technology MMW, Radio, and Terahertz Telescopes*, volume 3357 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, pages 336–347, July 1998. doi: 10.1117/12.317368.
- A.J. Faulkner, P. Alexander, and 4 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Design of an Aperture Phased Array System for the SKA. In *Proc. URSI XXIX General Assembly, Chicago, August 2008*, August 2008. URL <http://www.ursi.org/proceedings/procGA08/papers/J02p9.pdf>.
- Andrew Faulkner, Dion Kant, and 12 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** The Aperture Arrays for the SKA: the SKADS White Paper. Technical report, SKA Organisation, April 2010. URL https://www.skatelescope.org/uploaded/5367_122_Memo_Faulkner.pdf.
- U. Frisk, M. Hagström, and 49 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** The Odin satellite. I. Radiometer design and test. *A&A*, 402:L27–L34, May 2003. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20030335.
- J. Ch. Hamilton, L. Mousset, and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC I: Overview and science program. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):034, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/034.
- A. Hjalmarson, U. Frisk, and 56 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Highlights from the first year of Odin observations. *A&A*, 402:L39–L46, May 2003. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20030337.

- E. S. Howell, A. J. Lovell, B. Butler, F. P. Schloerb, and **S. A. Torchinsky**. Radio OH Observations of Comet 9P/Tempel 1 before and after Deep Impact. In *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, volume 207 of *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, page 187.04, December 2005.
- S. Kwok, P. Bernath, and 6 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** The First Astronomical Spectrum of Orion KL between 555-573 GHz. In *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, volume 205 of *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*, page 105.14, December 2004.
- B. Larsson, R. Liseau, and 56 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Molecular oxygen in the ρ Ophiuchi cloud. *A&A*, 466(3):999–1003, May 2007. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20065500.
- A. Lecacheux, N. Biver, and 20 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Observations of water in comets with Odin. *A&A*, 402:L55–L58, May 2003. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20030338.
- S. Marnieros, P. Ade, and 125 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** TES Bolometer Arrays for the QUBIC B-Mode CMB Experiment. *Journal of Low Temperature Physics*, 199(3-4):955–961, January 2020. doi: 10.1007/s10909-019-02304-5.
- S. Masi, E. S. Battistelli, and 127 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC V: Cryogenic system design and performance. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):038, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/038.
- A. J. May, C. Chapron, and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Thermal architecture for the QUBIC cryogenic receiver. In Jonas Zmuidzinas and Jian-Rong Gao, editors, *Millimeter, Submillimeter, and Far-Infrared Detectors and Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*, volume 10708 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 107083V, July 2018. doi: 10.1117/12.2312085.
- A. Mennella, P. A. R. Ade, and 106 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC: the Q&U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology. A novel way to look at the polarized Cosmic Microwave Background. In *Proceedings of the European Physical Society Conference on High Energy Physics. 5-12 July*, page 44, July 2017.
- Aniello Mennella, Peter Ade, and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC: Exploring the Primordial Universe with the Q&U Bolometric Interferometer. *Universe*, 5(2):42, January 2019. doi: 10.3390/universe5020042.
- L. Mousset, M. M. Gamboa Lerena, and 129 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC II: Spectral polarimetry with bolometric interferometry. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):035, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/035.

- M. Olberg, U. Frisk, and 14 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** The Odin satellite. II. Radiometer data processing and calibration. *A&A*, 402:L35–L38, May 2003. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361:20030336.
- A. O. Henrik Olofsson, Laure Bouscasse, and **Stephen A. Torchinsky**. Observation of the $2_{1,1}$ - $2_{1,2}$ Transition of Methanol at 2502.8 MHz in Sgr B2. *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 1(1):46, December 2017. doi: 10.3847/2515-5172/aaa089.
- H. A. O. Olofsson, **S.A. Torchinsky**, and 14 co-authors. Profiling the EMBRACE tile beam using GPS satellite carriers. In *Wide Field Astronomy & Technology for the Square Kilometre Array*, page 42, January 2009.
- C. O’Sullivan, P. Ade, and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC: the Q and U bolometric interferometer for cosmology. In Jonas Zmuidzinas and Jian-Rong Gao, editors, *Millimeter, Submillimeter, and Far-Infrared Detectors and Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*, volume 10708 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 107082B, July 2018a. doi: 10.1117/12.2313332.
- C. O’Sullivan, D. Burke, and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Simulations and performance of the QUBIC optical beam combiner. In Jonas Zmuidzinas and Jian-Rong Gao, editors, *Millimeter, Submillimeter, and Far-Infrared Detectors and Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*, volume 10708 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 107082I, July 2018b. doi: 10.1117/12.2313256.
- C. O’Sullivan, M. De Petris, and 127 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC VIII: Optical design and performance. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):041, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/041.
- M. Piat, B. Bélier, and 136 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC: using NbSi TESs with a bolometric interferometer to characterize the polarisation of the CMB. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1911.12418, November 2019.
- M. Piat, G. Stankowiak, and 127 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** QUBIC IV: Performance of TES bolometers and readout electronics. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):037, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/037.
- M. Salatino, B. Bélier, and 130 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Performance of NbSi transition-edge sensors readout with a 128 MUX factor for the QUBIC experiment. In Jonas Zmuidzinas and Jian-Rong Gao, editors, *Millimeter, Submillimeter, and Far-Infrared Detectors and Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*, volume 10708 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 1070845, July 2018. doi: 10.1117/12.2312080.

- C. Taffoureau, P. Renaud, and 5 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Monitoring and Control of EMBRACE: A 4608 Element Phased Array for Radio Astronomy. In P. Ballester, D. Egret, and N. P. F. Lorente, editors, *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XXI*, volume 461 of *Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series*, page 209, September 2012.
- S.A. Torchinsky.** Analysis of a conical horn fed by a slightly oversized waveguide. *International Journal of Infrared and Millimeter Waves*, 11(7):791–808, July 1990. doi: 10.1007/BF01010133.
- S.A. Torchinsky.** 3d-Quasi-Optical Ray-Tracing for the Odin Radiometer. In *Odin Technical Report*. Zenodo, February 2000. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3725933. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3725933>.
- S.A. Torchinsky.** The Questions that Drive the Specifications. In *Wide Field Astronomy & Technology for the Square Kilometre Array*, page 4, January 2009.
- S.A. Torchinsky.** Highlights of Radioastronomy from 1800 to 2007 (a personal selection). *Ecole de Goutelas*, 30:15–22, April 2011.
- S.A. Torchinsky** and V. Yu. Belitsky. Optical Architecture for the Het on First. In A. Wilson, editor, *The Far Infrared and Submillimetre Universe.*, volume 401 of *ESA Special Publication*, page 449, August 1997.
- S.A. Torchinsky** and SKADS Consortium. Probing Dark Energy with the Square Kilometre Array. In *Proc. 19th Rencontres de Blois*, May 2007. URL http://satorchi.net/skads/blois_dark-energy-with-SKA_Torchinsky20070524.pdf.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, C. T. Cunningham, and S. R. Davies. *A 690 GHZ SIS Mixer*, volume 187, page 723. Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1994. doi: 10.1007/978-94-011-0794-5_125.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, A.O.H. Olofsson, and 15 co-authors. EMBRACE System Engineering and Astronomical Test Plan SKADS: DS5T3. Technical report, June 2008. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3727697>.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, A. van Ardenne, T. van den Brink, A.J.J. van Es, and A.J. Faulkner, editors. *Wide Field Science & Technology for the Square Kilometre Array*, November 2009. ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4. URL <https://pos.sissa.it/132/>.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, A. O. H. Olofsson, and 5 co-authors. Characterization and Initial Results with EMBRACE. In L. Cambresy, F. Martins, E. Nuss, and A. Palacios, editors, *SF2A-2013: Proceedings of the Annual meeting of the French Society of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, pages 439–444, November 2013.

- S.A. Torchinsky**, A. O. H. Olofsson, and 5 co-authors. EMBRACE@Nançay: an ultra wide field of view prototype for the SKA. *Journal of Instrumentation*, 10(7):C07002, July 2015. doi: 10.1088/1748-0221/10/07/C07002.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, J. W. Broderick, A. Gunst, A. J. Faulkner, and W. van Cappellen. SKA Aperture Array Mid Frequency Science Requirements. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1610.00683, October 2016a.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, A. O. H. Olofsson, and 6 co-authors. Characterization of a dense aperture array for radio astronomy. *A&A*, 589:A77, May 2016b. doi: 10.1051/0004-6361/201526706.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, J.-Ch. Hamilton, and 127 co-authors. QUBIC Technical Demonstrator Calibration Report. Technical report, January 2020. URL <https://tinyurl.com/QUBICcaldoc>.
- S.A. Torchinsky**, J. Ch. Hamilton, and 126 co-authors. QUBIC III: Laboratory characterization. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2022(4):036, April 2022. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2022/04/036.
- Stephen A. Torchinsky**. *Gravitational Lenses & Conical Feedhorns*. PhD thesis, University of Edinburgh, November 1991.
- Steve Torchinsky**. Saint Augustin et le Big Bang. In *Bulletine Interne de l'Observatoire de Paris*, number 1856. Observatoire de Paris, September 2014. URL http://satorchi.net/media/Torchinsky_SaintAugustin-et-le-Big-Bang.pdf.
- Steve Torchinsky**. Un histoire d'hydrogène neutre dans l'Univers. In *Histoire du Cosmos*. Université de Paris, February 2020. URL <https://box.in2p3.fr/index.php/s/WCtKZwAPcTXkd7y>.
- Steve Torchinsky**. Un histoire d'hydrogène neutre dans l'Univers. In *Histoire du Cosmos*. Université de Paris, April 2021. URL <https://box.in2p3.fr/index.php/s/z7QRb7GmryXX95K>.
- Steve Torchinsky** and Wim van Driel. Révéler l'invisible par les ondes radio. In *Dossier pour la Science : Galaxies Fenêtres sur l'Univers*, number 56. Pour la science, July 2007. URL <https://www.pourlascience.fr/sd/astrophysique/dossier-pour-la-science-56-272.php>.
- Steve Torchinsky**, Charles Cunningham, and Steve Davies. Dixie D-Mixer. *The JCMT/UKIRT Newsletter*, July 1993. URL <https://www.eaobservatory.org/JCMT/publications/newsletter/jcmt-n1.pdf>.

- Steve Torchinsky**, Isabelle Ristorcelli, and 9 co-authors. *Odin Telescope Beam Measurements at CESR-Toulouse 2000 September*, November 2000. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3726677>.
- Steve Torchinsky**, Kevin Volk, and Sun Kwok. The Odin Satellite. In *Proceedings of the Canadian Astronomical Society (CASCA), Penticton, B.C, 2002 May 11-14*, Canadian Astronomical Society Meeting Proceedings, 2002. URL http://satorchi.net/Odin/Torchinsky_casca2002poster.pdf.
- W. A. van Cappellen, M. Santos, and 15 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** MANTIS: The Mid-Frequency Aperture Array Transient and Intensity-Mapping System. *arXiv e-prints*, art. arXiv:1612.07917, December 2016.
- N. D. Whyborn, Th. de Graauw, and 6 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** The Focal Plane Unit of the Heterodyne Instrument for FIRST: HIFI. In Rob McGrath, editor, *Ninth International Symposium on Space Terahertz Technology*, pages 453–462, March 1998.
- S. J. Wijnholds, G. W. Kant, and 7 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** EMBRACE: First experimental Results with the Initial 10% of a 10,000 Element Phased Array Radio Telescope. In *Wide Field Astronomy & Technology for the Square Kilometre Array*, page 43, January 2009.
- Wolfgang Wild, John M. Payne, and 12 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** Receivers for ALMA: preliminary design concepts. In Harvey R. Butcher, editor, *Radio Telescopes*, volume 4015 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, pages 320–327, July 2000. doi: 10.1117/12.390465.

Autres références

- Constantine A. Balanis. *Advanced Engineering Electromagnetics*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012. ISBN ISBN 978-0-470-58948-9.
- Chris Blake and Karl Glazebrook. Probing Dark Energy Using Baryonic Oscillations in the Galaxy Power Spectrum as a Cosmological Ruler. *ApJ*, 594(2):665–673, September 2003. doi: 10.1086/376983.
- J. M. Cordes, P. C. C. Freire, and 22 co authors. Arecibo Pulsar Survey Using ALFA. I. Survey Strategy and First Discoveries. *ApJ*, 637(1):446–455, January 2006. doi: 10.1086/498335.
- P. de Bernardis, M. Calvo, C. Giordano, S. Masi, F. Nati, F. Piacentini, and A. Schillaci. Science with Future Cosmic Microwave Background Observations. *Nuclear Physics B*

- Proceedings Supplements*, 194:350–356, October 2009. doi: 10.1016/j.nuclphysbps.2009.07.097.
- J. S. Deneva, J. M. Cordes, and 24 co authors. Arecibo Pulsar Survey Using ALFA: Probing Radio Pulsar Intermittency And Transients. *ApJ*, 703(2):2259–2274, October 2009. doi: 10.1088/0004-637X/703/2/2259.
- Albert Einstein. Zur allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie. *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Berlin)*, pages 778–786, January 1915.
- Daniel J. Eisenstein and Wayne Hu. Baryonic Features in the Matter Transfer Function. *ApJ*, 496(2):605–614, March 1998. doi: 10.1086/305424.
- H. Fizeau. Sur les hypothèses relatives à l'éther lumineux et sur une expérience qui paraît démontrer que le mouvement des corps change la vitesse avec laquelle la lumière se propage dans leur intérieur. *Compte Rendu des Séances de l'Académie des Sciences*, pages 349–355, September 1851. URL <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k29901/f351.image>.
- A. Friedmann. Über die Krümmung des Raumes. *Zeitschrift für Physik*, 10:377–386, January 1922. doi: 10.1007/BF01332580.
- G. Gamow. Expanding Universe and the Origin of Elements. *Physical Review*, 70(7-8): 572–573, October 1946. doi: 10.1103/PhysRev.70.572.2.
- Héctor Gil-Marín, Julián E. Bautista, Romain Paviot, Mariana Vargas-Magaña, Sylvain de la Torre, Sebastien Fromenteau, Shadab Alam, Santiago Ávila, Etienne Burtin, Chia-Hsun Chuang, Kyle S. Dawson, Jiamin Hou, Arnaud de Mattia, Faizan G. Mohammad, Eva-Maria Müller, Seshadri Nadathur, Richard Neveux, Will J. Percival, Anand Rai-choor, Mehdi Rezaie, Ashley J. Ross, Graziano Rossi, Vanina Ruhlmann-Kleider, Alex Smith, Amélie Tamone, Jeremy L. Tinker, Rita Tojeiro, Yuting Wang, Gong-Bo Zhao, Cheng Zhao, Jonathan Brinkmann, Joel R. Brownstein, Peter D. Choi, Stephanie Escoffier, Axel de la Macorra, Jeongin Moon, Jeffrey A. Newman, Donald P. Schneider, Hee-Jong Seo, and Mariappan Vivek. The Completed SDSS-IV extended Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey: measurement of the BAO and growth rate of structure of the luminous red galaxy sample from the anisotropic power spectrum between redshifts 0.6 and 1.0. *MNRAS*, 498(2):2492–2531, October 2020. doi: 10.1093/mnras/staa2455.
- Paul F. Goldsmith. *Quasioptical Systems*. 1998.
- Alan H. Guth. Inflationary universe: A possible solution to the horizon and flatness problems. *Phys. Rev. D*, 23(2):347–356, January 1981. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevD.23.347.
- Ellen S. Howell, Amy J. Lovell, Bryan Butler, and F. Peter Schloerb. Radio OH observations of 9P/Tempel 1 before and after Deep Impact. *Icarus*, 187(1):228–239, March 2007a. doi: 10.1016/j.icarus.2006.10.005.

- Ellen S. Howell, Amy J. Lovell, Bryan Butler, and F. Peter Schloerb. Radio OH observations of 9P/Tempel 1 before and after Deep Impact. *Icarus*, 191(2):469–480, January 2007b. doi: 10.1016/j.icarus.2006.10.041.
- Edwin Hubble. A Relation between Distance and Radial Velocity among Extra-Galactic Nebulae. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science*, 15(3):168–173, March 1929. doi: 10.1073/pnas.15.3.168.
- A. Kogut, D. J. Fixsen, D. T. Chuss, J. Dotson, E. Dwek, M. Halpern, G. F. Hinshaw, S. M. Meyer, S. H. Moseley, M. D. Seiffert, D. N. Spergel, and E. J. Wollack. The Primordial Inflation Explorer (PIXIE): a nulling polarimeter for cosmic microwave background observations. *J. Cosmo. Astroparticle Phys.*, 2011(7):025, July 2011. doi: 10.1088/1475-7516/2011/07/025.
- Akito Kusaka, Dale J. Fixsen, Alan J. Kogut, Stephan S. Meyer, Suzanne T. Staggs, and Thomas R. Stevenson. MuSE: a novel experiment for CMB polarization measurement using highly multimoded bolometers. In Wayne S. Holland and Jonas Zmuidzinas, editors, *Millimeter, Submillimeter, and Far-Infrared Detectors and Instrumentation for Astronomy VI*, volume 8452 of *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, page 84521L, September 2012. doi: 10.1117/12.926271.
- G. Lemaître. Un Univers homogène de masse constante et de rayon croissant rendant compte de la vitesse radiale des nébuleuses extra-galactiques. *Annales de la Société Scientifique de Bruxelles*, 47:49–59, January 1927.
- A. D. Linde. A new inflationary universe scenario: A possible solution of the horizon, flatness, homogeneity, isotropy and primordial monopole problems. *Physics Letters B*, 108(6):389–393, February 1982. doi: 10.1016/0370-2693(82)91219-9.
- D. R. Lorimer, I. H. Stairs, and 34 co authors. Arecibo Pulsar Survey Using ALFA. II. The Young, Highly Relativistic Binary Pulsar J1906+0746. *ApJ*, 640(1):428–434, March 2006. doi: 10.1086/499918.
- Nathan Marcuvitz. *Waveguide Handbook*. Institution of Electrical Engineers, GBR, 1986. ISBN 0863410588.
- V. F. Mukhanov and G. V. Chibisov. Quantum fluctuations and the “non-singular” universe. *Pisma v Zhurnal Eksperimentalnoi i Teoreticheskoi Fiziki*, 33:549–553, January 1981.
- Viatcheslav Mukhanov. Quantum cosmological perturbations: predictions and observations. *European Physical Journal C*, 73:2486, July 2013. doi: 10.1140/epjc/s10052-013-2486-7.

- J. A. Murphy, T. Peacocke, B. Maffei, I. McAuley, F. Noviello, V. Yurchenko, P. A. R. Ade, G. Savini, J. M. Lamarre, J. Brossard, R. Colgan, E. Gleeson, A. E. Lange, Y. Longval, G. Pisano, J. L. Puget, I. Ristorcelli, R. Sudiwala, and R. J. Wylde. Multi-mode horn design and beam characteristics for the Planck satellite. *Journal of Instrumentation*, 5(4):T04001, April 2010. doi: 10.1088/1748-0221/5/04/T04001.
- J. Anthony Murphy and Rachael Padman. Radiation patterns of few-moded horns and condensing lightpipes. *Infrared Physics*, 31(3):291–299, January 1991. doi: 10.1016/0020-0891(91)90060-S.
- J. Anthony Murphy, Ruth Colgan, Creidhe O’Sullivan, Bruno Maffei, and Peter Ade. Radiation patterns of multi-moded corrugated horns for far-IR space applications. *Infrared Physics and Technology*, 42(6):515–528, December 2001. doi: 10.1016/S1350-4495(01)00063-9.
- J. E. Noordam and J. Hamaker. An Ever more penetrating View. In *Westerbork Telescope 50th Anniversary*, volume 361, page 7, September 2018.
- A. A. Penzias and R. W. Wilson. A Measurement of Excess Antenna Temperature at 4080 Mc/s. *ApJ*, 142:419–421, July 1965. doi: 10.1086/148307.
- Uroš Seljak and Matias Zaldarriaga. Signature of Gravity Waves in the Polarization of the Microwave Background. *Phys. Rev. Letters*, 78(11):2054–2057, March 1997. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevLett.78.2054.
- V. M. Slipher. Radial velocity observations of spiral nebulae. *The Observatory*, 40:304–306, August 1917.
- A. A. Starobinskiĭ. Spectrum of relict gravitational radiation and the early state of the universe. *Soviet Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Physics Letters*, 30:682, December 1979.
- A. Richard Thompson, James M. Moran, and G. W. Swenson Jr. *Interferometry and Synthesis in Radio Astronomy, 3rd Edition*. 2017. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-44431-4.

7 Curriculum Vitæ

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Professional Affiliations

Member *Société Française d'astronomie et astrophysique (SF2A)*
Associate Member Free Software Foundation (FSF)

Professional Recognition

2002: The Onsala Medal of Recognition for work on the Odin satellite

Education

1991: Ph.D. Astronomy, University of Edinburgh
thesis title: Gravitational Lenses and Conical Feedhorns
thesis topic: Theoretical modeling of the amplification of submillimetre background radiation by the gravitational lensing of foreground galaxy clusters, and design considerations for conical feedhorns on SCUBA
supervisors: J.A. Peacock, W.K. Gear
1987: Bachelor of Mechanical Engineering (Honours with Distinction), McGill University
thesis: The Dynamics of a Tethered Platform in Orbit
supervisor: A.K. Misra

Positions

2007 – present: *Ingénieur de recherche* (Research Engineer)
Observatoire de Paris, France
2018-present *Hors Classe* (Exceptional Class)
2007-2018 *1^{re} classe* (First Class)
2019-present: QUBIC Calibration Scientist
2018-2022: Assistant Head of Group “Cosmology” at APC
2013-2017: SKA AAMID Consortium Project Scientist
2010-2012: Assistant Director, Nançay Radio Observatory
2006-2010: SKADS Project Scientist
2006 – 2007: SKADS Project Scientist
Observatoire de Paris, France
(funded by the European Commission Framework Programme 6)
2003 – 2006: Senior Research Associate
Arecibo Observatory, National Astronomy and Ionosphere Center, Cornell University
Puerto Rico, USA
2003-2006: ALFA Project Manager
2004-2005: Interim Head of Astronomy
2002 – 2003: Program Scientist for Space Astronomy
Canadian Space Agency, St-Hubert, Québec, Canada
1999 – 2002: Research Associate, and Adjunct Assistant Professor
Space Astronomy Laboratory, University of Calgary, Canada
(funded by the Canadian Space Agency)
1995 – 1999: Canadian Odin Instrumentation Scientist
Onsala Space Observatory, Gothenburg, Sweden
(funded by the Canadian Space Agency)
1991 – 1994: Research Associate
James Clerk Maxwell Telescope Group, Herzberg Institute of Astrophysics
National Research Council of Canada, Ottawa

Teaching experience

Courses

- 2020 & 2021:** Une histoire d'hydrogène neutre (A History of Neutral Hydrogen)
Université Ouverte de l'Université de Paris, Cycle "Histoire du Cosmos"
- 2010:** *Les bases de la radio astronomie* (Introduction to Radio Astronomy)
Université d'Orléans, Master *Electronique, Signal, Microsystèmes*
- 2004:** The Arecibo L-Band Feed Array
one of multiple lecturers for Cornell University course A620 (Masters level)

Summer Schools

- 2018:** Measuring the Cosmic Microwave Background
"Teaching the Universe" Athens, Greece
- 2015:**
 1. EMBRACE System Overview and Observational Highlights
 2. How to launch an EMBRACE observation
 3. How to look at EMBRACE statistics data
 4. Pulsar observations with EMBRACE
 5. How to write a python script for observing with EMBRACE
 6. How to setup a long term observational programme with EMBRACE
 EMBRACE Workshop at Nançay, 7-11 September, 2016
- 2014:** Radio Interferometry and the Square Kilometre Array
European Project INFIERI Summer School, held at Université de Paris-Diderot
- 2009:** The Driving Questions: Scientific Motivation for the Square Kilometre Array
European "Marie-Curie" Summer School held at Observatoire de Paris
- 2009:** Scientific Motivation and Multibeam Science
European "Marie-Curie" Summer School held at Oxford University
- 2008:** Scientific Motivation for Deep Field Imaging with the Square Kilometre Array
European "Marie-Curie" Summer School held at Cambridge University
- 2007:**
 1. History of Radio Astronomy
 2. The Square Kilometre Array and SKADS
 3. *Sur les traces de l'énergie sombre et de la masse manquante dans l'univers*
(Hunting for Dark Energy and the Missing Mass in the Universe)
 Summer School on Radioastronomy, *Ecole CNRS de Goutelas XXX*

Student Projects

- 2017 - present:** QUBIC data analysis
Masters internships
- 2017 - present:** "Penzias & Wilson from Paris"
Student project to measure the Cosmic Microwave Background (Prof. Michel Piat)
- 2016:** Low Frequency Molecular Transitions in the Foreground of Cosmology Surveys
Masters internship, joint programme between Imperial College London and Université de Strasbourg
- 2014:** Square Kilometre Array prototype EMBRACE
pre-engineering school internship
- 2012:** Square Kilometre Array prototype EMBRACE
pre-engineering school internship
- 2004:** Carbon Monoxide at High Redshift with the Arecibo radio telescope
Cornell University "Research Experience for Undergraduates"

Committees

- 2016 to present:** External member for the BINGO advisory committee
- 2010 to 2017:** member of the Scientific Council of the SKA-LOFAR Working Group (*Conseil Scientifique de l'Action Spécifique SKA-LOFAR*)
- 2011 to 2015:** External member for the Science & Technology Advisory Committee of the *Institut de Recherche en Astrophysique et Planétologie* (IRAP)
- 2013 to 2014:** CNRS National Institute for Science of the Universe, Astronomy and Astrophysics longterm plan 2015-2020, member of working group F, “Future Instruments and Research & Development” (*Institut National de Science de l'Univers, Astronomie et Astrophysique, La Prospective 2015-2020, Groupe de travail F, “Moyens du futur et R&D amont”*)
- 2011:** Coordinator for the working group on low frequency radio astronomy for the CNRS/INSU Research & Development Workshop

Publications – Book Editor

R. Strom, A. van Ardenne, and **Torchinsky, S.A.**(eds), “50 Years Westerbork Radio Observatory: A Continuing Journey to Discovery and Innovation,” 2018, ASTRON

Torchinsky, S.A., A. van Ardenne, T. van den Brink, A. van Es, and A.J. Faulkner (eds), 2009, “Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA,” PoS(SKADS-2009), ISBN 978-90-805434-5-4

Torchinsky, S.A.(ed.) “Proceedings of Simulations for the Square Kilometre Array, Pushchino, Russia 30 July - 1 August 2007,” December 2007

Publications – General Audience

Torchinsky, S.A., “St Augustin et le Big Bang,” (St. Augustine and the Big Bang) 2014, Bulletin Interne de l’Observatoire de Paris

Torchinsky, S.A., “En attendant SKA ...” (Preparing for SKA...) 2012, CNRS Microscop, No. 65

Torchinsky, S.A., “En attendant SKA, un prototype prometteur à Nançay, EMBRACE,” (Preparing for SKA: A Promising Prototype at Nançay) 2012, L’Astronomie, No, 46

Torchinsky, S.A. & Wim van Driel, “Révéler l’invisible par les ondes radio” (Unveiling the Invisible with Radio Waves), *Dossier Pour La Science*, #56, juillet, 2007

Publications – Refereed

Hamilton, J. -Ch., Mousset, L., and 128 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC I: Overview and Science Program”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 034H

Mousset, L., Gamboa Lerena, M. M., and 129 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC II: Spectro-Polarimetry with Bolometric Interferometry”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 035M

Torchinsky, S.A., Hamilton, J. -Ch., and 126 colleagues, 2022, “QUBIC III: Laboratory Characterization”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 036T

Piat, M., Stankowiak, G., and 127 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC IV: Performance of TES Bolometers and Readout Electronics”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 037P

Masi, S., Battistelli, E. S., and 127 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC V: Cryogenic system design and performance”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 038M

D’Alessandro, G., Mele, L., and 127 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC VI: cryogenic half wave plate rotator, design and performances”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 039D

Cavaliere, F., Mennella, A., and 129 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC VII: The feedhorn-switch system of the technological demonstrator”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 040C

O’Sullivan, C., De Petris, M., and 127 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2022, “QUBIC VIII: Optical design and performance”, 2022, *J. Cosmology & Astroparticle Phys.* 04, 041O

Scóccola, C. G., and 127 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2021, “Current status of the QUBIC experiment”, *Boletín de la Asociación Argentina de Astronomía*, vol. 62, pg. 177S

Gamboa Lerena, M. M., Scóccola, C. G., and 128 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2020, “Angular resolution at map level in the QUBIC instrument”, *Boletín de la Asociación Argentina de Astronomía*, vol. 61B, p.155-158

Mele, L., Ade, P., and 125 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2020, “The QUBIC instrument for CMB polarization measurements”, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Volume 1548, Issue 1, article id. 012016 (2020).

Publications – Refereed (cont'd)

- R. Ansari and 16 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Design, operation and performance of the PAON4 prototype transit interferometer” 2020, MNRAS, 493, 2965
- E.S. Battistelli and 138 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “QUBIC: The Q & U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology” 2020, J. Low Temp. Phys., 199, 482
- S. Marnieros and 138 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “TES Bolometer Arrays for the QUBIC B-Mode CMB Experiment” 2020, J. Low Temp. Phys.
- M. Piat and 138 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “QUBIC: using NbSi TESs with a bolometric interferometer to characterize the polarisation of the CMB” 2020, J. Low Temp. Phys.
- A. Mennella and 128 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “QUBIC: Exploring the Primordial Universe with the Q&U Bolometric Interferometer” 2019, Universe, vol. 5, issue 2, p. 42
- P. de Bernardis and 129 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “QUBIC: Measuring CMB polarization from Argentina,” 2018, BAAA, 60, 107B
- M. Salatino and 131 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Performance of NbSi transition-edge sensors readout with a 128 MUX factor for the QUBIC experiment,” 2018, SPIE, 10708E, 45S
- A. May and 129 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Thermal architecture for the QUBIC cryogenic receiver,” 2018, SPIE, 10708E, 3VM
- S. Das and 46 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Progress in the construction and testing of the Tianlai radio interferometers,” 2018, SPIE, 10708E, 36D
- C. O’Sullivan and 130 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Simulations and performance of the QUBIC optical beam combiner,” 2018, Proc. SPIE, 10708, 16
- C. O’Sullivan and 129 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “QUBIC: the Q and U bolometric interferometer for cosmology,” 2018, SPIE, 10708E, 2BO
- D. Burke and 133 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Optical modelling and analysis of the Q and U bolometric interferometer for cosmology,” 2018, Proc. SPIE, 10531, 14
- A. Mennella and 101 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “QUBIC - The Q&U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology – A novel way to look at the polarized Cosmic Microwave Background,” 2018, Proc. of Science, 314, 44
- A.O.H. Olofsson, L. Bouscasse, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Observation of the $2_{1,1} - 2_{1,2}$ transition of methanol at 2502.8 MHz in Sgr B2,” 2017, Research Notes of the AAS, 1, 46O
- Torchinsky, S.A.**, A.O.H. Olofsson, B. Censier, A. Karastergiou, M. Serylak, P. Picard, P. Renaud, C. Taffoureau, “Characterization of a dense aperture array for radio astronomy,” 2016, A&A, 589, A77
- Torchinsky, S.A.**, A.O.H. Olofsson, B. Censier, A. Karastergiou, M. Serylak, P. Renaud, C. Taffoureau, “EMBRACE@Nançay: An Ultra Wide Field of View Prototype for the SKA,” 2015, JINST, Vol. 10, No. 7, article id. C07002
- S. Bosse, S. Barth, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, B. da Silva, “BeamFormer ASIC in UHF-L band for the Square Kilometer Array international project,” 2010, Proceedings of the 40th European Microwave Conference, Paris, France

Publications – Refereed (cont'd)

B. Larsson, R. Liseau, L. Pagani, and 55 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** “The Discovery of Molecular Oxygen in the Interstellar Medium. O₂ Observed with Odin in the rho Ophiuchi Cloud” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 466, 999-1003 (2007),

A. Lecacheux, N. Biver, J. Crovisier, and 19 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** “Observations of water in comets with Odin” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, v.402, p.L55-L58 (2003)

Å. Hjalmarson, U. Frisk, M. Olberg, and 55 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** “Highlights from the first year of Odin observations”, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, v.402, p.L39-L46 (2003)

M. Olberg, U. Frisk, A. Lecacheux, and 13 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** “The Odin satellite II: Data processing and calibration” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, v.402, p.L35-L38 (2003)

U. Frisk, M. Hagström, J. Ala-Laurinaho, and 48 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** “The Odin satellite I: Radiometer design and test” *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, v.402, p.L27-L34 (2003)

W. Wild, J. Payne, V. Belitsky, and 11 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Receivers for ALMA: Preliminary Design Concepts”, *Proceedings of SPIE*, vol. 4015, “Radio Telescopes”, March 27-30, 2000, Munich, pp.320-327.

N.D. Whyborn, Th. de Graauw, H. van de Stadt, V. Belitsky, R. Kruisinga, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, H. Visser, K. Wildeman, “The Focal Plane Unit of the Heterodyne Instrument for FIRST: HIFI”, *Proceedings of the Ninth International Symposium on Space Terahertz Technology*, March 17-19, 1998, p.453-462

M.W. de Graauw, N.D. Whyborn, H. van de Stadt, and 38 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.** “Heterodyne instrument for FIRST (HIFI): preliminary design” in *Advanced Technology MMW, Radio, and Terahertz Telescopes SPIE Proceedings Vol. 3357* Editor(s): Thomas G. Phillips, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA, USA. ISBN:0-8194-2804-3, 1998, pp.336-347

Torchinsky, S.A., “Analysis of a Conical Horn Fed by a Slightly Oversized Waveguide,” *Int. J. Infrared and Millimeter Waves*, vol. 11, pp. 791-808, July 1990

Publications – Proceedings and Project Documents

Gunst, A. W., Faulkner, A. J., and 4 colleagues including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, 2020, “Mid Frequency Aperture Array Architectural Design Document”, eprint arXiv:2008.04583

Torchinsky, S.A. et al., “QUBIC - The Q & U Bolometric Interferometer for Cosmology” 2019, *URSI, Journées Scientifiques 2019*

C. Ferrari and 100 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “The SKA France White Book,” 2017, arXiv:1712.06950

W. van Cappellen, and 17 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “MANTIS: The Mid-Frequency Aperture Array Transient and Intensity-Mapping System,” 2016, arXiv:1612.07917

Torchinsky, S.A., J.W. Broderick, A. Gunst, A.J. Faulkner, W. van Cappellen, “SKA Aperture Array Mid Frequency Science Requirements”, 2016, SKA-TEL-MFAA-0200009, arXiv:1610.00683

J.G. bij de Vaate, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, A.J. Faulkner, Y. Zhang, A. Gunst, P. Benthem, I.M. van Bemmelen, G. Kenfack, “SKA Mid Frequency Aperture Arrays: Technology for the Ultimate Survey Machine” in *Proc. URSI General Assembly Beijing, China*, 16-23 August, 2014

J.G. bij de Vaate, P. Benthem, R. Witvers, R. van den Brink, Y. Zhang, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Mid Frequency Aperture Array Technology Developments for the SKA”, in *Proc. Antenna Technology and Applied Electromagnetics (ANTEM)*, Victoria, Canada, 13-16 July 2014

Publications – Proceedings and Project Documents (cont'd)

Torchinsky, S.A., A.O.H. Olofsson, A. Karastergiou, B. Censier, M. Serylak, P. Renaud, C. Taffoureau, “Characterization and Initial Results with EMBRACE,” 2013, Proc. Société française de l’astronomie et de l’astrophysique, 4-7 June, Montpellier

R. Weber, G. Hellbourg, C. Dumez-Viou, A.J. Boonstra, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, C. Capdessus, K. Abed-Meraim “RFI Mitigation in Radio Astronomy: an Overview,” 2013, Journée Scientifique d’URSI, 26-27 March, Paris

C. Taffoureau, P. Renaud, P. Picard, J. Borsenberger, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, A.O.H. Olofsson, F. Viallefond, “Monitoring and Control of EMBRACE, a 4608 Elements Phased Array for Radio Astronomy,” 2011, Proceedings Astronomical Data Analysis Software Systems, Paris, 6-10 November, 2011

Torchinsky, S.A., “Highlights of Radioastronomy from 1800 to 2007 (a personal selection),” 2011, Proceedings Radioastronomie Basses Fréquences Ecole CNRS de Goutelas XXX (2007) P. Zarka, M. Tagger (eds)

Torchinsky, S.A., “The Square Kilometre Array and SKADS,” 2011, Proceedings Radioastronomie Basses Fréquences Ecole CNRS de Goutelas XXX (2007) P. Zarka, M. Tagger (eds)

A.J. Faulkner, and 13 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Aperture Arrays for the SKA: The SKADS White Paper,” 2010, International SKA Memo #122,

Torchinsky, S.A., and 17 co-authors, “Final Astronomical Test Report for EMBRACE,” SKADS Deliverable, DS5-101, 22 February 2010

Torchinsky, S.A., “The Questions that Drive the Specifications”, 2009 *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, et al. (eds), PoS(SKADS 2009)004

A.O.H. Olofsson, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, and 14 co-authors, “Profiling the EMBRACE tile beam using GPS satellite carriers”, 2009 *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium,

Torchinsky, S.A., et al. (eds), PoS(SKADS 2009)042

S.J. Wijnholds and 8 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “EMBRACE: First Experimental Results with the Initial 10% of a 10,000 Element Phased Array Radio Telescope”, 2009 *Proc. Wide Field Science and Technology for the SKA*, Limelette, Belgium, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, et al. (eds), PoS(SKADS 2009)043

R.C. Bolton, A.J. Faulkner, P. Alexander, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, and 13 co-authors, “Design of an Aperture Phased Array System for the SKA” International SKA Memo 111, July 2009

S. Bosse, M.-L. Grima, G. Kenfack, and 18 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “R&D at Nançay for Radio Astronomy Detectors and Systems” Astrophysics Detector Workshop 2008 P. Kern (ed) EAS Publications Series, 37 (2009) 127-134

Torchinsky, S.A., A.O.H. Olofsson, L. Chemin, R. Strom, and 13 co-authors, “EMBRACE System Engineering and Astronomical Test Plan,” SKADS Deliverable DS5T3.2, 4 June 2008

A.J. Faulkner, P. Alexander, M.E. Jones, R.C. Bolton, A. van Ardenne, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Design of an Aperture Phased Array System for the SKA”, *Proc. 2008 URSI General Assembly, Chicago, 10-16 August, 2008*

Torchinsky, S.A. & SKADS, “Probing Dark Energy with the Square Kilometre Array”, *Proc. 19th Rencontres de Blois 20-25 May 2007*, L. Celnikier, J.T. Thanh Van eds., January, 2008

Torchinsky, S.A., “SKADS: The Square Kilometre Array Design Studies”, *Proc. Simulations for the Square Kilometre Array, Pushchino, Russia 30 July - 1 August 2007*, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, ed., December 2007

Publications – Proceedings and Project Documents (cont'd)

P. Alexander, R. Bolton, A.J. Faulkner, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, and 11 co-authors “SKADS Benchmark Scenario Design and Costing”, SKA Memo #93, June 2007

S.R. Golwala, and 13 co-authors including **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Sunyaev-Zeldovich Effect Science with the Cornell-Caltech Atacama Telescope”, AAS Meeting #211, id.91.18; Bulletin of the American Astronomical Society, Vol. 39, p.886, 2007

E. S. Howell, A.J. Lovell, B. Butler, F. P. Schloerb, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Radio OH Observations of Comet 9P/Tempel 1 before and after Deep Impact” AAS Division of Planetary Science, Poster 43.07, Cambridge, U.K., 4-9 September, 2005

S. Kwok, P. Bernath, T. Hasegawa, N. Koning, K. Volk, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, Å. Hjalmarsen, H. Olofsson, “The First Astronomical Spectrum of Orion KL between 555-573 GHz”, American Astronomical Society Meeting 205, #105.14, San Diego, January 9-13, 2005

Torchinsky, S.A. “Arecibo Software Development for Spectral Line Data Reduction”, Arecibo internal memo, 2004 October 5

Torchinsky, S.A., K. Volk, S. Kwok, “The Odin Satellite”, Proceedings of the Canadian Astronomical Society (CASCA), Penticton, B.C, 2002 May 11-14.

Torchinsky, S.A., M. Hagström, M. Fredrixon, I. Ristorcelli, C. Marty, N. Biver “Odin Telescope Beam Measurements at CESR-Toulouse 2000 September”, Odin Technical Report, November 16, 2000

S. Kwok, **Torchinsky, S.A.**, K. Volk, “Canadian Involvement in the Odin Mission” Canadian Astronomical Society Conference 2000, Vancouver, May 26-28 2000.

Torchinsky, S.A., “3d Optical Ray Tracing for the Odin Radiometer”, Odin Technical Report, 3 February 2000

Torchinsky, S.A., “Odin Radiometer Data Extraction and Plotting routines (software and help files),” Odin Technical Report June 15, 1999

Torchinsky, S.A. & V. Yu. Belitsky, “Optical Architecture for the HET on FIRST,” Proc. Far Infrared and Submillimetre Universe, Grenoble, April 1997

V. Yu. Belitsky & **Torchinsky, S.A.** “A Design for the HET Receiver on FIRST,” submitted to the FIRST Payload Working Group, May 1996

Torchinsky, S.A., C.T. Cunningham, & S.R. Davies, “A 690 GHz SIS Mixer,” in Frontiers of Space and Ground-Based Astronomy W. Wamsteker, M.S. Longair, Y. Kondo eds., pp. 723-4, 1994 Kluwer Academic Pub.

Torchinsky, S.A., “Hot Tip #904,” CADalyst Magazine, pp. 100 & 102, October 1993

Torchinsky, S.A., C.T. Cunningham & S.R. Davies, “Dixie D-Mixer,” The JCMT/UKIRT Newsletter, July 1993

A.K. Misra, V.J. Modi, & **Torchinsky, S.A.**, “Frequencies of Elastic Oscillations of a Tether-Platform System,” 13th Biennial Conference on Mechanical Vibration and Noise: Structural Vibration and Acoustics, DETC1991-0205, pp. 207-212, doi:10.1115/DETC1991-0205

Torchinsky, S.A., “Submillimetre Cosmology Experiments with a Bolometer Array,” Proceedings of the Young European Radio Astronomer Conference (YERAC) Khar'kov, Ukraine S.S.R., 4-9 September 1989